

Prepared by: Johan Couder, University of Antwerp

INTERLINKAGE AND SYNERGIES BETWEEN SELECTED OTHER POLICY AREAS AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY

D.1.3

PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

NATIONAL REPORT FOR BELGIUM

AUGUST 2015

HERON project

“Forward-looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries”

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors’ views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Universiteit
Antwerpen

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Contents

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS 3

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY 3

1.1.1 THE EMPLOYMENT-ENVIRONMENT ALLIANCE IN WALLONIA 3

1.1.2 THE VIAPASS SYSTEM 6

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY 10

1.2.1 SOCIAL HOUSING POLICY IN FLANDERS 10

1.2.2 FISCAL TREATMENT OF COMPANY CARS 14

REFERENCES 18

Table of Figures

Figure 1 Synergy between energy, climate and social policies 12

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.1.1 THE EMPLOYMENT-ENVIRONMENT ALLIANCE IN WALLONIA

Introduction

The Marshall Plan 2.Green in the Walloon Region was a 2.75 billion EUR initiative for the period 2009 to 2014. It aimed to ensure the region's sustainable development through promoting R&D, investment and training. The plan focused on six (6) Priority Areas: 1) enhancing Wallonia's human capital; 2) further developing the region's competitiveness clusters; 3) fostering scientific research; 4) creating new investment and job-creation incentives; 5) supporting the 'green' sector through the Employment-Environment Alliance, and 6) promoting the care industry.

The 5th Priority Area (Area V) of the Marshall Plan 2.Green was the so-called "*Employment-Environment Alliance*" (EEA). The targets of the EEA were to "*Support a new sustainable and united economic model through employment-environment alliances which constitute an opportunity in terms of employment, economic development and a response to environmental challenges*" and to "*Position Wallonia as a pioneer for sustainable development in Europe and worldwide, by providing it with an expertise that can be recognised and exploited abroad, while creating employment that cannot be relocated.*" [Walloon Region, 2011]

The EEA's principal objective was to "*focus on the potential of energy and environmental improvements in buildings to generate jobs, create economic opportunities and increase training especially in the field of sustainable construction jobs.*" [Walloon Region, 2011]

The approach was to gather the different efforts done in the sustainable construction field, in terms of policies for vocational training and integration, and for supporting SMEs. The main concrete objective was to create high-quality local jobs. This also meant answering two key bottlenecks:

- the saturation of the building companies that cannot answer to the increase in the demand for renovation works;
- the needs of continuing training to use up-to-date solutions (for the qualitative improvement of the works).

Relation to Energy Efficiency

The "Employment-Environment Alliance" (EEA) comprised five policies:

1. Launching the "First Alliance" through a multi-year energy saving and sustainable construction plan and a multisectoral contract;
2. Creating optimal conditions for development with a quality offer. This entailed developing innovation by promoting research projects and financing technology innovation partnerships in the sustainable construction sector; and implementing training initiatives for EEA jobs;

3. Improving the attractiveness of sustainable investments (“eco-investments”) in the housing industry. This included measures aimed at households (energy and housing subsidies and eco-loans, third party financing, communication strategies) and at the public sector (renovation of the public housing stock based on a land register of all housing, collective boiler rooms and large solar thermal systems, the “Rational use of Building Energy” (UREBA) plan for buildings within the Administration, pilot projects in eco-construction and eco-renovation, etc.);
4. Considering the opportunity to other employment-environment alliances;
5. Improving sectoral policies and initiatives in terms of research, economy, employment and training in other green job.

The choice to involve the building industry for the “First Alliance” was dictated on the one hand by the relative obsolescence of the Walloon housing stock, and on the other hand by the fact that the building industry constitutes a important sector of the Walloon economy.

The energy savings multi-annual plan (first dimension of the EEA) comprised some 50 measures defined around three specific objectives:

- Stimulation of *private* demand for sustainable renovation or construction;
- Stimulation of *public* demand for sustainable renovation or construction;
- Consolidation of the capacities on the supply side, mainly the construction sector.

Interaction between objectives

Through jobs creation, the EEA benefited 420,000 employees and 15,600 employers. One million EUR invested in the sector allowed the creation of 10 jobs in one year. On average, 4,700 jobs per year are linked to the EEA over the 2010-2014 period.

The Walloon energy administration estimates that in the 2009-2015 period 1.5 million tons of CO₂ were saved, of which 590,000 tons in the year 2014.

Interaction between target groups

The Agreement on the Sustainable Construction Axis gathered 50 private and public signatories. The process involved 130 organizations (52% public and 48% private). The actors in question elaborated 44 concrete actions aimed at education, training, technical references, research, support to companies, financing, labels ...

The EEA multi-annual plan engaged 44 partners who signed the multi-sectorial contracts.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

In order to reinforce the attractiveness of sustainable investments in the building sector, the EEA policies and measures focused on the demand side, the supply side and on the intersection of demand and supply.

On the demand side:

- Implementation of financial and non financial incentives, with particular attention given to low income households;
- Implementation of a public investment policy;
- Setting progressive environmental performance requirements.

On the supply side:

- Aid to companies;
- Promotion of Research and Development (R&D) in companies;
- Implementation of financial incentives and tools for companies;
- Setting progressive energy performance requirements;

At the intersection of supply and demand:

- Various audiences targeted by “green trainings” (jobseekers, students or youngsters, workers, trainers);
- Training devices adapted to those different audiences. .

The most important measures in budgetary terms were

- actions aimed at creating a high-quality offer through innovation, training actions on alliance skills, and the creation of Employment Creation Support (APE) / Vocational Transition Programmes (PTP);
- actions relating to sustainable investment in Walloon housing through specific measures aimed at private individuals and at the public sector;
- actions relating to sector policies in areas of green jobs research, economics, training and creation;
- the other measures in the ‘green’ area are marginal (in monetary terms) compared to those mentioned above, namely: a multi-annual plan setting quantitative objectives and environmental standards and a multi-sectoral contract; and the action “other alliances”).

The following measures of the EEA were assessed:

- Subsidies and loans intended for private housing; ;
- Measures intended to restart the renovation of the public building stock;
- “Green training”.

The results were as follows [IWEPS, 2014]:

- Household demand for sustainable renovation works is highly sensitive to changes of the technical and financial conditions relating to the incentive systems. Overly abrupt or too frequent changes of the legislation are likely to induce erratic variations of the demand. This is harmful for the expansion of the building sector, who rather needs stability to thrive;
- The proportion of the subsidized works carried out by lower-income households remains weak in the light of their weight within the Walloon population. A difference in access to natural materials or to materials with higher insulating properties exists depending on the income category to which the applicant belongs, with an appreciably higher probability of those materials being used for the higher income households;
- The windfall effects of the “Ecopack” measure seems closely related to the income category to which the household belongs. Whereas none of the households of the lowest income category said that financed works would have been carried out in the absence of the measure, this proportion reaches practically 20% for the higher-income households;
- The majority of the companies involved in the sectors a by the EEA measures said that they needed to be trained on the new energy-saving techniques and materials. However, among those, the majority was unaware of the training-cheque system proposed by EEA. The need

to make this measure known is all the more relevant as the companies that have used it seem to be overall satisfied by the experience.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

The EEA coordination was managed by the Ministry of Sustainable Development, Public Service, Energy, Housing and Research. A coordination cell mandated with the implementation of the multi-annual plan and multi-sectorial contracts was part of the administration services. Its mission was to elaborate evaluation and impact indicators of the EEA. The cell was under direct authority of the Minister mandated with EEA coordination, who organized the implementation and works.

The ministers had a decisional power on all measures of the multi-annual plan. The majority of the executive power (27 measures) was delegated to Walloon public actors, and the rest was scattered between extra-regional public actors, private sector companies federations, other private sector actors, associative sector actors, clusters, and training centres. Administrative or budgetary management was entirely in the hands of Walloon public actors.

The area devoted entirely to the employment-environment alliance (Area V) represented an investment of 879.6 million EUR over four years (almost one-third of the total Marshal Plan 2.Green investment, and nearly 70% of the total green initiatives). This area was made up of 279 million EUR of ordinary financing and 600 million EUR of alternative financing. Alternative financing comprises 'loans taken out by third party institutions and the interest and write down of which are partly or wholly covered by the Walloon Region, for the whole duration of the loan.' One of these third-party institutions was the Société Wallonne pour la Gestion d'un Financement Alternatif (SOWAFINAL).

The EEA project realized returns that (in the mid and long term) benefit federal, regional and local public finances, through value added tax (VAT) revenues, corporate tax, individual income tax, local taxes, Social Security National Office contributions, reduction of unemployment benefits, etc. The return effects are estimated at 40% of the direct public investment.

1.1.2 THE VIAPASS SYSTEM

Introduction

In Belgium, 4.7 billion truck-kilometres are annually driven by Belgians, and 3.5 billion by foreigners.

A tax per kilometre is to be implemented for all trucks weighing over 3.5 tonnes throughout Belgium from 1 April 2016.

In early 2011, the three Belgian regions reached an agreement on the introduction of an intelligent road pricing for trucks over 3.5 tons and a vignette for cars. Originally the idea was to introduce both systems in 2013, but this was found not to be feasible. It was decided in 2013 that the proposed vignette for all vehicles under 3.5 tonnes will not proceed, as the three Belgian regional governments look at alternative solutions (e.g. a pilot trial of distance charging for cars in Brussels, see supra).

The Agreement establishes the inter-regional institution Viapass, responsible for all government tasks related to road charging. Some examples:

- Overseeing the work of the Single Service Provider.
- Monitoring and controlling the financial flows of the toll system.
- Adapting the toll network where needed (cf. to avoid unwanted traffic diversions).
- Operational coordination of enforcement of the system, including detection of fraudulent drivers via technological means.

The system will be based on satellite technology, using on board units (OBUs), which drivers will collect at a distribution point. Each truck will get an On-Board Unit (OBU), an electronic device using GPS technology and wireless networks. The OBU will register the distance travelled by the vehicle and on which roads. Mileage data will be transmitted to a data centre and an invoice generated, which the driver will pay on returning the OBU.

The kilometre charge for trucks will replace the existing Eurovignette based on satellite technology.

The tariff levels have not yet been decided. Toll rates by European law must not exceed the proportion of infrastructure costs fairly attributable to the vehicles being charged, and a calculated charge for *environmental externalities* (which has to be justified). The rate of road pricing will vary depending on the maximum permissible weight of the trucks, their Euro emission class and type of the road being used.

The charge will be applied to a road network including the current Eurovignette network, consisting of Belgium's highways, the orbital roads around the main cities, and a number of other important routes. Belgium will withdraw from the trans-national "Eurovignette" charge, which is a prepaid pass for using the major highway networks in Belgium, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Denmark and Sweden. So it is a replacement of an existing charge, although the Eurovignette only applies to trucks 12 tonnes and over, whereas this charge covers them down to 3.5 tonnes. The Regions can include more roads in their networks to avoid traffic diversions to roads without a toll [[Scott Wilson, roadpricing.blogspot.be, 17.04.2014](#)].

Relation to Energy Efficiency

The primary aim of the new road charging system Viapass is to make those that use the roads pay for them. This means that once the system is introduced foreign truckers that use the Belgian roads will also pay towards their upkeep. This is likely to increase revenue from foreign trucks [[Scott Wilson, roadpricing.blogspot.be, 17.04.2014](#)].

The aim of road pricing in general however is to confront road users with the marginal external costs they impose on society. The rate of road pricing in the Viapass system will thus vary depending on, amongst others, the Euro emission class.

According to Viapass, for the three Regions of Belgium, the Viapass project will mark a permanent transition towards a fairer and more *sustainable* way of road pricing [[viapass.be](#)].

Interaction between objectives

The Flemish mobility minister promised accompanying measures for the sectors affected by the toll. "Among other things, we're thinking of extra investments in the road network and incentives for safer trucks," he said [[Flanderstoday.eu, 16/02.2015](#)].

Interaction between target groups

The target groups are drivers of (heavy duty) trucks versus drivers of cars and vans. There is at present no charge for light vehicles in Belgium.

The Brussels-Capital Region estimates to decrease truck traffic on its roads considerably, but this is contested by MOBI's professor Cathy Macharis ([interview with Cathy Macharis on brusselsnieuws.be, 13.02.2015](#)). As the Viapass measure only affects trucks, it is extremely likely that the trend will move towards a higher usage of small vans, which are more polluting when taking all proportions into account. In addition, the kilometre tax does not consider peak and off-peak hours, a discouraging sign towards the pilot projects (see supra) in Flanders and Brussels on night-time deliveries. Finally, questions are raised concerning the revenues of the measure, for which no specific objective has been communicated.

The federation FEBIAC insists that *cars* should also be subject to a kilometre charge, with a variable rate based on the duration, location and environmental impact of a vehicle's movement (fleeteurope.com, 16.07.2013). The federation believes that a smart distance-based charge offers an ideal way of improving mobility, but at the same time it is convinced that a charge of this kind will only be accepted by the public if certain criteria are met. These criteria include the reform and reorganisation of taxation in the area of mobility.

A consortium of companies including Touring, Mobistar, Magic View, NSL, NXP, IBM and the Belgian consultancy Transport and Mobility Leuven (TML) conducted a study in 2011-2012 in the City of Leuven on how Flemish driving behaviour would change if the driver is compelled to pay for every kilometre on the road [[TML, press release, 15.02.2012](http://tmleuven.be), tmleuven.be]. The system was tested out amongst 30 drivers in Leuven, who were issued with a fictional invoice and had to try and drive as cheaply as possible. The results of the 11,000 test drives, totalling 100,000 kilometres, were very clear. *“During the test drives over half of the subjects changed their driving behaviour”*, said Sven Maerivoet of TML [expatica.com, 16.02.2012]. Road pricing would lead to a five percent decrease in rush hour rat-run traffic and a 30 percent cut in personal excursions during the busiest times of the day.

In 2013, Brussels and Antwerp were named the worst places for traffic congestion, The Pilot project on kilometre charge for cars in the Brussels Regional Express Network (BREN) zone is a scientific study to measure the influence of road charging [[Mayeres, 2015](#)]. It was commissioned by Belgium's three regions: the Flemish Region, the Walloon Region and the Brussels Capital Region. The multidisciplinary research team included PwC as coordinator, VITO for the scientific approach and analysis of the results, Touring for its expertise on Belgian mobility (Touring was also the first contact point for the participants, via its helpdesk facilities); Magicview for the technical aspects (on-board units; website for the participants; back office); and GfK Belgium for the recruitment of a representative sample of participants. The scheme involved installing special satellite navigation equipment in the cars to record every journey and calculate how much it would cost. They gave the drivers a virtual wallet and charged 9 cents/km in the city, 5 cents/km on motorways and 6.5 cents/km elsewhere. The first report from the pilot scheme, which measured 1,000 motorists, revealed that they would cut back on car use and look for alternative modes of transport including bike and public transport. Car use in and around Brussels fell by an average of 5.5% during the pilot scheme. There was an 8% reduction of car-kilometres in urban areas with higher km-charge, but a 4% increase outside the BREN zone. Some drivers also changed the time of their journey and their destination. In the peak period car-kilometres decreased by 3.6% and the number of trips by 2%. The most frequently chosen alternatives, as stated by the participants, were walking/cycling; combining trips, or changing shopping behaviour (cheaper periods of day or closer to home). The behavioural effects may be larger with a definitive roll-out on a larger scale, because in the project only short run effects were measured; it was a temporary project so the urge to find new solutions was smaller, the level of the kilometre-charges was rather low; as a more attractive alternative become available, the price elasticity would increase. [[Mayeres, 2015](#)]

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

Road pricing is an essential part of a broader package, namely the supply of public transport and infrastructure for other modes; the correct pricing for public transport and for parking (“parking charges”); fuel and car taxation; and company car taxation and labour taxes.

According to VITO [[Mayeres, 2015](#)], there are a number of problems with the current policy instruments to tackle congestion and to help realize a modal shift.

- Fuel taxes make no distinction between the peak and off-peak period. There is no distinction either between less and more polluting vehicles. They may also lead to “fuel tourism”. Fuel

tax is completely absent from the debate in Belgium. In part, because fuel tax is mandatory under EU law, but also because it is a Federal matter. However, the platform nationwide road charging would create to partially replace fuel tax in Belgium does beg the question as to whether there would be efficiencies in doing so.

- Parking charges can at best be used as a second-best policy instrument to tackle congestion.
- Public transport subsidies are a good policy instrument, on the condition that 1) the price of private transport is too low and cannot be changed; 2) that the subsidies encourage a large number of people to switch from private transport to public transport on links in periods with a lot of congestion; the own price elasticity of public transport is limited; there is a differentiation of subsidies according to trip purpose. Furthermore, subsidies need to be financed.

"Efforts by government and businesses have had limited effect", professor Ann Verhetsel of the University of Antwerp says in reference to carpooling and telecommuting (working from home), which were presented as solutions to the traffic problem since the beginning of 2000 [[The Bulletin, 04.08.2014](#)]. Professor Verhetsel therefore urges support for road pricing: *"The only solution is to make driving more expensive, much more expensive. Only then will we make the switch to public transport or the bicycle. Other countries have shown that a financial measure, combined with a strong expansion of public transport, does have an effect."* [[The Bulletin, 04.08.2014](#)].

Transport & Environment also says that a kilometre charge is a more effective way to cut congestion and emissions than a congestion charge which some users simply get used to. *"We prefer the kilometre charges because if you pay a one-off fee you're incentivized to maximize your driving within that period,"* said Transport & Environment's Renshaw [[Reuters, Philip Blankinsop, 27.04.2014](#)].

Bruno De Lille, Green Party member and mobility secretary for the Brussels region, points out that Belgium has a tax system that encourages company cars and compensates the cost of driving to work, with the former taxed at a lower rate than salaries and the latter able partially to be offset against tax. So far Brussels has tried to fight traffic creep by making public transport more attractive with special bus or tram lanes. That has worked by convincing many commuters to switch to public transport or bicycles, but has also created its own problems. *"What we've seen in the last 10 years is that we've got 7 percent fewer cars on the roads, but the jams have got longer. That's because there's less room for cars"*, De Lille said [[Reuters, Philip Blankinsop, 27.04.2014](#)].

FEBIAC thinks that road pricing measures should ultimately replace existing taxes on mobility (i.e. vehicle tax, annual road taxes, excise duties). This simplification could be fiscally neutral: the average road user wouldn't need to pay more – if they adapt their driving behaviour. On a macro-economic level, road pricing could be made to be financially neutral at the moment of transition from the old to the new system. [[fleeteurope.com, 16.07.2013](#)]

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

The three Regions of Belgium signed a Cooperation Agreement for the charging system for Heavy Goods Vehicles on December 2, 2013. The introduction of the kilometre charge for HCVs is based on this Agreement.

Governance of the Viapass scheme is such that governance will be by all three Belgian regions; Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels, and not by the Federal Government. All regions will be separately liable for the payment of availability fees to the supplier, with that service provider responsible for the end-to-end charging service and fraud control.

None of this is being done at the Federal level, but instead by all three constituent regional governments. It creates obvious risks for any service provider, having a contract with three

governments in parallel. *“However, if it works it will show a somewhat different model for governance of these sorts of systems.”* [Scott Wilson, roadpricing.blogspot.be, 17.04.2014]

The application by the City of Leuven for subsidies for the pilot project on road pricing in the City of Leuven was refused by the Flemish Government. The City of Leuven went ahead with its own resources. The reasons for the Flemish Government’s refusal are unknown.

The congestion in the Brussels-Capital Region has had the effect of uniting Belgium's environmentalist Green Party, centre-right rivals N-VA and business and motoring groups in a call for a solution whose time may finally have come - charging drivers for distance travelled. The idea of a road pricing is backed by the Flemish nationalist party N-VA, currently the largest party in parliament, albeit balanced against reductions of annual road tax, as well as business bodies, the Belgian auto federation FEBIAC and Touring. [Reuters, Philip Blenkinsop, 27.04.2014]

The Belgian auto federation FEBIAC asked the consultancy PwC to examine the feasibility of the proposals and calculate their impact on the existing mobility budget. The results were published in a report, *“Smart taxation for improved mobility (“Slimme fiscaliteit voor betere mobiliteit”)*. [PwC, 2013] The report concludes that there is in fact no reason why improved mobility would imply higher costs for users and the state.

“In Belgium, the tax rules in the area of mobility are extremely complex”, states Thierry van Kan, Chairman of the Belgian auto federation FEBIAC, *“and we’re proposing that they be reformed and reorganised, by making changes to the way in which the budget is funded and spent. This will make it possible to influence the behaviour of users in a way that has a positive impact on mobility.”* [PwC, press release, Brussels 22.10.2013] The proposal comprises three key tax shifts, which affect income and spending [PwC, 2013]:

- ⋮ Currently, more than 50% of government income in the area of mobility is derived from taxes based on ownership. Moving towards taxing usage (the distance travelled) will encourage the use of appropriate means of transport at appropriate times, making it possible to reduce the cost to society in terms of the environment and congestion;
- ⋮ In order to gain support for any moves to base the taxation of mobility increasingly on usage, it is vital road users are given guarantees that the associated income for the government will at the very least be used to improve and maintain the road network;
- ⋮ In addition to placing a greater focus on the quality of the road infrastructure, it is also vital to develop co-modal transport solutions. These are necessary in order to compensate and offer alternatives to those who are unable or unwilling to pay to use the road infrastructure.

According to the Belgian auto federation FEBIAC, the proceeds of road pricing should first and foremost go towards improving and expanding the existing road infrastructure. But a Belgium-wide system of road pricing can only come into effect if and when there is sufficient agreement and cooperation between the three regions (Flanders, Brussels and Wallonia) [PwC, press release, Brussels 22.10.2013].

It should be noted that fuel tax is absent from the debate, partly because it is (still) a federal matter [Scott Wilson, roadpricing.blogspot.be, 17.04.2014].

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.2.1 SOCIAL HOUSING POLICY IN FLANDERS

Introduction

In Flanders (and Belgium), strategies of stimulating home ownership through direct and indirect measures have for more than a century played a far more important role than social protection in the field of housing. Housing is thus less seen as a social right but more as an individual responsibility, albeit with strong financial support from the government [Cools & Oosterlynck, 2015].

In the Flemish Region applicants for social dwellings have to register with local providers on the basis of income, and are consequently selected on the basis of chronological registration and availability.

The Flemish Government promises to invest more money in social rental dwellings, based on earlier conclusions that the social rental sector is too small. Social housing in Flanders covers 6% of the housing stock. The regional “Support Organisation for Social Housing” (VMSW) estimated in 2011 that almost half of all Flemish tenants were eligible to rent a social dwelling.

The Flemish Government eased the requirements for receiving the free Flemish housing expenses insurance, including dropping most of the income requirements.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Income poverty and energy poverty are strongly related, but they are not synonyms [Cools & Oosterlynck, 2015].

The most prominent causes of energy poverty are a low income in relation to the expenditures required to satisfy elementary needs; low energy efficiency of the dwelling; a situation of health and employment where one is “forced” to stay at home; and rising energy prices. The possible consequences are hardship; debt; possible long-term negative effects on health; a bad condition of the house, and social exclusion [Huybrechts et al, 2011].

There are no statistics available in Flanders that allow to link data on low-income households to data on households’ energy consumption and housing quality.

Interaction between objectives

Housing policies that target structural problems of the houses have potentially negative social effects. The King Baudouin Foundation observed that strategies that focus on implementing relatively high quality criteria, using the Energy Performance Certificate (“*Energie Prestatie Certificaat – EPC*”), risk broadening the gap between vulnerable tenants and the rest of society instead of closing it. [Koning Boudewijnstichting, 2013].

The identification of energy poverty by local welfare centres or social organisations often coincides with the emergence of problems of debt to private energy providers. The Federal approach to fight energy poverty can best be summarized as ‘protecting the consumer’ (Meyer & Huybrechts, 2012). When an energy provider drops a client, the client will automatically be provided energy at a ‘social rate’ for gas and electricity by the grid manager. But the prices of this social rate are often higher than the lowest prices on the free market. This tends to aggravate the debt problem. The grid manager cannot simply drop clients. When a client cannot pay the grid manager, he has to appear before the Local Advisory Commission (LAC), who decide on payment, the possible installation of a budget meter, or in extreme cases being cut off. The local welfare centres (OCMW) coordinate these measures. Such measures are at best “curative”.

Energy efficiency (EE) policies, climate policies and (social) housing policies are linked, but actions in one domain are not necessarily positive for the other domains. There is a continual search for trade-offs and synergy between energy, climate and social policies. [Verbeeck, 2014]

Figure 1 Synergy between energy, climate and social policies

Source: [Verbeek, 2014]

Interaction between target groups

The target groups are all households affected by energy policy and the subset of households targeted by social housing policies.

In the Flemish Region, households in energy poverty are often private renters living in older dwellings; with a below average income; with a lower than average education level; and very often single or single parent families. In many cases, the energy quality of their dwellings is also below the Flemish average.

There is always the danger that energy and social policies in the Flemish Region may widen the gap between poor families and other households. The threats are [Verbeek, 2014]:

- ⋮ Limited energy savings measures for low-income families could lead to a lock-in effect. The low-income households (including the energy poor) would increase their thermal comfort rather than lowering their energy consumption (“rebound effect”), while the underutilisation of the energy savings potential would make future investments much harder and less economically viable;
- ⋮ The existing policies could lead to increasing inequality between those households living in highly energy efficient dwellings and those living in less energy efficient dwellings;
- ⋮ The social energy-related policy measures are based on net energy consumption. That way, the contribution of lower-income households to the financing of those measures is relatively higher than for higher income households.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

The “Fund for the Reduction of Global Energy cost” (FRGE) provides soft loans to support households, and low-income households in particular, in improving the quality of their homes and to lower their energy bills. FRGE was originally a Federal enterprise, but devolved to the Regions on 1 January 2015.

In the Flemish Region, the grid managers are obligated to provide a number of public services within the Rational Use of Energy (RUE) framework (“Rationeel Energiegebruik” - REG). This includes a variety of services for ‘protected customers’ or vulnerable households such as a range of financial premiums for energy efficiency improvements.

In several Flemish municipalities, social enterprises called “Energy Savers” (“*energiesnoeiers*”) install small energy saving equipment compact fluorescent lamps, radiator foil, water saving shower heads and so on) in private homes, and train and employ disadvantaged people to do this.

Social workers of “Samenlevingsopbouw” who inform people about energy policy measures, experience that those policy instruments are often not accessible to lower income households [Cools & Oosterlynck, 2015].

In 2015, The Flemish Government promised to work on:

- A thorough evaluation and simplification of the social rent rules. In future, rent price calculations for social housing should also take into account renovation and energy performance of the dwelling and the income of the occupant.
- Improving participation of the target group “energy poor” in (social) housing policy-making;

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

Since 1980, social housing in Belgium is a regional competence. Differences exist between the Regions, not only in housing policies, but also in the average building year of residences, the overall quality of the housing stock and the ways in which people heat their house [Meyer & Huybrechts, 2012].

In Flanders, a dwelling is considered a “social rental dwelling” if an accredited social housing landlord lets the dwelling. Accreditation is the responsibility of the “Regional Support Organisation for Social Housing (“*Vlaamse Maatschappij voor Sociaal Wonen*”- VMSW). Accredited landlords include the “Social Housing Company” (“*Sociale huisvestingsmaatschappij*” - SHM), but also municipalities and the “Public Centres for Social Welfare” (“*Openbaar Centrum voor Maatschappelijk Welzijn*” - OCMW).

In 1997, the Flemish Housing Code broadened the definition of social landlord, to include dwellings that are let by Social Rental Agencies (“*Sociale Verhuurkantoren*” - SVK) . These agencies offer social rental houses or apartments to vulnerable households as intermediary between private owner-landlords and low-income households.

The Housing Code also charged local authorities with the task of organising broad consultations with stakeholders to coordinate their activities in the fields of housing and welfare. However, local authorities have little responsibilities concerning social housing, unless they are the owners themselves.

The Flemish financing system for social rental and owner-occupier housing entered into force on 1 January 2013 (Decree on Financing of Social Housing).

Via the Decree the funds of the Flemish Government are paid to the regional support organization VMSW (“*Vlaamse Maatschappij voor Sociaal Wonen*”) which allocates the subsidies in three ways to investors in social housing:

- help in the payment of the debt;
- project subsidies;
- help to the pre-financing of those taking the initiative for social housing projects.

It is only since May 2014 that the rent legislation and housing subsidies were also devolved to the regional level.

1.2.2 FISCAL TREATMENT OF COMPANY CARS

Introduction

In Belgium company cars are fiscally deductible. An individual who drives around in a company car is almost always taxed as a private individual on a benefit of 5,000 km multiplied by a certain CC factor. In most cases, this will come down to an amount of EUR 1,000 on which the employee is taxed as a private individual. This is regardless of the type of car or mileage [De Hoon, s.d.¹]. That helps explain why 68% of the Belgian employees use a company car for commuting. Why would they bother to look for more environmentally-friendly alternatives (modal shift)?

The heart of the matter is that in Belgium it is cheaper for companies to give their employees a car instead of higher wages, because the employees have to pay fewer taxes on the (company) car. In other words, company cars are a relatively easy and cheap way to reward employees for their performance, in the absence of a reduction of taxes on labour [Schoefs, 2015²].

An employer may give an employee a company car to raise worker productivity (which in reality only true for a limited number of company cars); because of image building; or as a response to the implied subsidies offered (to both workers and firms) by the government. It is not so clear however why a government would want to subsidize cars ! [De Borger, 2012]

A increasing number of people in Belgium are questioning the use of company cars, out of mobility and environmental concerns. Belgium should move progressively towards the elimination of the special fiscal treatment of company cars.

The current policy reforms include:

- the tax advantage for an employee is no longer based on commuting distance;
- the tax advantage for an employee is based on CO₂, value and age of the car;
- extra tax on firms [17% on benefits in kind (“Voordeel van Alle Aard” - VAA)].

CO₂ solidarity contribution (Federal Level)

At the end of 2011, the rules applied on company cars for calculating the taxable benefit in kind shifted from the parameter “fiscal horsepower” (mostly based on the size of the engine) to a combination of CO₂ emissions and the value of the car.

When an employer provides a company car to an employee that can be used for private purposes, a solidarity contribution by the employer to the national office of social security is due. This monthly contribution depends on the vehicle’s CO₂ emissions and type of fuel, and is a fixed amount. The amount is also linked to the health index of September 2004 and is adjusted each year in January. The indexation coefficient is 1.2051 with effect from 1 January 2015 [KBC, 2015 Tax Brochure Company Cars].

“Green” vehicle registration tax (Flemish Region). The vehicle registration tax is a one-off tax that is collected when a new or used passenger car, dual-purpose vehicle, minibus or motorcycle is registered for use on public roads by one particular person. On 1 March 2012, a new rate scale came into force for vehicle registration tax in the Flemish Region. The new calculation is based on type of fuel, age and a number of environmental features of the vehicle such as CO₂ emissions and engine

¹ Retrieved from www.spaarbelastingen.be, August 2015.

² Retrieved from www.fleeteurope.com, August 2015.

euros standard. However, the tax for leased company cars that are put on the road by certain leasing companies is still calculated on the basis of the power of the engine expressed in kW and the age of the vehicle.

Ecomalus (Walloon Region). Since 1 January 2008, the Walloon region applies a CO₂-based Ecobonus/-malus scheme for registering a car (company cars excluded). The „éco-bonus“ and „éco-malus“ system was tightened in 2012. As of 1 January 2012, cars emitting less than 81 g CO₂/km receive a premium-um („éco-bonus“) of 500 EUR to 3,500 EUR. Cars emitting more than 146 g CO₂/km pay a penalty („éco-malus“) of up to 2,500 EUR. On 1 January 2014, the Walloon government abolished the „éco-bonus“.

The recent policy reform is a step in the right direction. The current reform however is inspired by budgetary needs, not by energy, transport, climate or labour policies. Further reforms would have to include a further reduction of the implicit subsidies to company cars [De Borger, 2012].

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Company cars do not face monetary incentives to reduce (or even) monitor their fuel consumption, thus lessen the concern for energy efficiency.

The implications of providing company cars include [De Borger, 2012]:

- an increase in the car stock, with a shift towards cars in the “upmarket segments” (size, engine power, extra’s, etc.);
- an increase in car-kilometres, because company cars are more intensively used than private cars;
- an increase in congestion;
- effects on other external costs of transport, such as an increase in pollution as well as accidents.

The OECD Economic Surveys Belgium report, published on 4 February 2015, took aim at Belgium’s generous tax breaks for corporate vehicles. *“Massive commuting, subsidised through several tax expenditures in personal and corporate income taxes, raises transport emissions and, in urban areas, congestion and air pollution”* [OECD, 2015, p. 23].

Interaction between objectives

The current implicit government subsidies to company cars would require very high congestion charges, and would also justify “free” public transport [De Borger, 2012].

An optimal tax treatment of company cars would imply less company cars, a decline in car-kilometres, congestion, and pollution levels; and an increase in public transport [De Borger, 2012].

Interaction between target groups

The target groups are the Flemish commuters, with those who wish to keep the benefits of using a company car against those who wish to decrease the use of company cars, and of cars in general.

End 2014, three Belgian NGO’s, the “Federation for a Better Environment” (“Bond Beter Leefmilieu”), the “Flemish League against Cancer” (“Kom op tegen Kanker” and the “Sustainable Mobility Network” (“Netwerk Duurzame Mobiliteit”) started a petition against company cars, collecting 25,000 signatures. Belgium at the time was in the midst of a political debate about shifting taxes from labour to consumption and pollution. A big element of the petition was a call for company car subsidies to be used to fund lower labour taxes. The petition received support from leading economics professors and all the leading national newspapers. The Federal Government in the end reacted by saying the policy around company cars will remain unchanged for the time being.

Three Belgian car federations, “[FEBIAC](#)” (Belgian Federation of the Car and Two-wheeler Industries), [Féderauto](#) (now TRAXIO) and [Renta](#) (Belgian federation of rental and lease companies), commissioned KPMG to study the different aspects of company cars. The report, published on June 12, 2012, concluded that [[KPMG, 2012](#)]:

- Company cars are generally more environmentally friendly than privately-owned cars, as they are replaced, on average, every three or four years ;
- Company cars do not drive significantly more kilometres annually, compared to privately owned cars, except when used for professional purposes;
- When evaluating an increase in taxation and comparing the regime with the neighbouring countries, the authorities should take into account the existing high tax and social security burden in Belgium;
- Company car policies are favouring vehicles with low CO₂ emissions and are integrating tools that measure the ecological footprint of the fleet.

FEBIAC also points out that Belgian motorists have no alternative to commuting by car, because of Belgium’s lack of a coherent public transport offering. The Belgian public transportation system lacks connectivity and has a poor timeliness record. Furthermore, company cars as “a tool of the trade” are comparatively “over-taxed”. FEBIAC furthermore points out that company cars ‘only’ comprise 20% of Belgium’s total fleet of 5.4 million [[fleeteurope.com, 05.02.2015](#)].

Most tax payers in the meanwhile have dealt with the tax increase of 2011 in an intelligent way. They choose a combination between a reasonable car value and a low CO₂ emission, thus reducing the taxable car benefit to the pre 2012 values or even below [[Jan Lambrechts, Ichiban consult blog, 29.10.2014](#)].

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

An optimal tax policy would consist of 1) introducing congestion charges (see D1.2.1); 2) an “optimal” tax treatment of company cars; and 3) a reduction in labour taxes.

An „optimal tax reform“ would therefore imply a combination of measures [[De Borger, 2012](#)]:

- reducing the implicit subsidies to company cars;
- introducing a form of „road“ or „congestion“ pricing;
- reducing the tax pressure on labour;
- offer sufficient alternatives to the car, including more efficient public transport.

The Flemish Social Environment Association (“*Bond Beter Leefmilieu*” - BBL) and an organisation for sustainable mobility “*Mobiel 21*”, in cooperation with the sustainable mobility organisation “*Traject*”, Labour & Environment (“*Arbeid & Milieu*”) and other stakeholders) investigated the idea of a “multi-modal mobility budget”, allowing an employee to spend it on a large range of transportation means. The study concluded that administrative burden and extra wage costs for the employer and the wage loss for the employee should be avoided. However, the system should not be made compulsory. Employers should be able to choose the system they deem best. Trade Unions defend the employee’s right to choose and even quit the system if they wish [[BBL, 2010](#)].

The European Automobile Manufacturers Association (ACEA) welcomes the trend towards CO₂-related car taxation in the EU. However, it regrets the lack of uniformity in the implementation of these taxes. They support taxation for passenger cars that is exclusively based on CO₂ emissions; technologically neutral; linear; and budget neutral [[ACEA, 27.03.2015](#)].

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

Vehicle registration taxes are a Regional competence. The fiscal treatment of company cars is a Federal competence.

Subsidizing company cars constitutes a large budgetary cost for the Federal Government. A Danish study calculated that the Belgian Government spends 1.2% of their GDP (about 4.1 billion euro) on a favourable taxation environment for company cars. The high cost of the funds implies that the welfare costs are even much higher [[Copenhagen Economics, 2010](#)].

End 2014, the Belgian finance minister stated that the fiscal system favouring company cars was the 'prototype' of rules to be reconsidered within the framework of a 'tax shift' away from the heavy burden on labour in Belgium. But he also warned that the rules benefiting corporate mobility were very complex – precisely because of their inverse relation to high personal taxes – and should not be amended in haste [[Press Communication, 02-12-2014](#)] [[fleeteurope.com, 02.12.2014](#)]. He later commented that a revision of company car tax benefits in Belgium is not on the agenda.

REFERENCES

- BBL (2010), Multimodaliteit in het woon-werkverkeer, Op weg naar een multimodaal mobiliteitsbudget? Eindverslag, Bond Beter Leefmilieu, April 2010.
- Cools, P. & Oosterlynck, S. (2015), Energy poverty and social entrepreneurship: Strengthening prefinancing models for energy efficient electrical appliances through the 'Energy for All' programme, ImPROvE Case Study N°13. Antwerp: Herman Deleeck Centre for Social Policy – University of Antwerp.
- Copenhagen Economics (2010), Taxation papers, Company Car Taxation, Working Paper NO. 22.
- Cornelis, E., Castaigne, M., Pauly, X., De Witte, A., and Ramaekers, K. (2009), Professional mobility and company car ownership "Promoco". Final Report. Brussels : Belgian Science Policy 2009 – 126 p. (Research Programme Science for a Sustainable Development).
- De Borger (2012), Company cars and the congestion problem, presentation, University of Antwerp.
- Delbeke, B., Verbeeck, G. & Oostrlynck, S. (2013), Aanpak van energiearmoede via energie-efficiëntie: mogelijkheden en beperkingen, in: Callens, M., Noppe J. and Vanderleyden, L. (eds), De Sociale Staat van Vlaanderen 2013, Studiedienst van de Vlaamse Regering.
- Huybrechts, F., Meyer, S. & Vranken, J. (2011), Energiearmoede in België, Final report, research agreement Universiteit Antwerpen OASeS, ULB CEESE, Electrabel, 189p.
- IWEPS (2014): Assessment programme of PM2.5 (Marshall Plan 2.Green, Plan Marshall 2.Vert), Executive Summary.
- KBC (2015), Tax Brochure Company Cars, KBC Autolease, 07-2015.
- Koning Boudewijnstichting (2013), Zoom: Energiearmoede en energieprestaties van gebouwen, Luc Tayart de Broms: Brussels, 4p.
- KPMG (2012), Studierapport Company vehicles, Een vlag die vele ladingen dekt, 6 juni 2012.
- Mayeres, I. (2015), Pilot project on kilometre charge for cars in Brussels Reginal Express Network zone, VITO, Antwerp Tax Academy – Studienamiddag Rekeningrijden, Antwerp, 12 February 2015.
- Meyer, S. & Huybrechts, F., (2012), Energiearmoede in België, p. 179-202 in Vranken, J., Lahaye, W., Geerts, A. & Coppée, C. (eds.), Armoede in België: Jaarboek 2012, Acco: Leuven.
- Minaraad (2005), Study document on the introduction of a system of duties for road traffic, Study commissioned by the Minaraad and carried out by Anneleen De Smedt, deputy of the director, September 2005.
- OECD (2015), OECD Economic Surveys Belgium, overview, February 2015.
- PwC (2013), Slimme fiscaliteit voor betere mobiliteit, Oktober 2013.
- Verbeeck, G. (2014), Sustainable energy for families in poverty, presentation, Community Service Engineering, September 4th 2014.
- Walloon Government (2011), Marshall Plan 2.Green, 1.6 billion euros for 6 priorities.

Prepared by: Black Sea Energy Research Centre

Interlinkage and synergies between selected other policy areas and energy efficiency

D.1.3

Part of work package 1: Mapping of energy efficiency policy instruments and available technologies in buildings and transport

National Report for Bulgaria

31 July 2015

HERON project

“Forward-looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries”

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors’ views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACRONYMS 3

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY..... 4

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS 5

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY 5

 1.1.1 *Case study for the buildings sector*..... 5

 1.1.2 *Case study for the transport sector* 6

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY 9

 1.2.1 *Case study for the buildings sector*..... 9

 1.2.2 *Case study for the transport sector* 11

REFERENCES 13

ACRONYMS

COP	Coefficient of performance
EC	European Commission
EEA	Energy Efficiency Act
EER	Energy efficiency ratio
EU	European Union
EVs	Electric vehicles
GHG	Green house gases
kg	kilogram
ME	Ministry of Energy
MEE	Ministry of Economy and Energy
MOEW	Ministry of Environment and Water
MRDPW	Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works
MTITC	Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications
NZEB	Nearly zero energy building
PV	Photovoltaics
R&D	Research and development
REECL	Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line
RES	Renewable energy sources
SG	State Gazette

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The BSERC's team performed research to ascertain the interlinkage between other policy areas and energy efficiency. Direct and indirect connection has been identified and split into buildings and transport sectors. Despite the importance of the topic, no official studies have been performed so far.

Buildings

The Bulgarian national definition of NZEB has been introduced with the new Energy Efficiency Act and it combines requirements for use of RES (not less than 55 percent of the energy consumed (supplied) for heating, cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water and lighting) and high energy efficiency (class A) of all buildings constructed after 2020.

The implementation of the national NZEB policy will lead to major reduction of energy consumption in new buildings. For example, the primary annual energy consumption in class A is less than 50% of the consumption in class B, which is mandatory for the commissioning of new buildings at present. Respectively, the energy consumption of all new public buildings after 2018 and all new residential buildings after 2020 will be reduced more than two times and more than a half of this reduced energy demand will be from renewable sources.

The Regulation on the labelling and provision of standard information by household appliances is a typical information policy instrument, indirectly linked to energy efficiency, which determines:

- The procedure for providing information to consumers through labelling and information sheets on the consumption of energy and other resources.
- The obligations of producers and traders to provide labelling of household appliances.

A barrier to the amplification of the effect of the measure is the lack of direct information about the reduction of energy costs. Consumers should do the corresponding calculations and compare the financial savings with the difference in the prices of appliances.

Transport

The policy, directed towards the promotion of environmentally friendly vehicles aims at the reduction of harmful emissions (including CO₂) and at energy efficiency improvement and reduction of the dependency on the import of fossil energy resources.

Electric mobility is expected to be one of the key technologies that will contribute to the attainment of these aims, and in addition it will encourage the use of intermittent RES (solar PV and wind) in transport and enhance local employment and economic growth in the coming decades.

The primary objective of the regulatory policy instruments in the transport sector, such as the mandatory periodical technical inspections of vehicles and maximal speed limitations, is the safety of the but they have also substantial impact on the reduction of emissions and improvement of energy efficiency of the road transport.

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.1.1 Case study for the buildings sector

Introduction

National definition for nearly zero energy consumption buildings (NZEB)

According to the Directive 2010/31/EC (Directive 2010/31/EU, 2010), after 2018 all new public buildings, and after 2020 all residential buildings in the EU Member States, must meet the requirements for the nearly zero energy buildings.

The Bulgarian national definition for a building with nearly zero energy consumption has been formulated considering:

- the NZEB definition and requirements, provided by the Directive 2010/31 /EC;
- the characteristics of the existing national legal framework for assessment of the energy performance of buildings;
- the specific economic and social conditions in Bulgaria;
- the influence of local climatic conditions.

The objectives of the national definition are as follows:

- reduction of the energy demand of buildings by improving the energy performance of their envelopes, of the systems providing the necessary microclimate parameters, and of the other energy related systems and appliances;
- utilization of renewable energy generated in the building or in its immediate vicinity.

The requirements for improvement of the energy performance of the systems to provide the microclimate in buildings are:

- minimum seasonal coefficient of performance of heat pumps - 3,5;
- mandatory use of condensing boilers;
- water heating systems with temperature of water not higher than 60°C.

Based on the above considerations, the following definition for a “Nearly zero energy consumption building” was adopted with the new Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015):

“Nearly zero energy consumption building” is a building that meets both of the following conditions:

- energy consumption of the building, defined as primary energy, corresponds to class A of the scale of energy classes for the type of buildings;
- not less than 55 percent of the energy consumed (supplied) for heating, cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water and lighting is energy from renewable sources produced on-site at the building level or near the building”.

Relation to energy efficiency

The introduction of the national NZEB definition will lead to a major reduction of energy consumption in new buildings. For example, the primary annual energy consumption in class A is less than 50% of the consumption in class B, which is mandatory for the commissioning of new buildings at present. Respectively, the energy consumption of all new public buildings after 2018 and all new residential buildings after 2020 will be reduced more than two times and more than a half of this reduced energy demand will be of renewable sources.

Suggestions for improving the energy performance of buildings and for increasing the number of buildings with nearly zero energy consumption will be made in the following years and after in-depth analyses of statistical data for the energy consumption of the first NZEBs in Bulgaria. One of the unsolved problems, which needs further addressing, is the definition of the “renewable source produced near the building”. It is proposed that this distance corresponds to that of the delivery of heat energy from district heating.

The potential benefits of this measure will depend on the scale of the construction of new residential buildings after 2020 and the refurbishment of existing buildings to the standard of NZEB. The consumers will benefit from the reduced energy costs.

Interaction between objectives

The NZEB requirements will interact directly with the legislative requirements for the insulation of buildings towards reaching of class A on the scale of energy classes of buildings.

Both instruments aim at the drop-off in fossil fuels' consumption and reduction of GHG emissions.

In this case the two policy instruments can be implemented only linked.

Interaction between target groups

Both policy instruments address consumers, construction companies, producers of energy efficient materials, RES equipment etc.

Interaction between rules-influencing mechanisms

Both policy instruments are regulatory and interact directly.

The legislative requirements for buildings' insulation determine the primary energy consumption for class A, which constitutes the basis for defining of the required for NZEB amount of energy from RES.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

Both policy instruments are implemented by the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works (MRDPW), which is responsible for the enactment of the requirements for insulation of all new buildings.

The Ministry has the capacity to ensure the adequate implementation of the instrument. The administrative burden and costs will not increase significantly. As it has already been mentioned, the only problem to be resolved is the control of RES energy consumption „near the building“.

1.1.2 Case study for the transport sector

Introduction

National action plan to promote production and penetration of environmentally friendly vehicles including electrical mobility in Bulgaria 2012-2014

Bulgaria is one of the nine EU countries that supported the Joint Declaration on Electric Mobility in Europe (European Council 2010). With this act EVs were put in the spotlight and the countries called for supporting the creation of a common EU standard through financing of pilot projects in electric mobility.

The strategic goals laid out in the EU documents and the objectives and priorities of the Bulgarian national policy for sustainable economic development and environmental protection, form the objectives of this first action plan to promote the introduction and development of sustainable road transport, including electrical mobility in our country for the period 2012-2014 (Council of Ministers 2012), as well as the expected benefits of their implementation, namely:

- Encouraging the production of electric and other environmentally friendly vehicles in Bulgaria, including equipment items and parts. Their production is a relatively new industry that has yet to be developed. EVs represent a new market niche, thus creating conditions for inclusion of new operators in the market. On the other hand, this sector is based on innovative technologies that bring greater added value to our economy. Meanwhile, the development of the automotive industry will accelerate the expansion of other innovative sectors such as information and communication technologies, smart grids, as well as the services sector. As part of the "smart" networks, they will support the energy system by smoothing peaks in electricity consumption and compensate for irregular work of some renewable energy technologies.
- Stimulating of R&D for the elaboration of environmentally friendly vehicles and charging systems. The aim is to provide financial support to promote research into new materials and technologies related to the development of sustainable mobility.
- Stimulating the demand for new environmentally friendly vehicles. Bulgaria needs renewal of the fleet, the status of which is unsatisfactory. Currently more than 50% of the cars are over 15 years old. In addition, this involves significant financial resources for fuels, lubricants and service. The outdated vehicle fleet causes significant environmental pollution and risks to human health. Bulgaria is interested in putting in place measures to achieve the objectives in the field of renewable energy, namely by 2020 to increase the share of biofuels and other RES fuels in the energy consumption of transport to 10%.
- Accelerated construction of charging infrastructure. Building of charging infrastructure is a powerful factor for accelerating the deployment of electric and hybrid vehicles.
- Raising the awareness and capacity of stakeholders and the public on the nature, purpose and benefits from the development of sustainable mobility. In this policy's implementation it is important to raise the awareness of the parties of the benefits from choosing environmentally friendly vehicles and to focus on costs throughout the life cycle of these products.
- Encouraging the development of sustainable urban mobility. Promoting the development of electric mobility in cities. Introducing innovative low-carbon and energy efficient transport technologies and management systems by local authorities, thus providing sustainable future for the public transport. Reducing the dependence on fossil fuels and the generation of greenhouse gases and other pollutants.

The following groups of ecological vehicles will be treated with preferentiality:

- electric vehicles - that use an electric motor with full power and do not have an internal combustion engine;

- hybrids vehicles that use two or more drive systems of different types - the electric motor and an internal combustion engine (gasoline or diesel);
- passenger cars emitting CO₂ emissions up to 120 g/km; minibuses - up to 175 g/km; buses - the requirements of EURO V.

At this stage hydrogen technologies have not reached the required level for marketing that is why the primary focus of this segment is put on stimulation of research and development.

Preferences will be given to vehicles used for the transport of people and goods.

Relation to energy efficiency

In 2014 the number of the electric cars in Bulgaria was 497 and of the hybrid cars – 1031 (MEE & MOEW 2015)

The elaboration of the action plan was the first step; based on the experience gained, a policy for promotion of efficient vehicles will be developed.

Electric mobility is expected to be one of the key technologies that will contribute to the improvement of energy efficiency in transport, promotion of the use of intermittent RES (solar PV and wind), reduction of the uneven load of the electricity grid, reduction of the emissions and of the dependence on import of fossil fuels, enhancement of local employment and economic growth in the coming decades.

The instrument has direct effect on consumers of transport fuels, producers and traders of electric and hybrid cars, storage batteries, electricity etc.

Interaction between objectives

The primary objectives of this policy instrument are identical to those of all the other policy instruments in the transport sector: protection of the environment (including the reduction of CO₂ emissions), energy efficiency improvement, reduction of the import of fossil energy resources and increased security of supply (more than 90% of the energy sources used in the Bulgarian transport are imported) (NSI 2015).

Interaction between target groups

The national action plan for electrical mobility addresses the private cars. The other policy instruments in the sector are directed towards the transport infrastructure, rail and public urban transport. The measure is considered as a complementary to the other measures in the sector.

Interaction between rules-influencing mechanisms

The measures to promote the use of electric and other environmentally friendly vehicles, components and parts include:

- Exemption from annual tax for the owners of environmental vehicles for a period of 5 – 10 years. Introduction of preferential fees for initial registration of electric and hybrid cars and introduction of additional "green" component for the other vehicles on the basis of the CO₂ emissions generated;
- Relief of tolls for all environmental vehicles for the use of road infrastructure;
- Single grant for the purchase of new vehicles – 2 500 EUR for new electric car and 1 250 EUR for new hybrid car.

The interaction between influencing mechanisms for this instrument is financial (tax exemption, toll relief for the use of the road infrastructure and grants for the purchase of new vehicles).

The other measures in the transport sector are subsidized through the Operational Programmes with EU financing.

Interaction between the implementation network / governance structures

The principal institutions responsible for the building of low carbon economy and sustainable development in Bulgaria are:

- Ministry of Energy;
- Ministry of Economy;
- Ministry of Environment and Water;
- Sustainable Energy Development Agency.

The institutions in charge of the management, coordination and control of the state / local policy in areas related to sustainable road transport, including this action plan and electric mobility in Bulgaria, are:

- Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications;
- Ministry of Finance;
- Ministry of Interior;
- Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works;
- Ministry of Education and Science;
- Local authorities.

The administrative burden is relatively low. The limiting factor at this stage is the financial feasibility of the large-scale promotion of electric cars due to the vehicles' high price and the building of a network of charging stations.

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.2.1 Case study for the buildings sector

Introduction

Regulation on the labelling and provision of standard information about the consumption of energy and other resources by products consuming energy

This Regulation of the Council of Ministers has been in force since 20.07.2011 but the measure on labelling of household appliances has been implemented since 2006 (Council of Ministers 2015).

This Regulation determines:

- The procedure for providing information to consumers through labelling and information sheets on the consumption of energy and other resources, as well as other information about energy related products.
- The obligations of producers and traders to provide labelling of household appliances.

The Regulation applies to appliances, which have a significant direct or indirect impact on the consumption of energy and other resources.

The household appliances covered, are:

- Refrigerators and freezers;
- Washing machines;
- Drying machines;
- Combined washing/drying machines;
- Dishwashers;
- Lamps;
- Air-conditioners;
- Electric ovens.

The purpose of this Regulation is the provision of consumers with important and accurate information, which would enable them to make a correct choice.

Relation to energy efficiency

For example, the label of an air-conditioner includes the following information:

- Producer, his authorized representative or market distributor (name / company name or trademark).
- Model identification number.
- Energy efficiency class of the unit.
- EU ecolabel, if available.
- Annual energy consumption, estimated on the basis of the total input power, multiplied by an average of 500 hours/year for models for cooling at full load.
- Cooling output - cooling capacity in kW at full load operation. Energy efficiency ratio (EER) of the unit in cooling mode at full load.
- Type of appliance - cooling only or cooling/heating.
- Type of cooling - air cooling, water cooling.
- Heating capacity - heat output in kW, in heating mode at full load.
- Class of energy efficiency in the heating mode, expressed on a scale from A (most efficient) to G (least efficient). Coefficient of performance (COP) in heating mode.
- Noise level.

So far, no quantification of the effect of this instrument on the energy efficiency is available due to the lack of data and methodology. A barrier to the amplification of the effect of the measure is the lack of direct information about the reduction of energy costs. Consumers should do the corresponding calculations and compare the financial savings with the difference in the prices of appliances.

The main beneficiaries of the improved energy efficiency are the consumers, but also the producers and traders of more efficient appliances.

Interaction between objectives

This policy instrument interacts most closely with the eco-design requirements for energy related products which set minimal energy efficiency standards for household appliances, and the Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line (REECL 2015).

The common objectives of these policy instruments are the reduction of energy consumption, costs and harmful emissions.

For example, the eligible products that are supported by the Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line must comply with the requirements for mandatory energy efficiency standards and labelling.

Interaction between target groups

The three policy instruments mentioned above target the same groups – consumers, producers and traders of energy related products.

Interaction between rules-influencing mechanisms

The labelling, energy standards and REECL interact with the rules on the same trading commodity – energy related products.

The influencing mechanisms, however, are different for each instrument.

Energy labelling and standards are regulatory instruments for the producers and traders of the energy related products. They must comply with the requirements or face administrative sanctions and restrictions.

For consumers, the energy labelling serves as an important information source, enabling them to make a choice.

REECL is a financial policy instrument, which supports with soft loans and grants energy efficient products.

Interaction between the implementation network / governance structures

The capacity of the implementation network of the energy labelling and standards of products is adequate. The control of the implementation is carried out by the Commission for Consumer Protection and the Ministry of Economy.

There is no official data regarding the administrative burden and financial costs for the implementation of this policy instrument. The expert evaluation shows that these costs are low and the capacity of the existing institutions is being fully utilized.

1.2.2 Case study for the transport sector

Introduction

Mandatory technical inspections of vehicles

The periodical technical inspection of all road vehicles has been mandatory since more than 30 years.

The Regulation №32 from 16.12.2011 of the Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications specifies the periodical mandatory technical and emissions control of vehicles (MTITC 2014).

The inspection includes control of the proper maintenance of engines, transmissions etc. and vehicles exhaust gas emissions. It is carried out by public centres for Technical Control and only some categories of vehicles are excluded (military vehicles, vehicles produced before 01.01.1960). Public

transport vehicles must undergo tests once every 6 months; the rest of the vehicles – once every year.

The primary objectives of this policy instrument are the safety of transport and the reduction of emissions.

Relation to energy efficiency

The average age of the vehicles in Bulgaria is high and, therefore, the improved maintenance leads directly to a reduction of fuel consumption.

Considering the age and the technical conditions of the road vehicles, the expert evaluation shows that the achieved average annual decrease of specific fuel consumption as a result of the regular maintenance and control of emissions is not less than 3%.

Interaction between objectives

Fuel saving driving is part of the training courses for the drivers of motor vehicles. The common objectives of the technical inspections of vehicles and the training of drivers are the safety of travel and reduced emissions. The limits for emissions are specified in the Clean Ambient Air Act (MOEW 2011).

The effect of the parallel implementation of the two policy instruments on the attainment of the above objectives is that the proper maintenance of the vehicles is a necessary precondition for the safe and fuel saving driving.

Interaction between target groups

The common target group of the both policy instruments (technical inspections and training of drivers) are the owners of road vehicles.

Interaction between rules-influencing mechanisms

If a vehicle does not meet the technical requirements, it does not receive permission to be used on the roads. Drivers do not receive driving license if they do not pass the training.

Interaction between the implementation network / governance structures

The Ministry of Interior and the Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications are responsible for the implementation of the two policy instruments. Implementation network already exists and the capacity is adequate. No additional administrative cost is necessary.

REFERENCES

Council of Ministers, 2011, Regulation on the Labelling and Provision of Standard Information about the Consumption of Energy and Other Resources by Products Consuming Energy, Decision No. 140/17.05.2011, Promulgated in SG issue 41 from 31.05.2011, last amendment in SG issue 17 from 28.02.2014, <http://www.lex.bg/en/laws/ldoc/2135733112>

Council of Ministers, 2012, National Action Plan for the Promotion of the Production and Accelerated Penetration of Ecological Vehicles, including Electric Mobility 2012-2014, http://www3.moew.government.bg/files/file/POS/Strategic_documents/Nacionalen_plan_elektromobilnost.pdf

Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings, 2010, OJ L153/13, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EN:PDF>

European Council, 2010, Joint Declaration on Electric Mobility in Europe, <http://register.consilium.europa.eu/doc/srv?l=EN&f=ST%2014028%202010%20INIT>

Ministry of Energy (ME), 2015, Energy Efficiency Act, Promulgated in SG No.35 from 15.05.2015, <http://www.me.government.bg/bg/library/zakon-za-energiinata-efektivnost-537-c25-m258-2.html>

Ministry of Economy and Energy (MEE), 2014, National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2014 – 2020, http://www.seea.government.bg/documents/NEEAP_BG.pdf

Ministry of Economy and Energy & Ministry of Environment and Water (MEE, MOEW), 2014, Annual Report on the implementation in 2013 of the National action plan for the promotion of the production and accelerated penetration of ecological vehicles, including electric mobility, <http://www.strategy.bg/FileHandler.ashx?fileId=4803>

Ministry of Economy and Energy & Ministry of Environment and Water (MEE, MOEW), 2015, Annual Report on the implementation in 2014 of the National action plan for the promotion of the production and accelerated penetration of ecological vehicles, including electric mobility, <http://www.government.bg/cgi-bin/e-cms/vis/vis.pl?s=001&p=0228&n=6906&g=>

Ministry of Environment and Water (MOEW), 2011, Clean Ambient Air Act, amended and supplemented, SG No. 42/3.06.2011 http://www3.moew.government.bg/files/file/PNOOP/Acts_in_English/Clean_Ambient_Air_Act.pdf

Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works (MRDPW), 2015a, Ordinance №7 of 2004 on energy efficiency, heat and energy savings in buildings, <http://lex.bg/bg/laws/ldoc/2135497693>

Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works (MRDPW) 2015b, Ordinance №RD 16-1058 of 10 December 2009 on the indicators for energy consumption and energy performance of buildings, <http://seea.government.bg/documents/Naredba-RD-16-1058.pdf>

Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications (MTITC), 2000, Law on the Roads, Promulgated in SG No.26 of 29.03.2000, last amendment SG No.37 of 22.05.2015, <https://www.mtitc.government.bg/page.php?category=213&id=504>

Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications (MTITC) 2014, Regulation 32/16.12.2011 on the periodical inspections of the technical conditions of vehicles, http://www.rta.government.bg/images/Image/n_uredba/nH32.pdf

Residential energy efficiency credit line, 2015, REECL, <http://www.reecl.org/indexen.php>

National statistical institute, 2015, “Overall energy balance sheet” (2001 – 2013), <http://www.nsi.bg/en/content/5057/overall-energy-balance-sheet>.

HERON (No:649690): Deliverable 1.3

INTERLINKAGE AND SYNERGIES BETWEEN SELECTED OTHER POLICY AREAS AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY

D.1.3

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT**

NATIONAL REPORT FOR ESTONIA

DATE 11.08.2015

Partner: *Stockholm Environment Institute Tallinn Centre*

HERON project

“Forward-looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries”

This project has received funding from the *European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 649690

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: *Stockholm Environment Institute Tallinn Centre*
Steering Committee member⁽¹⁾: *Tiit Kallaste*

Prepared by: *Kerli Kirsimaa, Mari Jüssi, Tiit Kallaste, Piret Kuldna*

(1) The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Contents

ACRONYMS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS.....	6
1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY	6
1.1.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR: Promotion and production of green energy	6
1.1.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR: E-Estonia.....	10
1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY	12
1.2.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR: Fuel and Electricity Excise Taxes.....	12
1.2.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR: Traffic safety hazard mapping.....	14
REFERENCES.....	16

Table of Figures

Figure 1 EU Member States Share of Energy from Renewable Sources (percent of Gross Final Energy Consumption)	7
Figure 2: Energy use in buildings in Estonia.....	8

Table of Tables

Table 1 Energy savings in Estonian houses in 2013 after the implementation of KredEx renovation fund.....	14
--	-----------

ACRONYMS

ENMAK	-Estonian energy management development plan 2030+ [Eesti energiamajanduse arengukava aastani 2030+]
EU	- European Union
IBS	- Institute of Baltic Studies
MEAC	-Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The policy instrument with direct link to energy in buildings sector analysed hereof is the promotion and production of green energy. In Estonia, the power consumption in buildings sector makes up to about 42.7 % from the overall energy balance. Thus the production of energy is highly depending on the household sector and the other way around. The policy instrument with an indirect link to energy is the fuel and electricity excise tax, being one of the major mechanisms which indirectly influence the energy efficiency in housing sector. It affects all the energy producers and network operators, but also the homeowners who heat their houses with liquid fuel, and who are now, due to the tighter regulations, being influenced to change their heating systems towards more sustainable options in a way. The respective policy instrument interlinking both the direct and indirect policy instruments as described above in respect of the effects these have on the energy efficiency of Estonian housing market, is the National Energy Management Development Plan 2030+. In this document both, the topic of green energy production (direct policy instrument), as well as fuel and electricity excise tax (indirect policy instrument) have been combined and described in one comprehensive document, together with the strategies related to Estonian housing market (visions for Estonian housing stock up to 2050). Yet, the mentioned development plan is in the draft form and still, to be made official in the near future.

For the transport sector two case studies are represented. Developing E-Estonia and related e-services is a governmental policy instrument that has a direct link to energy efficiency, expected to reduce unnecessary trips and related energy consumption. Impact assessment of the Estonian e-government services in 2013 concluded that Estonia has managed to save remarkable amounts of time and money by developing and updating e-services, but obtaining accurate data for calculating the cost-effectiveness of e-government investments is very difficult. As to the indirect link to energy efficiency in transport sector a case on traffic safety hazard mapping tool for schools is presented. The aim of the tool is to analyse and map traffic safety hazards on students' home to school trips, to map travel modes and provide Road Administration and local authorities with highlighted traffic spots and traffic safety information generated by students, and improve overall traffic safety of primary school students. The mapping could be linked to energy efficiency targets and be integrated with science and physical education classes, the mapping tool could calculate energy saving potential of a class, a school or personal trips. The module could be also more closely linked to encouraging preparation of school travel plan (currently voluntary for schools). Both national and local governments, schools and families would benefit from full energy efficiency considerations. National Transport Development Plan 2014-2020 sets goals both for substituting unnecessary travel with e-services, for traffic safety and transports energy efficiency however it does not interlink all these goals and respective measures.

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS

In current debates the multiple benefits of energy efficiency are broadly discussed and available analyses are growing in number (e.g. IEA 2014 report on multiple benefits). However, in some cases energy savings can rather be seen as the co-benefit of other policies or measures, which do not target energy efficiency by design.

The aim of this task is to identify policy areas suitable for combination with energy efficiency policies and systematically analyse how they may contribute to improve energy efficiency, particularly if untapped energy saving potentials still exist.

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.1.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR: Promotion and production of green energy

Focus: More widespread introduction of renewable energy sources.

Target group: Electricity/ energy production companies or inhabitants of Estonia in general.

Objective: Reduce greenhouse gas emissions by increasing the share of renewable energy sources in the whole of energy consumption.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

It is stated in the Estonian Renewable Energy Action Plan up to 2020¹, that renewable energy must also be promoted through the introduction of local generating installations using renewable energy in buildings. Therefore, the direct supply of heat or cooling through district heating and cooling in buildings should also be considered in accordance with the Directive 2009/28/EC² (Eesti..., 2015).

Concerning the increase of the share of energy from renewable sources and requirements for the use of renewable energy in the buildings sector in Estonia, no national and regional legislation in Estonia have been established. However, it has been discussed to add requirements to the Building Act and legislation issued on the basis of thereof (MEAC, 2010).

No statistical data about the share of renewable energy in the buildings sector is available. Local authorities in Estonia have the right to establish additional techniques for increasing renewable energy in new buildings. This can be seen as part of fulfilling the EU obligation (Directive 2009/28/EC)

¹ Eesti taastuvenergia tegevuskava aastani 2020 [Estonian Renewable Energy Action Plan up to 2020], Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications. Available online:

https://www.mkm.ee/sites/default/files/taastuvenergia_tegevuskava.pdf, (05.07.2015)

² European Parliament & European Council, (2009). Directive 2009/28/EC. Available online:

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32009L0028>, (05.07.2015)

for all the new buildings to be zero-energy. The possibilities to share renewable energy in buildings is also studied by the construction of sample buildings, and training events organised for specialists working in the buildings sector (MEAC, 2010).

Additional measures concerning the use of renewable energy in buildings are definitely required. Further rules and legislations should come to establish the minimum level of energy use from renewable energy sources in the case of existing buildings particularly that undergo large-scale renovation (MEAC, 2010).

In 2014, 14.8 % out of all the energy consumption consisted of renewable energy. This is 2.2 % more than compared to 2013. In total, the overall amount of renewable energy produced in 2014 was 1.36 TWh and the production increased 18 %. Production of electricity increased the most out of biomass, biogas and waste (26 %), followed by increase in using wind energy (9 %) and hydro energy (3 %) (Elektrisüsteemi..., 2015).

Estonia in general is doing relatively well with renewable energy production. In 2011, Estonia was the first EU Member State to reach its 2020 target, and as according to Eurostat statistics, being the 7th best among the EU countries in terms of share of energy from renewable sources as shown on Figure 1.

Figure 1 EU Member States Share of Energy from Renewable Sources (percent of Gross Final Energy Consumption)

Interaction between objectives

Buildings and production of energy are highly interlinked sectors simply because a significant part of the energy balance is demanded by the buildings. Therefore, buildings sector is one of the important areas to work on when working towards energy efficiency – energy consumption in buildings make up to 40% of the overall EU energy consumption. In Estonia, the power consumption in buildings sector makes up to about 42.7 % from the overall energy balance (ENMAK 2030+, 2015). Achieving energy efficiency in buildings (renovating, insulation) and using renewable resources in the buildings both for heating and cooling are therefore an important factors to succeed in the same goal.

Figure 2: Energy use in buildings in Estonia

Source: European Commission, 2010

Up to 2013 Estonia was following the Estonian Housing Development Plan 2008-2013. In this document, reducing the dependence on non-renewable resources in housing sector has been discussed; however nothing is mentioned in terms of using renewable resources for heating and cooling (Eesti..., 2008). Today, Estonian Housing Development Plan 2008-2013 together with a list of other strategies, have all been replaced by the National Energy Development Plan 2030+³, which is currently yet in the draft form. The new document combines all the energy efficiency related objectives in line with the EU Directives, directly linking renewable energy production as part of achieving energy efficiency in the buildings sector. The use of renewable resources must be increased 20 % by 2020 and 27 % by 2030 (ENMAK 2030+, 2015).

Interaction between target groups

The target groups in terms of energy efficiency in buildings sector, are either the house/flat owners or tenants and apartment associations (inhabitants in general), as well as the government (both local and national) of Estonia whose interest is to fulfil EU targets related to energy efficiency.

The target group for renewable energy production are primarily the energy service companies, but similarly with the buildings sector target group consists also the house owners themselves who wish to install solar panels on their roofs for instance, as well as again the government (both local and national) of Estonia whose interest is to fulfil EU targets related to energy efficiency and

³ ENMAK 2030+, Eesti Energiamaajanduse arengukava aastani 2030+, [National Energy Management Development Plan 2030+]. (2015). Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications. Available online: http://www.energiatalgud.ee/img_auth.php/2/25/ENMAK_2030_Eeln%C3%B5u_23.10.2014.pdf, (05.07.2014).

sustainability. During the past few years, the number of private renewable energy micro-producers has increased, in 2014 more than ever before - 186 new micro-producers joined, that especially in terms of solar power (Taastuvenergia..., 2015). The largest share of renewable energy is in the heating sector – 43 %. In the electricity sector the share of renewable energy is about 13.2 % and in the transport sector about 0.2 %. In the heating sector the switch to renewable resources is rising every year, that because the wood is much cheaper than natural gas and heating oil. Yet, as about 83% of Estonian electricity is produced out of oil shale, the electricity production in Estonia is still very energy consuming with a large environmental impact (Taastuvenergia..., 2015).

In general the common target group does exist in the described two instruments, both on a political (public) and private level. The property owners can save costs both by renovating or making their homes more energy efficient as well as by using renewable resources. This works in symbolism with the government bodies whose direct interest is to achieve energy efficiency in the entire country. Therefore several governmental funding schemes have been implemented such as by Foundation KredEx for apartment associations to help them to renovate homes or the support given for renewable energy production under the Electricity Market Act §59⁴, recently being renewed in 01.09.2015 (Elering, 2015).

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

The energy performance of the buildings and production of renewable energy are topics recently both being combined within the new National Energy Management Development Plan 2030+. This is an overall national strategy which sets the targets in line with the EU Directive to achieve energy efficiency 20 % by 2020 (2009/28/EC). This is an overall law which interacts with the two policy instruments – 1. KredEx Foundation⁵ established for the benefit of achieving energy efficiency in the housing market (KRedEx provided support for renovation of the detached private houses for the purchase and installation of the equipment for local renewable micro-energy supply and replacement of heating systems with heat-pumps and biomass boilers); 2. National Renewable Energy Action Plan 2020⁶. Both of them have helped to implement the Estonian Housing Development Plan 2008-2013 and achieve energy efficiency in general as requested by EU Directive 2009/28/EC. The strategies set in latter being now part of and renewed in the new National Energy Management Development Plan 2030+.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

In Estonia, the main national body responsible for topics regarding renewable energy and energy efficiency in buildings sector, is the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communication (MEAC). Much of the energy efficiency in the Estonian houses is achieved thanks to the renovation fund KredEx which was established by MEAC. In addition, renewable energy production is also directly funded by MEAC through different energy companies such as Elering. In addition, the Ministry of Agriculture has also initiated and led the development of “Development Plan for the Promotion of the Use of Biomass and Bio Energy for 2007-2013” (MEAC, 2015). However, subsidies to the generation of

⁴ Electricity Market Act (2003) [Elektrituruseadus]. RT I, 30.06.2015, 43. Available online: https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/compare_original/503072015001, (25.09.2015).

⁵ KredEx Foundation, Available online: <http://www.kredex.ee/en/>, (20.06.2015).

⁶ Eesti taastuvenergia tegevuskava aastani 2020 [Estonian Renewable Energy Action Plan up to 2020], Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications. Available online: https://www.mkm.ee/sites/default/files/taastuvenergia_tegevuskava.pdf, (05.07.2015).

energy from all kind of renewable sources of energy are to be provided under the Electricity Market Act issued by the Parliament of Estonia (Electricity Market Act, 2003). Therefore, in general the network in Estonia in terms of implementation and financial administration is not too overlapping on the national level.

1.1.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR: E-Estonia

E-Estonia is a governmental program for developing electronic governance and public services with an objective to provide such services fast and with the smallest possible administrative burden (E-Governance, 2015). The e-Estonia digital society is made possible largely due to its infrastructure. Instead of developing a single, all-encompassing central system, Estonia created an open, decentralized system that links together various services and databases. The flexibility provided by this open set-up has allowed new components of the digital society to be developed and added through the years. E-Estonia means services available in Internet, such as:

- DigiDoc: Digital signing of documents (launched in 2002);
- I-voting (launched 2005);
- E-Tax: Submitting tax reports (VAT, income or social tax) (launched 2000);
- E-business register: for establishing a company, NGO;
- State e-services portal and social welfare e-services;
- E-Cabinet (Information System of Government Sessions), e-Health (Electronic Health Record), e-Prescription, e-School, e-Police, e-Law, etc.;
- E-residency: e-Residency — a transnational digital identity available to anyone in the world interested in administering a location-independent business online (launched 2014);
- MobileID, M-parking, MobilePayment.

The energy savings are linked to transport system efficiency and derived from fewer travels to visit various government agencies, banks or polling places.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

The main goal of E-governance is to reduce administrative burden and improve accessibility to services. National Transport Strategy (MEAC, 2014) lists developing E-governance/Digital society as one of the policy measures to improve transport system efficiency and reduce the need for travel (for errands related to national and local governmental offices, banks, health services, tickets etc. E-governance facilitates services related to public transport and other mobility services (e-ticketing, M-parking, car sharing).

Transport energy efficiency has been indirectly considered by the policy – **Digital Agenda 2020 for Estonia** (MEAC, 2013) states that the development of e-services reduces their environmental impact, incl. transport demand. Impact assessment of the Estonian e-government services in 2013 concluded that Estonia has managed to save remarkable amounts of time and money by developing and updating e-services, but obtaining accurate data for calculating the cost-effectiveness of e-government investments is very difficult (Kalvet et al., 2013).

Interaction between objectives

E-governance, transport and substituting the demand for physical travel with digital access and e-services is mainly discussed in the following three governmental strategic documents:

- 1) **The Transport Development Plan 2014-2020** (MEAC, 2014), measure 1.1, under the sub-goal 1 “Convenient and smart commuting environment” addresses reducing the demand for unnecessary trips and substituting trips partly with e-services and digital access. The underlying principle of the measure is that upon shaping the public sector’s services, solutions are preferred that enable their electronic use and reduce the need to physically visit an official institution or other physical service point (ticket office, information office).
- 2) **Green Paper on the Organisation of Public Services** (MEAC, 2013) discusses in more detail better arrangement of public services, inter alia to reduce obligatory commutes. Energy efficiency is not directly addressed in the Green Paper.
- 3) **Digital Agenda for Estonia 2020** (MEAC, 2013) states *“Smart manufacturing solutions, houses and transport have led to a more sustainable use of resources, which constitutes a saving both for businesses and individuals. This has reduced resource intensity - in Estonia, more is done with fewer resources”*.

No quantitative energy efficiency related targets are described in the above mentioned documents.

Interaction between target groups

Target groups of all these policies are citizens, Estonian residents, public authorities, businesses and other institutions in the broadest sense.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

Impact assessment of the Estonian e-government services in 2013 concluded that Estonia has managed to save remarkable amounts of time and money by developing and updating e-services, but obtaining accurate data for calculating the cost-effectiveness of e-government investments is very difficult (Kalvet et al., 2013). The Institute of Baltic Studies (IBS) developed method for assessment of the impact of e-services. 15 e-services with a different level of maturity were selected for the study. The development of these services has been co-funded from the structural funds of the European Union (Operational Programme for the Development of Economic Environment).

Full utilisation of information technology often requires major changes in the organisation of work of government agencies and/or communication between them. This concerns the organisation of work in the agency that provides the service as well as the interaction between various information systems (of different agencies). The X-road and ID card are extremely important as infrastructure, because they have created the basis on which the remaining services have been developed, and they have often been the unavoidable prerequisite of various e-services (Kalvet et al. 2013).

The analysis of Kalvet et al (2013) also concluded that a more thorough analysis must be carried out before the initiation of new e-government projects and measurable goals should be established for each development project. In future e-government projects, analysis of the total cost of ownership of an e-service should become one of the main selection criteria in making financing decisions. The expected impact and specific target levels that describe the future e-service, and the way of information collection for the cost-effectiveness should be determined in the preparatory stages of major new projects. While doing so, development of e-services that enable for greater cost effectiveness should be given priority.

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.2.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR: Fuel and Electricity Excise Taxes

Focus: fuel and electricity in entire energy sector

Target group: All sectors related to fuel and electricity consumption

Objective: Discourage the use of non-renewable energy sources; promote the production of energy from renewable resources.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Fuel and electricity excise duty is a law directly related to energy, yet it can be considered as an indirect tool when analysing the energy efficiency of housing sector. The law on excise duty for alcohol, tobacco, fuel and electricity (originally in force since 2003), was renewed very recently on July 1st 2015 (Alkoholi..., 2003⁷). The new law is increasing the rates of excise duty on natural gas; loses tax benefits of liquid fossil fuels; exempts electricity producers, who are connected to the grid and produce below 100 kilowatts, from tax burden; as well as releases biogas from excise duty (Alkoholi..., 2003).

In Estonia the housing development strategies are currently in the process of being combined with the overall National Energy Development Plan (ENMAK 2030+). Before that a separate Housing Development Plan existed up to 2013, called as Estonian Housing Development Plan 2008-2013. In the latter document, there was not even a word mentioned about excise taxes. Yet, the new National Energy Development Plan 2030+, currently under review, combines all the energy related activities, questions and sectors in one comprehensive document. However, fuel and electricity excise taxes in the mentioned document have only been discussed under sectors related to transportation, yet still quite in a limited manner.

However, fuel and electricity excise taxes are one of the major mechanisms which indirectly influence the energy efficiency in housing sector. It affects all the energy producers and network operators, but also the homeowners who heat their houses with liquid fuel. The new law on excise duty was implemented in 2015 (Alkoholi..., 2003). The overall aim of this is to limit the use of non-renewable resources and promote the use of renewables. However, as change is not to happen overnight, the new rules caused a lot of resentment explicitly for heating oil dependent house owners, as it doubled the prices existed so far. According to the Estonian Construction Register, there are about 3200 residential buildings which are depending on liquid oil heating (about 2800 detached houses), including some extra public buildings such as community houses, cultural centres etc. Thus the heating oil dependent house owners are in many cases considering to replace their heating

⁷ Alkoholi-, tubaka-, kütuse- ja elektriaktsiisi seadus. (2003). [Alcohol, Tobacco, Fuel and Electricity Excise Duty Act] Riigi Teataja I 2003, 2, 17, accessible at: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/ee/518062015016/consolide/current>, (23.07.2015).

systems, which is however not the easiest and cheapest task to do, even though it is possible to apply for the KredEx renovation grant, because it still requires home owners to self-finance some part of it. Though, once the investment is has been done, it is thought that not only the environment, but also public could benefit from using more sustainable energy resources what the law indirectly would hopefully trigger them to do. In the other words, it would encourage sustainable energy micro-production at homes, the more so as tax is not required for those producing below 100 kilowatts (Eesti..., 2015).

Whilst the excise taxes are in many cases seen as unpleasant expenses, it is believed that environmental benefits will be seen in the future. Support for the enterprises in the energy sector in order to promote renewable energy, is given to the electricity producers under the excise act of alcohol-, fuel- and electricity (Alkoholi..., 2003); and for the district heating support is given by EU structural funds and other sources through Estonian Environment Investment Centre (Taastuvenergia..., 2015). The more so, as with the implementation of the new excise law, production of biofuels was freed from taxes, in order to support local energy production and enhance energy independence from Russian gas (Eesti..., 2015).

Interaction between objectives

The energy efficiency policy instrument under discussion hereof is the National Energy Development Plan (ENMAK 2030+) and the selected policy instrument indirectly influencing the energy efficiency in the housing sector are the excise taxes set for fuel and electricity particularly. The common objective in both of the instruments is to promote the use of renewable energy resources, limit the emissions and reduce energy consumption in general. Another common objective is to achieve the EU 20/20 target set in EU Directive 2009/28/EC.

As the implementation of the new and stricter Excise Duty is still very fresh, as well as the new energy development plan is yet not official, it is hard to draw out the impacts what the implementation of these instruments have already achieved. However, according to KredEx, the renovation of apartment buildings, both in terms of insulation and heating system, has an increasing popularity. The volume of housing loans with KredEx guarantee increased by 29 % from the beginning of 2015 (KredEx, 2015). In the near future, even higher increase has been estimated.

Interaction between target groups

The common target group consists of the house owners, particularly the ones depending on natural gas or light fuel oil. Another common target group could also be the architects, engineers and builders who from now on must focus on building more energy efficient homes, and soon zero-energy homes as obliged by Directive 2010/31/EU.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

Environmental taxes should induce producers and consumers to make environmentally friendly decisions. In Estonia energy efficiency should be mainly improved in transport- and housing sector. One of the interacting measures to achieve this is by raising the excise taxes. However, it has been indicated, that the household sector is already the biggest environmental tax payer, fuel tax being the largest share in it, and this is often considered unfair when compared to industries or other sectors for instance. If to look at transportation fuels consumption and the distribution of excise duties, the sectors with the greatest influence on the environment, do not always bear the greatest

tax burden in Estonia (Keskkonnamaksud..., 2015). However, the collected environmental taxes in turn, are used to cover the environmentally beneficial projects (including related to buildings energy efficiency) such as via Estonian Environmental Investment Centre (KIK- Keskkonnainvesteeringute Keskus).

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

As the implementation of the new and stricter Excise Duty is still very fresh, as well as the new energy development plan is yet not official, it is hard to evaluate what has been the implementation capacity of the government to achieve the objectives targeted with both of the instruments. Yet one of the most influential tools in Estonia working towards improving the energy efficiency in houses is the funding and consultancy offered by Foundation KredEx. Below is the table providing information about the number of houses which have received KredEx funding and the savings (both in EUR and kWh) after the implementation of activities by KredEx.

Table 1 Energy savings in Estonian houses in 2013 after the implementation of KredEx renovation fund

City/County	Number of houses	2013 savings in kWh	Savings in EUR
Tallinn	153	18 835 839	1 488 031
Tartu	31	4 367 870	279 544
Harjumaa	43	3 566 858	267 514
Tartumaa	19	1 667 597	125 070
Pärnumaa	20	1 288 205	96 615
Ida-Virumaa	6	998 427	74 882
Lääne-Virumaa	7	895 827	67 187
Raplamaa	10	638 517	47 889
Valgamaa	4	626 060	46 955
Viljandimaa	6	402 608	30 196
Jõgevamaa	5	246 233	18 467
Saaremaa	2	226 290	16 972
Läänemaa	3	197 523	14 814
Järvamaa	2	116 447	8 734
Põlvamaa	1	65 253	8 734
Võrumaa	1	45 793	3 434
Hiiumaa	1	22 453	1 684
Total	314	34 207 800	2 592 882

Source: Korterelamute renoveerimisturu..., 2014. P. 21-22.

1.2.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR: Traffic safety hazard mapping

Traffic safety hazard mapping is an educational module (“*Koolitee ohtlike kohtade kaardistamine*”) provided by the Estonian Road Administration targeting primary schools, primary school students (especially 4. and 7.-graders) and local traffic safety officials. This module is part of “Health and Safety” educational program that is one of the 8 cross-curricular horizontal themes of primary school curricula that facilitates teachers of science, geography and other related classes to integrate safety issues in their class themes. The module consists of internet-based mapping tool, teacher’s guidance and activity descriptions. The aim of the tool is to analyse and map traffic safety hazards on students home to school routes (while learning about maps and traffic safety rules), to map travel modes and

provide Road Administration and local authorities with highlighted traffic spots and traffic safety information generated by students, and improve overall traffic safety of primary school students. (Estonian Road Administration..., 2015) This interactive mapping tool has been also used as a basis for developing school travel plans in 10 piloting schools in Estonia in 2012-2014 (Sarv, 2014).

Interaction between objectives

The explicit objective of this instrument is to improve traffic safety among school children. Safe traffic environment is one of the key prerequisites of children independent home to school trips and shifting car trips to public transport, walking and cycling. The National Transport Development Plan 2014-2020 has goals both for traffic safety and transport energy efficiency (MEAC, 2014), including funding schemes for better urban mobility environment/public transport/walking and cycling infrastructure and intends to cap energy consumption by improving walking, cycling and public transport conditions, this educational module is not directly linked to these interlinked goals and could be linked more closely to energy efficiency goals. For example the mapping exercise could be linked to mathematics, science and physical education classes and the mapping tool could calculate energy saving potential of a class, a school or personal trips. The module could be also more closely linked to encouraging preparation of school travel plan (currently voluntary for schools). Both national and local governments, schools and families would benefit from full energy efficiency considerations.

Interaction between target groups

National funding schemes for better urban mobility environment, public transport, walking and cycling infrastructure target mainly transport users living in the cities or commuting to the city. School children are essential sub-group of this target group. The selection of potential projects (both local and national governments) could benefit more from the mapping exercises and information generated by schools travel plans and students.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

The Road Administration has developed teacher's guidance and supports schools with organizing teachers' training to carry out the classes. The module is highly dependent on availability of computers during the classes and not all schools have the possibility to carry out the mapping exercise on computers. There is no comprehensive overview or annual statistics how many schools actually apply this module, how many children participated in mapping. One of the aims of the module is to provide local authorities with information about traffic safety concerns of children and improve the environment around schools; however there are no institutional arrangements for local authorities to actually use this data. NGO Linnalabor working on urban planning and mobility issues has suggested Road Administration to use the mapping tool more actively to promote school travel plans and increase awareness on more active travel modes and traffic safety (Sarv, 2014).

REFERENCES

- Alkoholi-, tubaka-, kütuse- ja elektriaktsiisi seadus. (2003). [Alcohol, Tobacco, Fuel and Electricity Excise Duty Act] Riigi Teataja I 2003, 2, 17. Available online: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/ee/518062015016/consolide/current>, (23.07.2015).
- Digital Agenda 2020 for Estonia, Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications. Available online: https://www.mkm.ee/sites/default/files/digital_agenda_2020_estonia_engf.pdf, (24.07.2015)
- Eesti eluasemevaldkonna arengukava 2008-2013. (2008). [Estonian Housing development Plan 2008-2013]. Available online: https://www.mkm.ee/sites/default/files/eluasemevaldkonna_arengukava_2008_2013.pdf, (06.07.2015)
- Eesti taastuvenergia tegevuskava aastani 2020 [Estonian Renewable Energy Action Plan up to 2020], Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications. Available online: https://www.mkm.ee/sites/default/files/taastuvenergia_tegevuskava.pdf, (05.07.2015)
- E-Estonia. (2015). Available online: <https://e-estonia.com>, (24.07.2015).
- Electricity Market Act (2003) [Elektrituruseadus]. RT I, 30.06.2015, 43. Available online: https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/compare_original/503072015001, (25.09.2015).
- Elektrisüsteemi kokkuvõte: 2014, Elering. Available online: http://elering.ee/public/Infokeskus/Kuukokkuvotted/2014/Elektrisusteeem_2014.pdf, (06.08.2015).
- Elektrituruseadus. (2003). Riigi Teataja RT I 2003, 25, 153. Available online: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/12894671>, (06.07.2015).
- Elering on taastuvenergiatoetuste makseagentuur, Elering. Available online: <http://elering.ee/taastuvenergia-toetus>, (06.07.2015).
- ENMAK 2030+, Eesti Energiamaajanduse arengukava aastani 2030+, [National Energy Management Development Plan 2030+]. (2015). Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications. Available online: http://www.energiatalgud.ee/img_auth.php/2/25/ENMAK_2030_Eeln%C3%B5u_23.10.2014.pdf, (05.07.2014).
- Estonian Road Administration. (2015). Koolitee ohtlike kohtade kaardistamine. Available online: <http://www.mnt.ee/index.php?id=12398> (08.07.2015).
- European Commission, Eurostat Statistics, 2010. Available online: <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database>, (07.07.2015).
- European Parliament & European Council, (2009). Directive 2009/28/EC. Available online: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32009L0028>, (05.07.2015)

European Parliament & European Council, (2010). Directive 2010/31/EU. Available online: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EN:PDF>, (30.07.2015).

https://www.mkm.ee/sites/default/files/digital_agenda_2020_estonia_engf.pdf (23.07.2015).

IEA (2014): Capturing the multiple benefits of energy efficiency. Available online: <https://www.iea.org/Textbase/npsum/MultipleBenefits2014SUM.pdf>, (2015.05.28).

Kalvet, T., Tiits, M., Hinsberg, H. (editors). (2013). Impact assessment of the Estonian e-government services. Tallinn: Institute of Baltic Studies & Praxis Center for Policy Studies. Executive Summary. Available online: http://www.ibs.ee/et/publikatsioonid/item/download/91_5df1730f345e8e3fb16c49e32ce59a00, (24.07.2015).

Keskkonnamaksud on toonud riigieelarvesse järjest rohkem tulu, Eesti Statistika. Available online: <https://statistikaamet.wordpress.com/tag/kutuseaktsiis/>, (06.07.2015).

Korterelamute renoveerimisturu ülevaade ja perioodi 2010-2014 korterelamute rekonstrueerimistoetuste mõju analüüs. (2014). [An overview of renovations made in the apartment building and analysis of the impacts of renovation funding during the period of 2010-2014], ordered by KredEx, page 21-22. Available online: http://kredex.ee/public/Uuringud/Korterelamute_analuus_030914.pdf, (30.07.2015).

KredEx Foundation, Available online: <http://www.kredex.ee/en/>, (20.06.2015).

MEAC, Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications (2014): Eesti transpordi arengukava 2014-2020 [Estonian Transport Development Plan 2014–2020]. Available online: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/aktiivisa/3210/2201/4001/arengukava.pdf#>, (23.07.2015).

MEAC, Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications. (2013). Digital Agenda 2020 for Estonia. Available online: https://www.mkm.ee/sites/default/files/digital_agenda_2020_estonia_engf.pdf, (23.07.2015).

MEAC; Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications. (2013). Green Paper on the Organisation of Public Services. Available online: https://www.mkm.ee/sites/default/files/green_paper_oige.pdf, (24.07.2015).

Sarv, K. (2014). Impacts of School Travel Plans to urban environment. Case Study of Peetri elementary school. Master's Thesis in Urban Studies. Estonian Academy of Arts, Faculty of Architecture, Chair of Urban Studies.

Taastuenergia on puhas energia, Eesti Taastuenergia Koda. Available online: <http://www.taastuenergeetika.ee/>, (06.07.2015).

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.3

INTERLINKAGE AND SYNERGIES BETWEEN SELECTED OTHER POLICY AREAS AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY

PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

NATIONAL REPORT FOR GERMANY

2015-08-15

Partner: *Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment, Energy*

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Universiteit
Antwerpen

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment, Energy

Steering Committee member ⁽¹⁾: Dr. Ralf Schüle

Prepared by: Thomas Adisorn, Carolin Schäfer-Sparenberg, Dr. Ralf Schüle, Maike Venjakob

⁽¹⁾ The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACRONYMS 4

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY 5

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS 6

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY 6

1.1.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR – MARKET INCENTIVE PROGRAMME 6

1.1.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR – CO₂-RELATED MOTOR VEHICLE TAX 7

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY 10

1.2.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR – RENOVATION SUPPORT FOR THE ELDERLY 10

1.2.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR – COMPANY CAR TAXATION 12

REFERENCES 14

ACRONYMS

BAFA – Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle, Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control

EER – Energy Efficient Renovation

KfW – Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau, Bank for Reconstruction

MAP – Marktanreizprogramm, Market Incentive Programme

RSE – Renovation Support for the Elderly

VCD – Verkehrsclub Deutschland, German Association for Transport

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

When taking a close look at implemented policy instruments in Germany, there are several ones that could be combined with energy efficiency. As the energy transition is a major policy stream of the German government and energy efficiency is one of its central pillars, advantages regarding reducing the burden on the environment, pushing the national environment economy, or securing jobs could be high. This is more and more seen by politics, as some of the described policy instruments are already recommended to be combined with energy efficiency issues.

This is for example the case with the “Renovation Support for the Elderly”. It is a KfW programme for renovating buildings regarding the increasement of living comfort for the elderly. When renovating anyway, it makes sense to include an energy efficient refurbishment. Therefore, KfW recommends the combination with such a programme.

A more direct link to energy efficiency is the construction of buildings with renewable energy systems. Described here is the example of the MAP programme for big solar thermal used for hot water generation, that can be combined with the KfW programme for energy efficiency construction.

The same applies for the transport sector. In this sector as well, policy areas are given that could be combined with energy efficiency policies. Exemplarily described here are the CO₂-related motor vehicle tax, this tax was reformed in 2009 in order to include a CO₂-component, and the company car taxation. This tax does not include any environment-related component and even supports high fuel usage.

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.1.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR – MARKET INCENTIVE PROGRAMME

Introduction

In Germany, several financial policy instruments for the support of energy-efficient construction / renovation, as well as for the use of renewable energies (e.g. for heating, cooling, electricity) exist. These instruments are closely interlinked (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy 2014) and some of these instruments already can be combined, some not. Two programmes that can be combined, are described here: The **BAFA-MAP-programme** (Marktanreizprogramm zur Förderung von Maßnahmen zur Nutzung erneuerbarer Energien im Wärmemarkt / market incentive programme for supporting measures for using renewable energies in heating) **for big solar thermal used for hot water generation** (BAFA 2015) and the **KfW-programme “Energy-efficient Construction / KfW-55 Efficiency House”** (KfW 2014).

The **BAFA** support for the use of big solar thermal panel systems for hot water production supports innovative big solar thermal panel systems of 20 sqm up to 100 sqm gross panel surface, that are used for hot water generation in residential buildings with at least three dwelling units or in non-residential buildings with at least 500 sqm useful area. The BAFA-allowance is 75 EUR per sqm gross panel surface at the initial installation. The target groups of this programme include private persons, local authorities, registered associations, churches, companies, and contractors.

This programme can be combined with the support programme of **KfW** that includes long-term and low interest rate loan financing in order to build or to first-buy KfW Efficiency houses with low energy consumption and low CO₂ emissions (BAFA 2015, KfW 2014). The support further aims to reduce the financial burden of building and heating costs make these costs calculable for the user in the long-term. The target group of this programme are all investors into new-build residential buildings (for own use or rent) and owner-occupied flats. Investors in this case are e.g. private persons, flat owner communities, housing corporations, housing cooperatives, owners / operators of residential homes, public corporations, public agencies, and contractors.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Impacts on energy efficiency due to the combination of these instruments can be expected. Unfortunately, there is no study on this available.

BAFA support was raised in April 2015 and the number of applications was 32% higher in June 2015 than in the year before (Sonnenhaus-Institut 2015). In 2013 close to 12,000 applications for KfW-55 Efficiency houses have been accepted. In total (all KfW Efficiency Houses), 336 GWh/a have been saved in 2013 compared to the reference case (IWU et al. 2014).

Existing barriers might be the complexity of the support programmes and the fact that not all support programmes can be combined. BAFA only supports innovative technologies and not each KfW energy efficiency programme can be combined with other support for installation of renewable energy devices. On the other hand, possibilities for the combination of support programmes are often displayed in the description of programmes.

Actors that would benefit from a full consideration of energy efficiency would be the investors buying / constructing buildings that are energy efficient and solely use renewable energies.

Interaction between objectives

Both programmes want to push the energy transition. While the MAP aims to motivate building owners to base their heating system on renewable energies, the KfW programme focusses on the energy efficiency of buildings. As both, renewable energy and energy efficiency, are important pillars of the German energy transition, the combination of the described programmes is useful and in line with the national energy policy.

Interaction between target groups

The described programmes have a common target group. In principal, building owners is the main target group of both programmes. An indirect common target group are energy consultants. While for the KfW programme it is mandatory to include an energy consultant, in the MAP programme it is recommended.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

The MAP and KfW programmes do not interact due to any trading commodities, they interact due to common energy policy targets. However, they both affect the market of energy consultant services, as such services are relevant for both programmes.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

The MAP programme is implemented by BAFA, which is a superior federal authority subordinated to the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy. The KfW programme "Energy Efficient Construction" is supported by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy as well. While both organisations are working independently, they have the backing of the Ministry. This has the advantage, that overlappings in the financial support schemes can be prevented.

1.1.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR – CO₂-RELATED MOTOR VEHICLE TAX

Introduction

The motor vehicle tax is an annual tax which the registered keeper of a vehicle is liable for. Until 2009 the motor vehicle tax was a matter of the Federal States and it was based on the cylinder capacity and the European emission class. Since 2009 the motor vehicle tax is a matter of the national level and the taxable base has changed as CO₂ emissions influence the tax rate. Since then, the motor vehicle tax consists of a base tax which is still based on the cylinder capacity and of a CO₂-tax which is

based on the CO₂ emissions for all new vehicles which are firstly registered after the 1st July 2009. (There are no changes for cars which were firstly registered before.)

Main goal of the reformation is a contribution to climate protection by giving incentives to choose low emission vehicles when considering the purchase of a new one as the CO₂ tax is proportional to emissions above a certain threshold.

Such a CO₂ tax was claimed by e.g. environmental organisations like the VCD (German Association for Transport 2009).

Relation to Energy Efficiency

In principle, the annual motor vehicle tax can provide stronger incentives to choose low emission vehicles when considering the purchase, since they must be paid annually as for example any kind of tax which has to be paid only once. Thus, impacts on energy efficiency can also be expected. As lower CO₂ emissions are also an indicator for a lower fuel consumption, vehicles with low CO₂ emissions are also energy-efficient vehicles.

In order to unfold the full impact, existing barriers and remaining weaknesses have to be overcome. One remaining weakness consists of comparatively low CO₂ tax rates. Higher CO₂ tax rates than 2 EUR per g/km emitted above a certain threshold could unfold a higher steering effect.

However, the high share of commercial vehicles on new registered cars (61,8%) in comparison to a relatively small share of private vehicles on new registered cars (38,2%) in 2012 (Website Kraftfahrtbundesamt 2015) is another barrier in regard to energy efficiency. Because of the existing company car taxation scheme (compare chapter 1.2.2), there is no real incentive for considering low operating costs when purchasing a car.

Interaction between objectives

The CO₂-related motor vehicle tax can be linked with the eco tax on motor fuels. With its ecological tax¹ reform the German Government aimed to encourage energy saving and promote renewable energies. Whereas the motor vehicle tax is an annual tax with no direct link to the actual level of use, the eco-tax has a direct connection to the level of use and aims at internalising a part of the external costs.

Both policy instruments have been implemented to improve the efficiency of the vehicles fleet as well as vehicle use and influence the modal choice. It was estimated that the implementation of the CO₂-based motor vehicle tax will lead to GHG emission reduction of about 3 million tons CO₂e per year by 2020 (Federal Environmental Agency 2009).

Interaction between target groups

The described policy instruments have the more or less the target groups: The motor vehicle tax directs the vehicle owner and the eco-tax on motor fuels directs the vehicle driver. The category of persons is often identical.

¹ Additionally, the ecological tax reform aimed at creating new jobs, as parallel to the introduction of the eco-tax, contribution rates for statutory pensions insurance – and consequently the nonwage labour costs – were reduced.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

The motor vehicle tax as well as the eco-tax would tackle the same trading commodity – vehicles. However, both instruments are completely independent from each other.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

Both taxes (motor vehicle tax and eco tax) have been implemented by the national government and are taxes on the national level. The customs authorities are responsible for the assessment and levying the motor vehicle tax all the way to enforcement. The local customs offices, under supervision of the Federal Ministry of Finance, ensure the collection of the eco taxes.

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.2.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR – RENOVATION SUPPORT FOR THE ELDERLY

Introduction

The programme Renovation Support for the Elderly (RSE; Germ.: Altersgerechter Umbau), managed by the Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW), is quite a good example of an instruments with an indirect connection to energy efficiency measures in the building sector. In particular, Renovation Support for the Elderly aims at removing barriers in buildings and, ultimately, increases the living comfort for elderly people.

While the programme is a financing instrument, it actually consists of two elements. On the one hand, there is the loan component, which provides a low-interest loan of up to EUR 50,000 to building owners seeking to remove barriers of their building or investors that invest in residential buildings without barriers. On the other hand, as an alternative to the loan sum, a grant of up to EUR 5,000 is offered to house or apartment owners. Moreover, the grant is also available to tenants if the landlord approves to removing barriers in a residential building. Please note that there is no age limit for respective target groups to gain access to the instrument.

Funding is eligible for the installation of a stairlift, removal of certain barriers (e.g. stairs) at the house entrance or canopies for car parks or exterior doors to, e.g., reduce the danger of slipping.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

The policy instrument itself does not include an energy efficiency criteria. Even those few elements, which are eligible for funding and consume energy (e.g. stairlifts, lifts), do not include any energy efficiency requirements. However, KfW recommends to combine the Renovation Support for the Elderly programme with the Energy Efficient Renovation (EER) programme, which is also managed by KfW (KfW 2015a, 2015b). The combination of both instruments is also recommended by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy 2014a).

KfW's Energy Efficient Renovation programme, described already in D.1.2., aims at facilitating energy efficiency in Germany's existing building stock. It does so – similarly to the Renovation Support for the Elderly programme – by offering either a soft-loan (including a grant redeployment) or a direct grant. The conditions of the financing support are dependent on the degree of energy efficiency sought to be realised. The loan of the Energy Efficient Renovation programme may amount to EUR 100,000. Hence, if an investors combines the loan components of RSE with EER, up to EUR 150,000 can be made available through KfW financing. EER's direct grant does not exceed EUR 30,000, but combined with the RSE-grant, an investor can receive up to EUR 35,000.

The nexus between RSE and energy efficiency has not be assessed in close detail yet. According to Prognos (2015), 30% and 50% of interviewed building owners and tenants, respectively, said that energetic building renovation was the primary reason for taking up measures to remove barriers in their buildings. Unfortunately, this figures does not provide any information, whether interviewees, in fact, also opted for the EER programme. Further research on the relation between these two issues is to be done for the future.

Interaction between objectives

The Renovation Support for the Elderly and the Energy Efficient Renovation programmes can be seen as perfect complements. Both instruments require relatively comprehensive renovation activities carried out by experts. Hence, if a building owner makes use of both instruments, two objectives (elderly-appropriate *and* energy-efficient living space) can be achieved more or less simultaneously. For the Government, these programmes are also beneficial as complements. First, through the RSE, the Government provides living space for the elderly. Second, through the EER, the energy consumption in the building sector is reduced.

Interaction between target groups

The direct target group of RSE and EER consists building of owners and of tenants. According to Prognos (2015), the majority (>70%) of applicants for the RSE are older than 55 years, even though there is no such thing like an age limit for application.

Apart from that, both policy instruments address different types of building experts and crafts men realising the different measures funded by RSE and EER. Hence, through the programmes, a greater variety of actors can be involved in building renovation.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

While the interaction between the discussed policy instruments is intended, KfW does not make this combination mandatory. However, for building owners that seek to renovate a building, it appears reasonable to gain access to both, the RSE and the EER. In particular, it is unreasonable to, first, renovate a building in order to increase its energy efficiency and, then, to again renovate the same building to remove barriers only a few years later.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

It is of great advantage that KfW is responsible for implementing both, the RSE and the EER. As mentioned above, both instruments consist of two alternative options for building owners to be accessible – a soft-loan option and a direct grant option. With respect to the latter, building owners can apply with KfW straightaway. However, for the loan option(s) interested parties have to go to their house banks, which check the clients' creditworthiness and, then, facilitate the application to KfW.

The state-owned bank KfW can be considered an ideal implementing agent for both programmes, since it has substantial experience in providing financing to enhance the German building sector. The institution was founded after the Second World War in order to ease the living situation in the country. Since KfW does not have any local branches, the choice to make use of existing structures (house banks) for facilitating loans reduces the administrative (and financial) burden for KfW and is also beneficial to respective house banks, which receive a profit margin due to processing the loan.

1.2.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR – COMPANY CAR TAXATION

Introduction

Purchasing and operational cost of company cars are tax deductible. The employee has only to pay a very low tax on the vehicle ("1%-method"²). De facto, as the 1% method is far too low to reflect the actual benefit received, there are strong incentives for the employees to drive fuel-inefficient vehicles as much as possible. Thus, the taxation of company cars thwarts the objectives of reducing greenhouse gases and improving energy efficiency in the transport sector.

From the companies point of view, it is also very attractive to provide a company car instead of increasing the employee's salary, because the employer has to pay lower contributions for the social security ("1%-method"). However, even more important are the regulations for the depreciation of company cars. The employer can depreciate the full acquisition costs as well as operating costs. Thus, the more expensive (in purchasing and in operating, e.g. because of high fuel consumption) , the more can be deducted.

Since more than 60% of the German new car registrations are company cars in 2012 (Website Kraftfahrtbundesamt 2015), this tax-exempt is a major gap for the regulative effectiveness of CO₂-related car taxation and counteracts the efforts to increase the energy efficiency in the transport sector.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

As mentioned above, the company car taxation thwarts the objective of improving energy efficiency in the company vehicle fleet. However, the company vehicle fleet influences the fleet of private cars significantly. As company cars are usually replaced sooner than private vehicles and most of the replaced company cars are up for sale on the used-car market. Thus, there is an oversupply of big cars with high fuel consumption.

A solution would be a CO₂-related tax exemption which would be effective beyond a margin that refers to the shifting fleet emission limits (e.g. 100 g when the emission limit is 130 g, 90 g when the limit is 120 g, etc.) as suggested by a joint expert report from Green Budget Germany (/Forum Ökologisch-Soziale Marktwirtschaft) (Görres and Meyer 2008).

Within the research project "tax treatment of company cars in Germany" several improvements of the company car taxation system have been developed in order to – among others – contribute to a reduction in CO₂ emissions instead of subsidizing big, inefficient vehicles.

It is suggested to introduce a CO₂ element ("climate factor") which is oriented towards the European Regulation for the reduction of CO₂ emissions from light-duty vehicles. "Either a bonus-malus system, or a penalty-based system, are possible options. The increments are related to emission values and time. The range of deduction extends from 50% (very poor emission values) to 150% (very good emission values) of the purchase cost. The CO₂ component also relates to the deductibility of the cost of fuel" (Finanzwissenschaftliches Forschungsinstitut an der Universität zu Köln 2011).

² These so-called benefits in kind are calculated using the so-called „1%-method“, which adds 1 % of the car's list price to an employee's taxable income each month.

Interaction between objectives

Currently, there is no interaction between the objectives of the company car taxation and energy efficiency policy. This would become the case, if the suggested introduction of a CO₂ element would be implemented into the company car taxation.

Interaction between target groups

The target group of the company car taxation are companies and their employees. So far, this target group has not been directly focused by national energy efficiency policy.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

There is a strong interaction between a proposed CO₂-related company car taxation and a CO₂-related motor vehicle tax possible, as the CO₂-related company car taxation could include many issues of the motor vehicle tax.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

The same national authorities would be responsible for the implementation of a CO₂-related company car tax as for the CO₂-related motor vehicle tax. Therefore, already existing governance structures could be used.

REFERENCES

BAFA (2015): Antrag auf Innovationsförderung einer thermischen Solaranlage zur Warmwasserbereitung und / oder Heizungsunterstützung nach den Richtlinien des Bundesministeriums für Wirtschaft und Energie (BMWi) zur Förderung von Maßnahmen zur Nutzung erneuerbarer Energien im Wärmemarkt. URL: http://www.bafa.de/bafa/de/energie/erneuerbare_energien/solarthermie/innovations_und_zusatzfoerderung/warmwasser_anlagen/ee_ifa_so_wr.pdf (2015-08-15)

Federal Environmental Agency (2009): Politikszenerarien für den Klimaschutz V – auf dem Weg zum Strukturwandel. Treibhausgas-Emissionsszenarien bis zum Jahr 2030. Dessau. URL: <http://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/publikation/long/3764.pdf> (2015-08-13)

Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (2014): A good bit of work. Making more out of energy. National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency. URL: <http://www.bmwi.de/English/Redaktion/Pdf/nape-national-action-plan-on-energy-efficiency,property=pdf,bereich=bmwi2012,sprache=en,rwb=true.pdf> (2015-08-13)

Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (2014a): Energetisch und altersgerecht sanieren. Ein Ratgeber für Wohnungseigentümergeinschaften. URL: <http://www.bmwi.de/BMWi/Redaktion/PDF/E/energetisch-und-altersgerecht-sanieren,property=pdf,bereich=bmwi2012,sprache=de,rwb=true.pdf> (2015-08-13)

Finanzwirtschaftliches Forschungsinstitut an der Universität zu Köln (2011): Steuerliche Behandlung von Firmenwagen in Deutschland. Online: http://www.foes.de/pdf/2011_Firmenwagenbesteuerung_lang.pdf. (2015-08-15)

Görres, A.; Meyer, B (2008): Dienstwagenbesteuerung modernisieren: Für Klimaschutz und mehr Gerechtigkeit. Kurzgutachten des Forum Ökologisch-Soziale Marktwirtschaft im Auftrag von Greenpeace.

IEA (2014): Capturing the multiple benefits of energy efficiency. URL: <https://www.iea.org/Textbase/npsum/MultipleBenefits2014SUM.pdf> (2015-05-28)

IWU – Institut Wohnen und Umwelt GmbH et al. (2014): Monitoring der KfW-Programme “Energieeffizient Sanieren” und “Energieeffizient Bauen” 2013. On behalf of KfW Bankengruppe. URL: https://www.kfw.de/PDF/Download-Center/Konzernthemen/Research/PDF-Dokumente-alle-Evaluationen/Monitoringbericht_2013_05-12-2014.pdf (2015-08-15)

KfW (2014): Merkblatt Bauen, Wohnen, Energie sparen – Energieeffizient bauen. URL: [https://www.kfw.de/PDF/Download-Center/Förderprogramme-\(Inlandsförderung\)/PDF-Dokumente/6000003103_M_153.pdf](https://www.kfw.de/PDF/Download-Center/Förderprogramme-(Inlandsförderung)/PDF-Dokumente/6000003103_M_153.pdf) (2015-08-15)

KfW (2015a): Merkblatt – Altersgerecht Umbauen – Kredit. [https://www.kfw.de/PDF/Download-Center/Förderprogramme-\(Inlandsförderung\)/PDF-Dokumente/6000003091_M_159_AU.pdf](https://www.kfw.de/PDF/Download-Center/Förderprogramme-(Inlandsförderung)/PDF-Dokumente/6000003091_M_159_AU.pdf) (2015-08-15)

KfW (2015b): Merkblatt – Altersgerecht Umbauen – Zuschuss. [https://www.kfw.de/PDF/Download-Center/Förderprogramme-\(Inlandsförderung\)/PDF-Dokumente/6000003270_M_455_AU_Zuschuss.pdf](https://www.kfw.de/PDF/Download-Center/Förderprogramme-(Inlandsförderung)/PDF-Dokumente/6000003270_M_455_AU_Zuschuss.pdf) (2015-08-15)

Prognos (2015): Endbericht - Evaluation des KfW- Programms Altersgerecht Umbauen.

http://www.prognos.com/uploads/tx_atwpubdb/140729_Evaluation-KfW-Programm-Altersgerecht-Umbauen.pdf (2015-08-15)

Sonnenhaus-Institut (2015): Sonnenhaus-Institut begrüßt steigende Solarthermie-Nachfrage; BMWi gewährt im MAP höchsten Zuschuss für große Solar-Heizungen. URL:

<http://www.solarserver.de/solar-magazin/nachrichten/aktuelles/2015/kw31/sonnenhaus-institut-begruesst-steigende-solarthermie-nachfrage-bmwi-gewaehrt-im-map-hoechsten-zuschuss-fuer-grosse-solar-heizungen.html> (2015-08-15)

German Association for Transport (Verkehrsclub Deutschland, VCD) (2009): Kfz-Steuer als Klimasteuer. VCD-Modell für eine Kfz-Steuer auf CO2-Basis. URL:

https://www.vcd.org/fileadmin/user_upload/Redaktion/Themen/Auto_Umwelt/Auto_Steuern/2009_0130_VCD_Kfz-Steuer-Modell_und_Steuerrechner.pdf (2015-08-15)

Website Kraftfahrtbundesamt (2015): Privat und gewerblich zugelassene Personenkraftwagen – der kleine Unterschied.online

http://www.kba.de/DE/Statistik/Fahrzeuge/Neuzulassungen/Halter/2012/2012_n_firmenwagen_diagramm.html?nn=1036776. (2015-08-15)

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D1.3

INTERLINKAGES AND SYNERGIES BETWEEN SELECTED OTHER POLICY AREAS AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY

D.1.3

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND AVAILABLE
TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT**

Partner: Energy Policy & Development Centre – National & Kapodistrian University of Athens

NATIONAL REPORT

HELLAS, AUGUST 2015

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Universiteit
Antwerpen

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: Energy Policy & Development Centre – National & Kapodistrian University of Athens

Steering Committee member ⁽¹⁾: Prof. Dimitrios MAVRAKIS

Prepared by: Dr. Popi KONIDARI, Anna FLESSA, Aliko-Nefeli MAVRAKI, Eleni-Danai MAVRAKI

⁽¹⁾ The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACRONYMS 5

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY 6

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS 7

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY 7

1.1.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR.....7

1.1.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR.....11

1.1.3 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR 16

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY 16

1.2.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR.....16

1.2.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR 16

REFERENCES.....22

Table of Tables

Table 1: Average thermal energy consumption per household – Percentage distribution by type of end-use.12

Table 2: PV Installations per category..... 12

Table 3: Feed-in-tariffs for PV systems installed on roofs..... 15

ACRONYMS

CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CRES	Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving
DSHWS	Domestic Solar Hot Water Systems
EC	European Commission
EE	Energy Efficiency
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GPP	Green Public Procurement
HEDNO S.A.	Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator S.A.
HELAPCO	Hellenic Association of Photovoltaic Companies
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
KENAK	Greek abbreviation for Regulation for the Energy Efficiency of Buildings
LED	Light Emitting Diode
MEECC	Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change
MEIST	Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism
NEEAP	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
OASA	Athens Urban Transport Organisation
PPP	Public-Private-Partnerships
PV	Photovoltaic
RAE	Regulatory Authority for Energy
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
ROI	Return Of Investment
TISA	Traveller Information Services Association

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The policy interactions are an important parameter for the successful implementation of policies, measures and policy instruments. The parallel implementation of a number of policy instruments has the potential to create synergies or conflicts that maximize or prevent the achievement of their anticipated outcomes. This report presents cases of positive policy interactions between two policy instruments for promoting even more the energy efficiency outcomes in Greece for two sectors, buildings and transport. The case studies refer to existing policy instruments that are linked directly and indirectly with energy. There are no officially recorded outcomes or evaluations for the parallel implementation of these policy instruments.

These Hellenic case studies are:

- “Energy labelling” and “Green Public Procurement” (for the building and the transport sector) – Direct link with energy;
- “Regulation for the Energy Efficiency of Buildings (KENAK)” and the “*Specific Program for the Development of Photovoltaic systems on buildings and specifically on their lofts and roofs*” (Only for the building sector) – Direct link with energy;
- “Planning policy instrument for Intelligent Transport Systems” and “Emission standards (Euro 5 and Euro 6)” (only for the transport sector) – Indirect link with energy.

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS

In current debates the multiple benefits of energy efficiency are broadly discussed and available analyses are growing in number (e.g. IEA, 2014a - report on multiple benefits). However, in some cases energy savings can rather be seen as the co-benefit of other policies or measures, which do not target energy efficiency by design.

The aim of this task is to identify policy areas suitable for combination with energy efficiency policies and systematically analyse how they may contribute to improve energy efficiency, particularly if untapped energy saving potentials still exist.

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.1.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

Introduction

The first case study is about the policy Interactions between the policy instruments of “Energy labeling” and “Green Public Procurement”. Both policy instruments concern **the building and the transport sector** and are presented analytically in *D.1.2 - Status Quo analysis of energy efficiency policies in 8 EU countries*.

They were selected as one of the few identified examples of policy interactions within the Hellenic framework and because of the amount of available information about them compared to other national policy instruments. They serve as an existing example of understanding the positive manner under which two policy instruments interact in achieving the outcomes for which they were designed and implemented for.

Relation to energy efficiency

Both policy instruments concern the policy area of energy efficiency. There are no official national assessments about their outcomes either individually or as a combination.

The outcomes of a survey regarding the implementation of the Green Public Procurement (GPP) in the EU27, showed that Greece had a below 20% GPP uptake performance (Centre for European Policy Studies and the College of Europe, 2012). This low percentage can be attributed to the fact that the “Green Public Procurement” has a short implementation period (set into force in 2005) compared to the “Energy labeling” (introduced in 1994). As described in *D.2.1 - Working paper on Social, Economic, Cultural and Educational Barriers in Buildings and Transport* the main barriers for the implementation of the “Green Public Procurement” in the country are linked with the public authorities (educational, informative and institutional barriers).

On the other hand for the “Energy-labelling” (referred also as a type of “Eco-labelling”), four out of ten people stated that the environmental impact of a product or service influences their purchasing decision (European Commission, 2015). Consumers mention frequently (along with price) that they trust the energy label and consider it when purchasing electrical household appliances (European Commission, 2015).

Out of the entities of the whole public sector, local authorities mainly were more active in implementing both policy instruments. The following cases are indicative:

- *Purchase of four multifunctional photocopiers - Municipality of Pilea-Hortiatis*¹. The technical specifications of the tender included energy and environmental criteria (indicatively such as Energy Star Certification, Blue Angel Certification, environmentally friendly ingredients (percentage of recycled plastic), Recyclability after Lifecycle, Ecological packaging etc) (Buy Smart+Pilot project – Municipality of Pilea-Hortiatis, 2014). The estimated results for this procurement - when compared to conventional photocopiers without the required energy characteristics asked - were a total of 79MWh and 31 t CO₂ throughout the machines lifetime (7 years)² (Buy Smart+Pilot project – Municipality of Pilea-Hortiatis, 2014).
- *Replacement of old lighting in student dorms with LED lamps - Technological Educational Institute of Thessaly (Larisa)*. The overall saving during lamp life (up to 15 years) will be 824 MWh, 342 tons of CO₂ and 29.780 EUR (Buy Smart+Pilot project – Technological Educational Institute of Thessaly (Larisa), 2014).
- *Replacement of four Euro 1 emission standard vehicles with four Euro 5 emissions vehicles – Municipality of Kalamaria*³. The annual savings are estimated to be 1,34tnCO₂, 0,29tn HC, 2,68tn NO_x, 0,26tn PM and 35MWh (Buy Smart+Pilot project – Municipality of Kalamaria, 2014).
- *Purchase of nine diesel ambulances for replacing old gasoline ones – Ministry of Health*. The diesel engines have a better fuel economy by 20 to 30% compared to the gasoline ones and 20,25 tonnes CO₂ less throughout the lifetime of the vehicle (250.000km). The total energy savings throughout the lifetime of the vehicles (250.000km) are estimated to be worth of 110.000 EUR according to fuel prices of the time of calculation (Buy Smart+Pilot project – Ministry of Health, 2014).

Interaction between objectives

The Energy Labelling Directive (and the Ecodesign Directive) aims to address the negative impact of products on the environment depending on how they are made, used and disposed of by 'pulling' the market towards more energy efficient products (European Commission, 2015).

Its objectives for fulfilling this aim are (European Commission, 2015): i) Increasing energy efficiency and the level of protection of the environment; ii) informing consumers about the energy efficiency and other resources use of products through an energy label, and encouraging them to buy more energy efficient ones; iii) Ensuring the free movement of energy-related products in the European Union.

In line with the aforementioned objectives, for the Hellenic case, the Ministerial Decision 12400/1108/29 (Government Gazette 2301 B, 14.10.2011⁴) defines as objective to enact a

¹ Suburb of the Thessaloniki urban area

² Assuming that conventional photocopiers today at full operating temperature may consume about 1600kWh per year whereas an energy star photocopiers consumes 900kWh per year.

³ Second largest municipality in population in the regional unit of Thessaloniki

⁴

http://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&frm=1&source=web&cd=2&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CCkQFjABahUKEwixv_GOz5HHAhUJORQKHdKrAX8&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.ydmed.gov.gr%2Fwp-content%2Fuploads%2F2011_09_10_diminiaio.doc&ei=4tXBVfHGEOnyUNLXhvgH&usg=AFQjCNFSqq8d5JaYRHWaeMdvBaHCMGeA8Q&bvm=bv.99261572,d.d24 and http://www.et.gr/idocs-nph/search/pdfViewerForm.html?args=5C7QrtC22wFYAFdDx4L2G3dtvSoClrl8zS83ZvoDVVQtiDow6HITE-JlnJ48_97uHrMts-zFzeyCiBSQOpYnTy36MacmUFCx2ppFvBej56Mmc8Qdb8ZfRjQznsIAdk8Lv_e6czmhEembNmZCMxLMtZqO3PZEZmZ4PAm4MxQaM4YkkPuOjFkftnSx0GKTOsdy

framework for: i) providing information to the end-users through the labeling and ii) quoting uniform information regarding the product (energy consumption and occasionally other basic resources during usage) and supplementary information about products related with energy. The aim is the end-users to be able to select more efficient products.

For the second policy instrument, the relevant information follows. The purpose of the EU Green Public Procurement (GPP) policy instrument is to use the purchasing power of the EU Member States governments to stimulate the markets for goods and services with lower impacts on the environment (BIO Intelligence Service, 2013). Energy efficient products and services are promoted for use by the public sector.

The policy interaction is positive since both policy instruments through their objectives (primary and secondary) aim to support energy efficient products and services.

Interaction between target groups

For the Hellenic case of “Energy labeling” the target groups include end-users in households and producers of the respective products. The energy labeling is applied to those products that have a significant direct or indirect effect on energy consumption and depending on the case of other resources during their use. It is not applied to: i) second hand products; ii) to transportation means of persons or merchandise; iii) on the indicative signal or the equivalent label for security reasons that is attached on the product.

For the GPP the target groups are public⁵ and private entities that sign contracts covering: Energy efficient computers, Office furniture from sustainable timber, Low energy buildings, Recycled paper, Cleaning services using environmentally friendly cleaning products, Electric, hybrid or low-emission vehicles, Electricity from renewable energy sources (European Commission and ICLEI – Local governments for Sustainability, 2011).

The target groups of the two policy instruments are different. There is no direct policy interaction under the target groups of these policy instruments. For Energy Labelling the target group consists of end-users (citizens) coming from the building and the transport sector, while for GPP the target groups are public entities. Producers and manufacturers of such products and services – whose participation is optional, particularly for the GPP - are benefitted indirectly by the implementation of both policy instruments.

Interactions between rules - influencing mechanisms

The Energy Labelling (or Eco-labelling) standards can be used as preconditions for the tenders of the GPP. This option facilitates the implementation of the GPP and reinforces the implementation of the Energy labelling standards. The reasons are: i) energy or eco-labelling is characterized by a significant potential to contribute to an effective reduction of environmental impacts associated to economic activities due to its criteria which take into account the environmental impacts that products may have in their life-cycle (Domingues A.R. et al., 2015); ii) they provide consumers/users with the information to select products energy efficient or least harmful to the environment since independent third parties narrow the information gap by assuring consumers/users about which product meets those energy or environmental standards (Domingues A.R. et al., 2015).

The public sector is expected to lead in such efforts for the fulfillment of energy efficiency targets due to the significant number of human resources, the services that it provides, the consumption of resources, its size and influence, particularly at the local level (Domingues A.R. et al., 2015). When

⁵ Public sector, first and second level of local authorities, companies whose stock share belongs to the public sector or local authorities - Public transport sector

public entities and specifically the local authorities, adopt the energy or eco-labelling criteria in the tenders of GPP they set out an example. If information about this example is accessible through web-sites, social media, etc then more end-users (citizens and companies of the private sector) are likely to be positively influenced. It is indicative that the majority of environmental related label initiatives for goods and services were produced by the private sector (Domingues A.R. et al., 2015). This is evident by the products that are covered by the EU ecolabel or by the overview provided by Ecolabel Index (Domingues A.R. et al., 2015).

The incorporation of sustainable development principles and practices (ie energy or eco-labelling and GPP) into processes of the multi-level governance structure, including policy formulation and operations is crucial since the public sector as a total represents an important part of international economic activities (Domingues A.R. et al., 2015).

This is a positive policy interaction between rules-influencing mechanisms of the two policy instruments.

Interactions between the implementation network/ governance structure

MEECC is responsible for the implementation of the “Energy labelling”, and particularly, the General Secretariat of Industry at the Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (MEECC⁶)). The Public Economic Services, the Service of Special Audits of the Ministry of Finance, Hellenic Police, Chambers and Regions will also contribute for the market monitoring if the pertinent authority decides their involvement.

For GPP, the MEECC was assigned as the authority responsible to design the National Policy and drawing of a National Action Plan for promoting the Green Public Procurements (Law 3855/2010 - Government Gazette 95 A, 23.06.2010⁷). MEECC will need to cooperate with other Ministries and bodies of the public and private sector for proceeding with the necessary legislative settings and measures for implementing the “Green Public Procurements”. For the better coordination of these efforts an eleven member Interministerial Committee was established⁸. Its Members are: The Minister of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (Head of Committee), The Minister of Finance, The Minister of Productive Reconstruction, Environment and Energy (Former MEECC), The Minister(s) who supervise(s) each of the Public Bodies that are examining the implementation of PPP projects, under their competencies.

There is a direct policy interaction since the MEECC is mainly responsible for the implementation of both policy instruments. However, due to the lack of information about the implementation of both policy instruments, the policy interaction can be characterized as negative for this part. This is justified as follows: i) There is still no national action plan about the Green Public Procurement⁹. Greece, along with Croatia, Estonia, Hungary, Luxemburg and Romania has not submitted such a plan. This situation imposes administrative burden to the implementation network. ii) there are no tenders with criteria related to Energy or eco-labelling or energy efficiency¹⁰ on the Hellenic web-page for PPP. This is attributed to the inadequate implementation network (lack of skills and knowledge to use the energy or eco-labelling standards under the GPP, lack of relevant studies, available perhaps but non-accessible information for the public through web-sites). This second reason is significant also from the perspective that public authorities are expected to be open and

⁶ http://www.cres.gr/kape/calendar/progr_ypapen_8_6_15.pdf

⁷ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=AxgQsUVAUjA%3d&tabid=506>

⁸ <http://www.sdit.mnec.gr/en/information>

⁹ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/action_plan_en.htm

¹⁰ <http://www.sdit.mnec.gr/en/information/PPP/procedures>

transparent about the management of the public funds and assets (Domingues A.R. et al., 2015). The interaction can become positive if the necessary actions are undertaken (establish a pertinent authority with qualified staff etc).

1.1.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

Introduction

The second case study is about the policy Interactions between the policy instruments of “*Regulation for the Energy Performance of Buildings (KENAK)*” and “*Specific Program for the Development of Photovoltaic systems on buildings and specifically on their lofts and roofs*”. The first policy instrument was presented analytically in D.1.2. The second one will be described in this session. This pair of policy instruments was identified and selected as a case study due to significant market share that Greece has in the European solar market.

More specifically, solar energy systems either as solar thermal systems or as photovoltaics have very high penetration rates in Greece (Tsalikis G. and Martinopoulos G., 2015). For year 2013, the Hellenic Photovoltaic (PV) market exceeded the 1GW mark, recording PV capacity of 1,04GW and ranking fifth in the European market behind Germany, United Kingdom, Italy and Romania (European Photovoltaic Industry Association, 2014). The residential segment of this market has developed rapidly from year 2012 to 2013 (European Photovoltaic Industry Association, 2014).

During year 2014, there were positive signs for the Hellenic solar thermal market which grew by 18,9% compared to year 2013 (European Solar Thermal Industry Federation, 2015). Domestic Solar Hot Water Systems (DSHWS) are characterized as mature and widely available technology, with installed capacity of 4,2 million m² (2.900 MW_{th}) at the end of 2013 from 4,1 million m² (2,8 MW_{th}) at the end of 2011 (Tsalikis G. and Martinopoulos G., 2015; Martinopoulos G. and Tsalikis G., 2014). In 2014, the total installed capacity reached the 3 GW_{th} (4,3 million m²), representing an increase of 2,6% over the previous year and providing an estimated energy supply of 2.989 GW_{th}, which corresponds to 52% of the indicative 2020 target (European Solar Thermal Industry Federation, 2015). The increase during the period 2013-2014 is attributed to investments in the Hellenic tourism sector (European Solar Thermal Industry Federation, 2015).

The newly installed capacity was 189 MW_{th}, representing 270.000 m² of newly installed collector area and the majority was for hot water supply in the tourism sector/islands (hotels, holiday lets, etc.) (European Solar Thermal Industry Federation, 2015). There was also a welcome market upturn for replacing old solar thermal systems with new ones (European Solar Thermal Industry Federation, 2015).

In 2014 Greece ranked second with 9% in the shares of the European Solar Thermal Market (Newly Installed Capacity) behind Germany with 31% (European Solar Thermal Industry Federation, 2015). In 2012, Greece was fifth with 7% in the shares of the European Solar Thermal Market (Newly Installed Capacity) (European Solar Thermal Industry Federation, 2013).

Although photovoltaics are characterized as a relatively new technology for the Hellenic residential market, more than 40.000 systems were installed in residential buildings up to 2013, resulting to increased installed capacity (from 47 MW_p in 2007 to 1.536 MW_p in 2012 and to 2.579 MW_p in 2013) (Tsalikis G. and Martinopoulos G., 2015). Greece is among the ten top PV markets globally (10th in 2011 and 2012, 9th in 2013)(IEA, 2014b).

Relation to energy efficiency

In 2012 the buildings sector (residential and tertiary together) accounted for 45% of the total final energy consumption (YPEKA, 2014). Their thermal energy consumption is for space heating,

production of domestic hot water use and cooking (Table 1). In 98,6% of the Hellenic household dwellings there is a system / equipment for their needs in hot running water (Hellenic Republic, Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2013). More specifically, 74,5% of households use an electrical thermo siphon system, 37,6% a solar thermo siphon system, and 25.2% a system linked to the central heating system (boiler) (Hellenic Republic, Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2013).

Despite the economic recession, the installation of PV systems on building roofs was significant (Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013). The share of PV systems that were installed on roofs when compared to the whole Hellenic PV market demonstrated an increase from 4% in year 2010 to 19% during the first six months of year 2012 (Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013). This increase continued (Table 2). By April 2013, the installed capacity grew up to 341MW_p (HELAPCO, 2013).

Table 1: Average thermal energy consumption per household – Percentage distribution by type of end-use.

Type of end-use	Average thermal energy consumption (in %)
Space heating	85,9
Production of domestic hot water use	4,4
Cooking	9,7
Total	100,00

(Source: Hellenic Republic, Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2013)

Table 2: PV Installations per category.

Interconnected systems per category	Roofs <10 KWp	<20 KWp	20-150 KWp	150 KWp – 2MWp	>2MWp
Total installed capacity (MW _p)	298,7	62,5	582,6	395,2	198,2

(Source: YPEKA, 2014)

The combined implementation of the two policy instruments “*Regulation for the Energy Performance of Buildings (KENAK)*” and “*Specific Program for the Development of Photovoltaic systems on buildings and specifically on their lofts and roofs*” demonstrates that EE interventions are adopted favoring the introduction of RES and promoting the nearly zero energy buildings.

The Regulation for Energy Efficiency of Buildings, that was introduced in year 2008 (see details at D.1.2) focuses mainly on the heat efficiency of buildings while it includes specifications for the efficient use of electricity also.

The “*Specific Program for the Development of Photovoltaic systems on buildings and specifically on their lofts and roofs*” was set in force in year 2009 and focuses on the penetration of PV systems in the building sector. This programme is expected to contribute in the achievement of the EE target for year 2016 according to the developed methodology of the 1st National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) (Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013; First Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2008). The target of total energy savings due to the installation of PV systems in the buildings sector for the production of domestic hot water use is estimated to 4.128 GWh until year 2020 (Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013). The expected installed capacity of PV systems on lofts-roofs is expected to be by year 2020 at 1.150MW (Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013).

Under Law 3851/2010 (Government Gazette 85 A, 04.06.2010¹¹) which was devoted to the RES development a link was created between RES and EE. One of its provisions sets under KENAK the obligation that all new buildings need to “cover the total of their primary energy consumption with

¹¹ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=pnhppGnURds%3D>

energy supply systems based on RES”, focusing on solar thermal, photovoltaic and ground heat-pump systems (pellet or other biomass residential heating systems are only hinted within the overall RES terminology) (Christidou C. et al., 2014). Consequently, the law formed a favorable context especially for photovoltaic installations on buildings, taking into consideration the very high prices for the generated electricity by these installations (550 EUR /MWh) when the maximum electricity price, for the household sector, for that period according to consumption ranged from 56,25 to 91,55 EUR /MWh) (Christidou C. et al., 2014). PV investments under these conditions had pay-back periods shorter than six years (Christidou C. et al., 2014).

Policy interaction between these two policy instruments appears to be positive overall (Christidou C. et al., 2014; Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013).

Interactions between objectives

The objectives that KENAK serves are the reduction of energy consumption for heating, cooling, lighting and production and use of hot water with the simultaneous ensuring of comfort conditions for the indoor spaces of the buildings. It aims also to promote the improvement of the energy performance of buildings in Greece, considering: i) outdoor climatic and local conditions and ii) indoor climate requirements and cost-effectiveness.

The “*Specific Program for the Development of Photovoltaic systems on buildings and specifically on their lofts and roofs*” was set in force by a Joint Ministerial Decision No. 12323¹² (Government Gazette 1079 B, 04.06.2009¹³). Law 3851/2010 (Government Gazette 85 A, 04.06.2010¹⁴) had relevant provisions with more important that for the feed-in-tariffs. Law 4023/2013 (Government Gazette 235 A, 11.11.2013¹⁵) has also provisions that refer to PV systems on buildings.

The objective of the “*Specific Programme*”¹⁶ is to contribute in the achievement of the national RES penetration target. It is the combination of two types of policy instruments: i) a regulatory policy instrument due to the rules for the installation of the PV systems and ii) a financial policy instrument due to the feed-in-tariffs for the PV systems.

The two policy instruments (KENAK and the regulatory part of the “*Specific Programme*”) interact positively through their common secondary objectives. The financial policy instrument of the “*Specific Programme*” reinforces this interaction.

Interactions between target groups

For KENAK the following categories of buildings fall under its framework: i) Households of different types such as detached houses, apartments and apartment complexes; ii) Multi-apartment buildings; iii) Offices; iv) Educational buildings; v) Hospitals; vi) Hotels and restaurants; vii) Sports facilities; viii) Buildings for Wholesale and retail trade services; ix) Any other category of buildings that are consuming energy. There are exemptions such as:

¹² <http://www.desmie.gr/ape-sithya/adeiodotiki-diadikasia-kodikopoiisi-nomothesis-ape/periechomena/timologisi-energeias-apo-ape/>

¹³ http://www.cres.gr/pvcatalog/FEK_1079_2009.pdf or http://www.deddie.gr/Documents2/%CE%A6%CE%A9%CE%A4%CE%9F%CE%92%CE%9F%CE%9B%CE%A4%CE%91%CE%99%CE%9A%CE%91/eidiko%20programma%20steges/nomothesia/%CE%A6%CE%95%CE%9A%201079_4-6-2009.pdf

¹⁴ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=pnhppGnURds%3D>

¹⁵ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=6FFnUN2JqSg%3d&tabid=555&language=el-GR>

¹⁶ The term “*Specific Programme*” refers to the *Specific Program for the Development of Photovoltaic systems on buildings and specifically on their lofts and roofs*

- monuments, buildings used as worship places, industrial installations, manufactories, workshops;
- Buildings that are characterized as protected either as part of specific environment or due to their unique architecture or historical value such as preserved and located in traditional settlements are exempted up to the degree that compliance to specific Minimum requirements of energy performance for buildings would be altered by an unacceptable manner their character or appearance.
- Buildings of temporary use which based on their planning the duration of their use will not exceed the period of two years, industrial installations, laboratories, buildings for agricultural use – not residences - with low energy requirements and similar buildings that are used under a relevant national agreement that concerns the energy performance of the buildings (Law 3661/2008, Presidential Decree 100/2010; Law 4122/2013).
- buildings with a total useful floor of less than 50 square meters only the minimum requirements of Energy Performance about the building elements of the building are set (not for the technical characteristics of the installations).

The “Specific Programme” concerns Photovoltaic (PV) systems with power up to 10kW_p for buildings that are used either as households or for housing small businesses. It will last until 31 December 2019 and covers the whole Hellenic territory. Initially non-interconnected with the mainland system islands were exempted, but based on a RAE decision (1251/2010) these islands have been included since January 10th 2011¹⁷ (HELAPCO, 2013; Joint Ministerial Decision No. 12323, 2009). The allowed capacity is for them up to 5kW_p (HELAPCO, 2013). Natural persons that are non-traders and natural or legal persons that are traders (of very small businesses) can participate at the “Specific Programme” as long as they own a space at which they can install a PV system. The only condition is that there has to be an active connection for electricity consumption in the name of the PV owner at the building where the system is installed.

The two policy instruments interact between the target groups of the “Specific Programme” ie households of different types (for example detached houses, apartments and apartment complexes), multi-apartment buildings, offices, hotels – restaurants, buildings for wholesale and retail trade services and any other category of buildings that are consuming energy.

Interactions between rules-influencing mechanisms

Within the framework of the “Regulation for the Energy Performance of Buildings (KENAK)” and the provisions of Law 3851/2010¹⁸ (Government Gazette 85 A, 04.06.2010¹⁹), the use of RES in buildings and particularly the production of domestic hot water use by solar systems is obligatory for new buildings, while for those buildings that are totally renovated the needs for hot water can be covered partially by solar thermal systems (YPEKA, 2014). The minimum percentage of annual solar share (in renovated buildings) is defined at 60% (YPEKA, 2014). This obligation is not applied for the uses that are exempted by the KENAK or when needs in domestic hot water use are covered by other decentralized energy supply systems that are based on RES, CHP, tele-heating systems (regionally or building block scale), heat pumps whose seasonal performance factor must be higher than 3,3 (YPEKA, 2014).

¹⁷ <http://www.deddie.gr/el/upiresies/fwtovoltaika-kai-alles-ape/fv-tou-eidikou-programmatos-stegwn>
(available in Greek language)

¹⁸ The law is about “Accelerating the RES development and confronting climate change - other provisions for issues under the responsibility of the MEECC

¹⁹ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=pnhppGnURds%3D>

The Joint Ministerial Decision for the “Specific Programme” sets also the rule that “part of the thermal needs in domestic hot water use under the household of the PV owner needs to be covered by renewable energy sources such as solar thermal systems and solar water heaters. The PV owner should not receive public financial support due to the Development-Investment Law or European financial mechanisms or any other funding resource so as to participate at the “Specific Programme” (Joint Ministerial Decision No. 12323).

The connection to the grid and to the interconnected system of photovoltaic systems that are installed at the premises of public authorities for research purposes is possible (Law 4023/2013 – Government Gazette 235 A, 11.11.2013²⁰). Surplus of the electric energy that is provided to the system or the grid from these systems and up to 20% of the total produced energy annually is compensated according to provisions of Law 4023/2013.

The Joint Ministerial Decision No. 12323 for the “Specific Programme” has provisions about: i) contracts and solution of contract; ii) installation and operation of the PV system – connection to the grid; iii) tax treatment; iv) measurements; and v) obligations of the PV owner.

Table 3: Feed-in-tariffs for PV systems installed on roofs.

Month/Year	Feed-in-tariff (EUR/MWh)
2009	550,00
2010	550,00
2011	550,00
January 2012	522,50
August 2012	250,00
February 2013	238,5
February 2013	125,00
August 2013	125,00
February 2014	120,00
August 2014	120,00
February 2015	115,00
August 2015	115,00
February 2016	110,00
August 2016	110,00
February 2017	105,00
August 2017	100,00
February 2018	95,00
August 2018	90,00
February 2019	85,00
August 2019	80,00

Note: for years 2009, 2010, 2011 and for January 2012 the figures were defined in Government Gazette 1079 B, 04.06.2009. For February 2012 the figure was defined in Government Gazette 97 B, 31.01.2012. For August 2012 and February 2013 the figures were provided under Government Gazette 2317 B, 10.08.2012. The price changed for February 2013 by the Joint Ministerial Decision Φ1/1289/9012 (Government Gazette 1103 B, 02.05.2013²¹). (Source: YPEKA, 2015²²; HELAPCO, 2013)

²⁰

http://www.depa.gr/uploads/files/ethniko_el/FEK235_1%2011%202013_%CE%A1%CF%85%CE%B8%CE%BCE%AF%CF%83%CE%B5%CE%B9%CF%82%20%CE%98%CE%B5%CE%BC%CE%AC%CF%84%CF%89%CE%BD%20%CE%91%CE%A0%CE%95.pdf

²¹ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=CPlp8mM2iTg%3D&tabid=555&language=el-GR> or http://www.deddie.gr/Documents2/Fotovoltaiika/%CE%A6%CE%95%CE%9A%201103_2-5-2013.pdf

²² <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=785&sni%5B524%5D=2401&language=el-GR>

Rules for the feed-in-tariffs, bills and payments are also defined. In 2010 the amount of the feed-in-tariffs was 550 EUR/MWh (Law 3851/2010). New adjustments followed. The figures in Table 3 demonstrate why the feed-in-tariffs (financial policy instrument of the “Specific Programme”) were a strong incentive that contributed to the penetration of PV systems installed on lofts-roofs (HELAPCO, 2013). The target groups that fall under both policy instruments benefitted the most. Furthermore, the reduction of the average investment cost for PV systems with installed capacity up to 10kW_p was another significant factor for this penetration. The reduction was 64% comparing prices in year 2010 and 2013 (HELAPCO, 2013).

Interactions between the implementation network/ governance structure

The two main entities that are responsible for the implementation of both policy instruments are the MEECC and CRES (details can be found in D.1.1 and D.1.2). MEECC has established a special service under its supervision for providing information about investments for RES²³. The implementation network includes also the Regulatory Authority for Energy (RAE), the Technical Chamber of Greece and the Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator S.A. (HEDNO S.A.²⁴).

In 2013, because of the activities of implementation network, there were approximately 150 small and medium companies activated in the field (solar systems) with about 3.000 people working in this area (Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013).

1.1.3 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

Please see first case study. It is common case.

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.2.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

No case study.

1.2.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

Introduction

The examined policy interactions are between the planning policy instrument for “*Intelligent transport systems*” and the regulatory policy instrument for “*Emission standards (Euro 5 and 6)*”. The first policy instrument will be presented in the following paragraphs while the second one was described in D.1.2. The first policy instrument does not have a direct link with energy; it belongs to the policy area of “Communications-Technologies”.

²³ <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=546&language=el-GR> (available only in Greek language)

²⁴ <http://www.deddie.gr/en/upiresies/fwtovoltaika-kai-alles-ape/fv-tou-eidikou-programmatos-stegwn>

Directive 2010/40/EU²⁵ (dated 7 July 2010) “on the framework for the deployment of Intelligent Transport Systems²⁶ in the field of road transport and for interfaces with other modes of transport” set into force this planning policy instrument of the EU transport policy that concerns traffic management.

Presidential Decree No. 50 (Government Gazette 100 A, 27.04.2012²⁷) incorporated Directive 2010/40/EU into national legislation, but the document presenting the “*National Strategy for the Intelligent Transport Systems, 2015-2025*” was released by the Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism this year (March 2015) (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015). This document aims to identify shortages for the ITS, to present the relevant national needs and to define a set of principles that are required for the ITS implementation (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015). The document serves as a Roadmap for planning, implementing, operating and maintaining the ITS.

An indicative example of the use of ITS in the country is for supporting the maritime-railway interconnection. Such integration in Greece is the 17 km of railway connection between the port of Neo Ikonio (Port Authority of Piraeus) and the Thriasio area freight centre. Among the benefits of this interconnection are: elimination of congestion in ports; improved transit times; improved utilization of resources (South East Europe, 2013).

However, the implementation in Greece of the planning policy instrument for the “Intelligent Transport Systems” encounters barriers such as required investment costs, financing restrictions, uncertainty as to the payback period - ROI, failure of planning, while others are technical (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012). These obstacles are due attributed mainly to economic instability and uncertainty about demand (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012).

The “Intelligent Transport Systems” policy instrument is creating a promising positive synergy with the regulatory policy instrument of “Emission Standards (Euro 5 and Euro 6)”. The implementation of ITS will probably contribute significantly in the reduction of road transport related GHG emissions, but empirical evidence to quantify the potential is not yet sufficient (European Commission, 2009). ITS for fuel consumption and/or emissions will allow monitoring and feedback so as to influence driving style and vehicle behavior (Ministry of Infrastructure, Transportation and Networks, 2014; European Commission, 2009). On the other hand, GHG emission reductions depend on cleaner cars and cleaner fuels. A combination of new technologies, improved efficiency of highway and vehicle operations, changing the driving behaviour and cutting-edge public policy will lead to the expected EE outcomes (European Commission, 2009).

This type of policy interaction is presented in the next paragraphs.

Relation to energy efficiency

A preliminary cost-benefit analysis that was carried out for the Commission indicated a positive cost/benefit ratio for real-time traffic information in a 10-year study window (2015-2025) (European Commission, 2014). The identified benefits included: i) the accelerated provision of information about traffic management measures (implemented in case of incidents and location along the road

²⁵ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:207:0001:0013:EN:PDF>

²⁶ Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) are advanced applications that integrate telecommunications, electronics and information technologies with transport engineering in order to plan, design, operate, maintain and manage transport system. ITS provide innovative services relating to different modes of transport and traffic management and enable various users to be better informed and make safer, more coordinated and ‘smarter’ use of transport networks.

²⁷ www.yme.gr/getfile.php?id=4653

network of other real time traffic data (e.g. location of queue)), and ii) efficient routing for equipped drivers (also for areas where there is no variable message sign) iii) reduced costs for digital map providers and ITS service providers due to more / easier access to data (European Commission, 2014).

It is estimated also that road congestion leads to economic losses of approximately 1% of GDP, while more than 35.000 citizens are killed on the road per year (European Commission, 2010). Possible benefits of including traffic management measures such as the ITS (implemented in case of incidents so as to provide necessary data for real time traffic information services) could result to 167,8 million EUR whereas including road-works information would lead also to benefits of 182,6 – 219,1 million EUR (European Commission, 2014). For the Hellenic case this problem is particularly important, since for the last decade approximately 1,500 people on average are lost in road traffic accidents annually, while the estimated socio-economic cost of road accidents is more than 5 billion EUR annually (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012).

From the point of efficiency the benefits concern the public and the private sector. However, benefits for business are difficult to be quantify due to costs of poor data and poor access that are usually hidden within organisations or because benefits will result in terms of new services. The distribution of the benefits between the two sectors is difficult to be established (European Commission, 2014).

Future trends aim to the further improvement of the traffic management, the reduction of pollution and of fuel consumption and to increasing the level of road safety (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015). These trends will be supported among others with e-ticketing, navigation systems for road safety and protection, ITS for logistics and supply chain, services for sustainable mobility and systems for improved environmental and energy efficiency (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015).

The ITS implementation is expected to increase employment and create new green jobs, which are priority objectives of the broader political agenda of Greece (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012).

The second policy instrument with which the planning instrument for ITS interacts is the “Emission standards (Euro 5 and Euro 6)”. The EC Regulation No. 443/2009²⁸ “*setting emission performance standards for new passenger cars as part of the Community’s integrated approach to reduce CO₂ emissions from light-duty vehicles*” introduced common requirements for emissions from motor vehicles and their specific replacement parts (standards Euro 5 and Euro 6). It also laid down measures, allowing improved access to information on vehicle repairs and promoting the rapid production of vehicles in compliance with the provisions of the Regulation. Its combination with the “ITS” can demonstrate the outcomes of EE efforts (real-time information about fuel consumption, fuel economy, GHG emissions etc, less travelling but with clean vehicles).

Interactions between objectives

The objectives of Directive 2010/40/EC are: i) establishment of the necessary specifications to ensure the accessibility, exchange, reuse and update of road and traffic data for the provision of real-time traffic information services in the European Union (European Commission, 2014). ii) Optimal use of road, traffic and travel data continuity of traffic and freight management ITS services; ITS road safety and security applications; Linking the vehicle with the transport infrastructure. Facilitation of Traffic management is the main objective of ITS.

²⁸ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EL/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32009R0443>

According to this Directive it is expected that the ITS application²⁹ (to the road transport sector and its interfaces with other modes of transport) will contribute significantly to improved environmental performance, efficiency, including energy efficiency, safety and security of road transport, including the transport of dangerous goods, public security and passenger and freight mobility, ensuring also the functioning of the internal market and increasing the levels of competitiveness and employment. The ITS provide reduced travel time, savings by avoiding unnecessary vehicle-kilometers, reduction in fuel consumption, reduction in environmental pollution and of accidents (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015).

The purpose of the emissions standards “Euro 5 and Euro 6” is to limit the pollution caused by road vehicles and support emission reduction actions in transport by introducing stricter limits on polluting emissions. These limits are applicable to light road vehicles, particularly with regard to emissions of particles and nitrogen oxides.

The two policy instruments share common secondary objectives which are the improvement of environmental performance (reduction of polluting emissions) and of energy efficiency (support of emission reduction actions).

Interactions between target groups

The introduction and usage of ITS forms the following set of target groups: public authorities, private service providers (satellite links, internet, dedicated cable networks etc), road operators, private companies that develop and purchase the necessary equipment (traffic cameras, loop detectors), companies that own, elaborate and provide data and end-users (travelers, all categories of drivers (professional drivers, taxi drivers, drivers in public vehicles, elderly people etc) (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015; European Commission, 2014; TISA, 2014).

Under the emissions standards the target groups are: i) vehicle manufacturers and ii) owners of vehicles (categories³⁰ M1, M2, N1 and N2, with reference mass not exceeding 2.610 kg³¹). These vehicles include, among others, passenger vehicles, vans and commercial vehicles intended for the carriage of passengers or goods or certain other specific uses (for example ambulances), provided that the vehicles are equipped with engine-spark ignition (gasoline engines, engines with natural gas or Liquefied Petroleum Gas - LPG) or compression ignition (diesel engines).

In order to limit as much as possible the negative impact of road vehicles on the environment and health, the Regulation (for Euro 5 and Euro 6) covers a wide range of pollutant emissions: carbon monoxide (CO), non-methane hydrocarbons and total hydrocarbons, oxides of nitrogen (NO_x) and particulates (PM). These include emissions of tailpipe, evaporative emissions and crankcase emissions.

The end-users (drivers of all vehicle types, private and public) are the common subset of the two target groups that benefit from the implementation of both policy instruments. Owners of vehicles with technology of Euro 5 and 6 when using ITS save travel time, consume less fuel and emit less.

Interactions between rules - influencing mechanisms

The Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (MEIST) (former Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks) supports centrally the

²⁹ ITS applications should be without prejudice to matters concerning national security or necessary in the interest of defense.

³⁰ <http://www.dft.gov.uk/vca/vehicletype/definition-of-vehicle-categories.asp>

³¹ defined in Annex II to Directive 70/156/EEC

availability of real-time traffic data which are accessible by the private sector for a fee (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012).

There are emission limits for each category of pollutant emissions and for the different types of vehicle. According to provisions of EC Regulation 715/2007, the Member States shall lay down the provisions on penalties “applicable for infringement by manufacturers” according to their obligations under the Regulation. The respective penalties must be effective, proportionate and dissuasive.

Offences subject to a penalty include: a) making false declarations during the approval procedures or procedures leading to a recall; b) falsifying test results for type approval or in-service conformity; c) withholding data or technical specifications which could lead to recall or withdrawal of type approval; d) use of defeat devices; and e) refusal to provide access to information.

There is no policy interaction under this category.

Interactions between implementation network/ governance structures

The same authority is responsible for the implementation of both policy instruments, ie the Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism.

For the planning policy instrument of ITS, the pertinent national authority will be the Department of Planning and Development of Transport that is under the General Directorate of Transport of the Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015). This Department is assigned with the following responsibilities (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015):

- Implementation of the “National Strategy and Architecture for the ITS”. It is also responsible for the update and specialization of this strategy when these are required;
- Installation of the implementation rules presented in national and European regulation documents for ITS;
- Monitoring of the progress for implementing the actions that derive from the national and European regulation documents for ITS
- Operation of the Advisory Committee for ITS and of the ITS Observatory;
- Supervision of the registries with data required by the national and European regulation documents for ITS.

The Advisory Committee for ITS provides periodically or whenever that is necessary, consulting services to the Department of Planning and Development of Transport (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015).

The ITS Observatory records the ITS actions, evaluates them through appropriate indexes, the implementation outcomes and the ITS performance so as to draw objective conclusions for the progress of their implementation in Greece and the level of coordinated penetration of the ITS applications. The ITS observatory is under the supervision of the Department of Planning and Development of Transport (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015).

The Institute for the Management of Information Systems "Athena" has developed and maintains the website www.geodata.gov.gr, so as to provide national support through a central point for collection, search, distribution and visualisation of information, e.g. bus routes (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012).

However, there is an overlap by entities such as Municipalities, OASA³² and the Egnatia Motorway in the performance of necessary actions (ie for implementing an integrated combined public information system for traffic, parking places and routes; informing public transport passengers etc) (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012). Defined roles and responsibilities for planning and coordination of such actions are not allocated clearly across the various levels of government (central government, local government) and transport operators (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012).

Other obstacles for the ITS implementation in the country are: i) Insufficient collaboration between public (central and regional) authorities and private entities; ii) lack of information for transport operators about the ITS and how they could implement them successfully, producing benefits for enterprises (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012).

For the second policy instrument the Directorate “Vehicles Technology” of the MEIST is responsible for these issues. However, there are no available information about the implementation.

The policy interaction can be positive if the aforementioned obstacles are confronted.

³² See Deliverable 1.1 for more information

REFERENCES

Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013. Build Up Skills – Greece, Analysis of the current situation at national level. Available at: [http://www.buildupskills.eu/sites/default/files/BUILD%20UP%20Skills-Greece_Status%20quo%20\(EL\)_0.pdf](http://www.buildupskills.eu/sites/default/files/BUILD%20UP%20Skills-Greece_Status%20quo%20(EL)_0.pdf) (Available only in Greek language) (Accessed: August 2015).

Buy Smart+Pilot project – Municipality of Pilea-Hortiatis, 2014. Available at: <http://www.buy-smart.info/good-practice-examples/pilot-projects/public-sector13/artikel1112> (Accessed: August 2015).

Buy Smart+Pilot project – Technological Educational Institute of Thessaly (Larisa), 2014. Available at: <http://www.buy-smart.info/good-practice-examples/pilot-projects/public-sector13/artikel1112> (Accessed: August 2015).

Buy Smart+Pilot project – Municipality of Kalamaria, 2014. Available at: <http://www.buy-smart.info/good-practice-examples/pilot-projects/public-sector13/artikel1112> (Accessed: August 2015).

Buy Smart+Pilot project – Ministry of Health, 2014. Available at: <http://www.buy-smart.info/good-practice-examples/vehicles2/public-sector7/public-sector11> (Accessed: August 2015).

Centre for European Policy Studies and the College of Europe, 2012. The uptake of Green Public Procurement in the EU27. Submitted to the European Commission – DG Environment. Authors: Andrea Renda, Jacques Pelkmans, Christian Egenhofer, Lorna Schrefler, Giacomo Luchetta, Can Selçuki (CEPS), Jesus Ballesteros, Anne-Claire Zirnhelt. Available at: <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/pdf/CEPS-CoE-GPP%20MAIN%20REPORT.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015).

Christidou Chrysanthi, Tsagarakis Konstantinos P., Athanasiou Costas, 2014. Resource management in organized housing settlements, a case study at Kastoria Region, Greece. *Energy and Buildings* 74, pp. 17–29.

Domingues Ana Rita, Pires Sara Moreno, Caeiro Sandra, Ramos Tomas B., 2015. Defining criteria and indicators for a sustainability label of local public services. *Ecological Indicators* 57, pp. 452-464.

European Commission, 2009. The potential of Intelligent Transport Systems for reducing road transport related greenhouse gas emissions. Special study No. 2/2009. A Sectoral e-Business Watch study by SE Consult. Principal authors: Jian Bani, Vicente Lopez, Paloma Dapena. Madrid/Brussels. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/archives/e-business-watch/studies/special_topics/2009/documents/SR02-2009 ITS.pdf (Accessed: August 2015)

European Commission, 2010. Framework for the Deployment of Intelligent Transport Systems – Directive 2010/40/EU. Presentation of the Directorate –General for Mobility and Transport. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/its/road/doc/2010_09_15_its_directive_2010-40-eu-standard.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

European Commission, 2014. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No.../.. of 18.12.2014. supplementing Directive 2010/40/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to the provision of EU-wide real-time traffic information services (Text with EEA relevance). Available at: [http://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/its/news/doc/2014-12-18-rtti/c\(2014\)9672_en.pdf](http://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/its/news/doc/2014-12-18-rtti/c(2014)9672_en.pdf) (Accessed: August 2015).

European Commission, 2015. Commission Staff Working Document - Evaluation of the Energy Labelling and Ecodesign Directives Accompanying the document Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on the review of Directive 2010/30/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the indication of labelling and standard product information of the consumption of energy and other resources by energy-related products - COM(2015) 345 final. Brussels, 15.7.2015 SWD(2015) 143 final. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/1_EN_autre_document_travail_service_part1_v2.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

European Photovoltaics Industry Association, 2014. Global Market Outlook for Photovoltaics 2014–2018. Available at: http://helapco.gr/wp-content/uploads/EPIA_Global_Market_Outlook_for_Photovoltaics_2014-2018_Medium_Res.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

European Solar Thermal Industry Federation, 2015. Solar Thermal Markets in Europe – Trends and market Statistics 2014. Available at: http://www.estif.org/fileadmin/estif/content/market_data/downloads/2014_solar_thermal_markets_LR.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

European Solar Thermal Industry Federation, 2013. Solar Thermal Markets in Europe – Trends and market Statistics 2012. Available at: http://www.estif.org/fileadmin/estif/content/market_data/downloads/Solar_Thermal_Markets%202012.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

First Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2008. Pursuant to Directive 2006/32/EC. Prepared by the Ministry of Development and the Centre for Renewable Energy Sources in Athens, June 2008 (Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficiency-directive/national-energy-efficiency-action-plans> & http://uest.ntua.gr/archive/eupalinus/Sxedio_Drasis_Elladas_gia_EA_2006_32.pdf). Accessed on July 2015.

HELAPCO, 2013. Report about the PV installations of the Specific Program for the development of PV systems on roofs – May 2013. Available at: http://helapco.gr/pdf/Report_PV_Rooftop_100513.pdf (Available only on Greek language)(Accessed: August 2015).

Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015. National Strategy for the Intelligent Transport Systems, 2015-2025. Available at: <http://www.yme.gr/?tid=1660> (Available only in Greek language)(Accessed: August 2015).

Hellenic Republic, Hellenic Statistical Authority, 2013. Press Release – Survey on energy consumption in households 2011-2012. Available at: http://www.statistics.gr/portal/page/portal/ESYE/BUCKET/A0805/PressReleases/A0805_SFA40_DT_5Y_00_2012_01_F_EN.pdf (Accessed: August 2015)

IEA, 2014b. Trends 2014 in Photovoltaic Applications. Available at: http://helapco.gr/pdf/IEA_PVPS_Trends_2014_in_PV_Applications_-_lr.pdf, ISBN 978-3-906042-25-1 (Accessed: August 2015).

IEA, 2014a. Capturing the multiple benefits of energy efficiency. Available at: <https://www.iea.org/Textbase/npsum/MultipleBenefits2014SUM.pdf> (Accessed: May 2015)

Martinopoulos Georgios, Tsalikis Georgios, 2014. Active solar heating systems for energy efficient buildings in Greece: A technical economic and environmental evaluation. Energy and Buildings 68, pp. 130-137.

Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012. ITS Action Plan – The Action Plan for Intelligent Transport Systems in Greece. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/its/road/action_plan/doc/2012-greece-its-action-plan-2012-final_en.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

Ministry of Infrastructure, Transportation and Networks, 2014. Plan for the national strategy on ITS, October 2014. Available at: <https://www.dikaiologitika.gr/images/pdf/sxedio-esm.pdf> (Available in Greek language)(Accessed: August 2015).

South East Europe, 2013. Intelligent Transport Systems in South East Europe – D.4.2.1 - Study for adopting EU ITS Action Plan main areas in Greece. Available at: http://www.seeits.eu/docs/Publications/Deliverables/new/SEEITS_D4.2.1_Study_for_adopting_EU_ITS_Action_Plan_main_areas_in_Greece.pdf (Accessed: July 2015)

Traveller Information Services Association (TISA), 2014. Terms and Definitions – Terms and Definitions for the Traffic and Travel Information Value Chain. Available at: <http://www.tisa.org/assets/Uploads/Public/EO12013TISADefinition-ITS-value-chain20121018.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015).

Tsalikis Georgios, Martinopoulos Georgios, 2015. Solar energy systems potential for nearly net zero energy residential buildings, *Solar Energy* 115 , pp. 743–756

YPEKA, 2014, Long Term Strategy report for the mobilization of investments for the renovation of consisting of residential and commercial buildings, public and private, national building stock. (*Article 4, Directive 27/2012/EU*), Athens. Available at: <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=vDjk62bRxSI%3d&tabid=282&language=el-GR> (Available in Greek language)(Accessed: July 2015).

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.3

INTERLINKAGE AND SYNERGIES BETWEEN SELECTED OTHER POLICY AREAS AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY

D.1.3

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT**

NATIONAL REPORT FOR ITALY

DATE

Partner: “Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi”

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Universiteit
Antwerpen

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi

Steering Committee member ⁽¹⁾: Edoardo Croci

Prepared by: Edoardo Croci, Benedetta Lucchitta, Tania Molteni, Alessandro Palma, Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi - UB - IEFE.

(1) The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors’ views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	4
GLOSSARY	5
ACRONYMS	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS	9
1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY	10
1.1.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR	10
1.1.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR	16
1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY	23
1.2.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR	23
1.2.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR	27
ANNEXES	36
REFERENCES	37

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Road fuel prices and taxes^a	17
Figure 2: Italy – Consumption of petroleum products (Millions of tons)	18
Figure 3: Petrol and diesel: rise of taxation, fall of consumption	18
Figure 4: Historical trend of average daily emissions from road traffic in the Ecopass Area	29
Figure 5: CO₂ average daily emissions during daytime (ton/day) (left graph)	30
Figure 6: Average CO₂ emission factor	31
Figure 7: Carbon dioxide due to circulating vehicles in Milan (divided according to zones)	31

Table of Tables

Table 1: FCS financial endowment and recipient companies by size	25
---	-----------

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

GLOSSARY

ACRONYMS

AMAT: Agenzia Mobilità Ambiente Territorio (Agency for Mobility Environment Territory).

ATM: Azienda Trasporti Milanesi.

CNG: Compressed Natural Gas.

CoM: Covenant of Mayors.

D.I.: Decreto Interministeriale (Inter-ministerial Decree).

D.L.: Decreto Legge (Law Decree).

Dlgs: Decreto Legislativo (Legislative Decree).

D.M.: Decreto Ministeriale (Ministerial Decree).

D.P.R.: Decreto del Presidente della Repubblica (Decree of the President of the Republic).

EEA: European Energy Agency.

EIB: European Investment Bank.

ESCO: Energy Service Company.

EU: European Union.

EU-ETS: EU- Emissions Trading System.

FCS: Fondo per la Crescita Sostenibile (National Fund for Sustainable Growth).

FIT: Fondo Rotativo per l'Innovazione Tecnologica (Fund for Technological Innovation).

GDP: Gross Domestic Product.

GSE: Gestore dei Servizi Energetici.

JRC: Joint Research Centre of the European Commission.

L.: National Law.

LPG: Liquefied Petroleum Gas.

MATTM: Italian Ministry for the Environment and the Protection of Land and Sea.

MISE: Italian Ministry of Economic Development.

MIT: Italian Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport.

NGO: Non-Governmental Organization.

OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.

ON-RE: Osservatorio Nazionale Regolamenti Edilizi per il Risparmio Energetico (National Observatory on Building Regulations for Energy Saving).

PATRES: Public Administration Training and Coaching on Renewable Energy Systems (EU-project).

POE: National Operational Plan for Research and Competitiveness.

PUMS: Piano Urbano della Mobilità Sostenibile (Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan).

SEAP: Sustainable Energy Action Plan.

SME: Small and Medium-sized Enterprise.

TEE: Titoli di Efficienza Energetica (Energy Efficiency Titles, other name for the White Certificates issued within the related system).

TEP: tonnellata equivalente di petrolio (tonnes of equivalent oil).

TOE: tonnes of equivalent oil.

ZTL: Zona Traffico Limitato (Limited Traffic Zone).

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Several policy instruments, not targeting specifically energy efficiency or not prioritizing it, may have the potential to deliver energy efficiency benefits. The following report analyses the energy efficiency implications of a set of policy instruments currently in force in Italy, ranging from the national to the local level. Four cases are analysed, two for the buildings sector and two for the transport one. For each sector, a policy instrument with a “direct” link to energy and one with an “indirect” link to energy are considered.

For each case, the report describes the main features of the policy instrument and its relation to energy efficiency. Subsequently, each policy instrument is put in relation with another instrument specifically targeted to energy efficiency and/or CO₂ reduction, in order to analyse their interactions along a series of aspects: objectives, target groups, rules-influencing mechanisms, implementation network / governance structures.

Specifically, with respect to the **direct link to energy** the following cases are examined:

Buildings: Municipal building regulations. These instruments are used to regulate several aspects of building construction/renovation practices in a municipality, including comfort and aesthetic aspects. By setting innovative standards and requirements, they can contribute to boost energy efficiency and to enhance building quality in new constructions and renovations.

Transport: Excise tax on petrol and diesel. The excise is a purpose tax applied to achieve certain goals and to finance interventions to cope with natural and other events. Combined with the effects of economic crisis, high levels of taxation on petrol/diesel in Italy have affected fuel consumption, as evidenced by the related consumption trends.

For the **indirect link to energy**, the following cases are examined:

Buildings: National Fund for Sustainable Growth (FIT/FCS).

This instrument envisages financial support to research areas related to ‘sustainable industrial activities’ and provides effective support to the technology deployment. In the present report, the case of ‘white goods’ for households are considered. Although energy efficiency is not explicitly mentioned as a final objective of this fund, it contributes to support firms in efficiently conducting research and generating new technical change to be embodied in new appliances, that can have a relevant impact on energy use.

Transport: Urban road pricing policy. For the city of Milan, urban road pricing is a policy instrument mainly thought to address the relevant traffic, congestion and air pollution problems affecting the city. However, the reduction of traffic and of motorized vehicle travel, together with the impulse to vehicle stock renewal, have enabled a reduction in CO₂ emissions from traffic in the city centre.

The analysis provides, where available, quantitative data on the energy efficiency/energy saving effect obtained in the four cases.

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS

In current debates the multiple benefits of energy efficiency are broadly discussed and available analyses are growing in number (e.g. IEA 2014 report on multiple benefits). However, in some cases energy savings can rather be seen as the co-benefit of other policies or measures, which do not target energy efficiency by original design.

The aim of this task is to identify policy areas suitable for combination with energy efficiency policies and systematically analyse how they may contribute to improve energy efficiency, particularly if untapped energy saving potentials still exist.

For **Italy**, the report describes the following four cases:

(1) policy instruments with a direct link to energy:

- a. for the buildings sector, the case of Municipal building regulations;
- b. for the transport sector, the case of the excise tax on petrol and diesel.

(2) 2 policy instruments with an indirect link to energy:

- a. for the buildings sector, the case of the National Fund for Sustainable Growth;
- b. for the transport sector, the case of the Ecopass/Area C urban road pricing policy of the City of Milan.

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.1.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

Introduction

Please provide information about the following issues:

- Full name of the energy policy instrument that may contribute to improve energy efficiency

Municipal building regulations (“Regolamento edilizio comunale”)

Municipal building regulations are instruments through which each Italian municipality regulates the construction modes within its territory, “with particular attention to the respect of the technical-aesthetic norms, hygienic-sanitary norms, safety and liveability of buildings and their appurtenances” (art. 4, D.P.R. 6 June 2001, n. 380). Regions contribute to the elaboration of municipal buildings regulations mainly in two ways: they either set a template of building regulations for the municipalities of their territories, or they provide criteria or orientation guidelines to elaborate them (Zara, 2007).

Building regulations have a direct link to energy, as far as both energy efficiency and renewable energy aspects are concerned. Since they address technical and procedural aspects of the building construction and renovation process, they can specify requirements for high-energy efficiency and environmental performances, as well as for the use and production of renewable energy, contributing to promote energy efficiency in the building sector. They can act through mandatory requirements, as well as through voluntary requirements, supported by incentives¹.

According to Zara (2007), the main topics where the link between building regulations and energy can be seen are: installation of solar thermal and photovoltaic panels; renovation of window fixtures; external insulation; excavations for external heat pumps; substitution/installation of heating systems; building orientation.

The National Observatory on Building Regulations for Energy Saving (ON-RE “Osservatorio Nazionale Regolamenti Edilizi per il Risparmio Energetico”) maps since 2008 the Italian municipal building regulations that include innovations regarding energy and environment-related aspects, going beyond national and regional laws in force. The 2013 ON-RE report (Cresme, Legambiente, 2013) identified 1.003 energy and environmentally innovative building regulations, which correspond to 12,4% of total Italian municipalities and a population over 21 million inhabitants (one third of the Italian population). Over time, the number of innovative regulations has increased significantly (188 in 2008, 705 in 2010 and 855 in 2011) (*ibid*).

A recent law² foresees that the Government, Regions and autonomous local authorities find an agreement to adopt a national template of municipal building regulations, with the aim to simplify and level out the norms. The template will define the performance requirements of buildings, regarding in particular safety and energy saving.

¹ Cresme and Legambiente (2013) identify three main typologies of incentives promoting energy efficiency and environmental quality in municipal building regulations: fiscal, economic and urban planning incentives.

² L. 11 November 2014, n. 164 “Conversione in legge, con modificazioni, del decreto-legge 12 settembre 2014, n. 133, recante misure urgenti per l'apertura dei cantieri, la realizzazione delle opere pubbliche, la digitalizzazione del Paese, la semplificazione burocratica, l'emergenza del dissesto idrogeologico e per la ripresa delle attività produttive”.

- **Specific focus of the policy instrument and target group**

The focus of the instrument are buildings (residential, commercial, tertiary). They can also address interventions on public spaces (e.g. public gardens...).

Its target groups are the public administration itself, all the actors involved in the building design and construction sectors, as well as buildings owners and more in general citizens.

- **Objective of the policy instrument**

The objective of building regulations is to set the rules for the construction modes within a municipality, as far as technical-aesthetic norms, hygienic-sanitary norms, safety and liveability of buildings and their appurtenances are concerned.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Please provide information about the following issues:

- **Are there already impacts on energy efficiency due to the policy instrument? Are the impacts positive or negative?**

The ONRE report (Cresme, Legambiente, 2013) has mapped more than a thousand municipal building regulations in Italy that include innovative requirements and prescriptions in terms of environmental and energy performances of buildings. A comprehensive estimation of all the impacts already achieved by these innovations is not available yet. An idea of impacts can be gathered from projects such as the EU-Funded PATRES³, which has promoted in Italy and other 6 EU countries the elaboration or the updating of codes and regulations for new buildings or buildings renovation with a specific attention to sustainable energy. The project implemented a wide range of training, technical assistance and coaching activities for local authorities, public utilities and social housing bodies. In addition, the PATRES project identified best practices of building regulations that promote energy efficiency and renewable energy and have already achieved impacts⁴.

- **What are existing barriers / reasons for not considering energy efficiency so far by the policy or measure?**

As shown above, energy efficiency is considered in several municipal buildings regulations, and 12,4% of Italian municipalities adopt an innovative approach on the topic (Cresme, Legambiente, 2013). However, the scale of the targets on CO₂ emission reduction, energy efficiency and energy performances of buildings at European and national level would require a wider diffusion of innovative approaches throughout Italian municipalities. According to several stakeholders, providing a national template of municipal building regulations - as it is currently being discussed (see note 2

³ PATRES – Public Administration Training and Coaching on Renewable Energy Systems, <http://www.patres.net/>, funded by the European Commission through the IEE – Intelligent Energy Europe Programme, involved 7 countries (Austria, Croatia, Estonia, Italy, The Czech Republic, Romania, Spain).

⁴ Among these, the municipality of Carugate (14.396 inhabitants), in the province of Milan, adopted innovative building regulations in 2003, which in the following years obtained impacts on renewable energy production. See at: <http://www.patres.net/ita/best-practice.aspx>

above) - could promote energy and environmental innovation in the building sector at local level, identifying shared procedures for buildings energy renovation and simplifying bureaucracy⁵.

The national template would also help overcoming the issue of the multiple buildings regulations, which currently causes a high complexity and fragmentation of rules and norms across regions and municipalities and has been recognized as a key barrier to energy efficiency in the building sector.

- Are revisions / additional measures necessary in order to address energy efficiency improvements? How big could potential benefits be?

As stated in the previous point, the elaboration and provision to municipalities of a reference document such as the national template for building regulations would help overcoming barriers to a wider integration of energy efficiency into these instruments.

Estimates on the potential benefits are not available.

- Which actors would benefit from a full consideration of energy efficiency?

A further consideration of energy efficiency could benefit installers of energy efficiency systems/buildings renovation companies; and building owners, that would benefit from the quality and increased energy efficiency performances of buildings.

Interaction between objectives

Two policy instruments interact when they have common primary or secondary objectives. *Please provide information for the selected policy instrument and the energy efficiency policy instrument(s) showing interlinkages and synergies on the following issues:*

- Which common objectives expressed either quantitatively or qualitatively are given?

A policy instrument targeting specifically energy efficiency and interacting with the municipal buildings regulations are the Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs) elaborated by municipalities within the Covenant of Mayors (CoM). The CoM initiative was launched in 2008 by the European Commission to support local authorities in Europe to reach and go beyond the 20-20-20 targets on CO₂ emission reduction, energy saving and renewable energy in their territories. CoM signatories commit to adopt a SEAP, which identifies and describes the set of actions selected by the Local Government to reach the CO₂ reduction and energy targets at territorial level. According to JRC data (2015), by mid-May 2014 CoM signatories were 5.132 representing 160 million inhabitants, of which 2.731 signatories were from Italy representing 33 million inhabitants (counting for 52% of total signatories and 18% of total CoM population).

The objectives of SEAPs are to reduce CO₂ emissions in a specific local context, to promote energy saving and energy efficiency, as well as the use and production of energy from renewable sources. CoM signatories are requested to adopt in their SEAPs a commitment of reducing current emissions by at least 20%, however several signatories adopt more demanding targets⁶. The buildings sector, together with transport, is the main field of action of SEAPs actions.

⁵ <http://www.legambiente.it/contenuti/comunicati/innovazione-e-semplificazione-edilizia-verso-il-regolamento-nazionale-0>

⁶ In the sample of cities analysed by JRC (2015), the overall estimated reduction was of more than 28%.

The general objectives of a municipal buildings regulation have been described above. Sustainable building regulations explicitly aim to promote the quality of the urban environment, identify design parameters that boost building quality, orientate design and building practice consistently with environmental protection and they usually have a specific annex dedicated to sustainable and efficient energy use (Curcuruto, 2012). Therefore a sustainable building regulation is totally consistent with the SEAP objectives and can contribute to the achievement of its targets. The text of the Covenant of Mayors itself⁷ recalls the interlinkage between the regulatory role of local governments regarding energy performance and renewable energy in buildings - which for Italy is implemented through the building regulations - and the objectives of the Covenant.

- Which impacts on objectives due to the parallel implementation of the policy instruments based on official comments or data can be regarded?

Several municipalities are currently implementing a SEAP in parallel with innovative building regulations integrating energy aspects, however detailed data on SEAP implementation are not available yet. Many municipalities are undertaking SEAP monitoring activities and part of them have already concluded these activities. As soon as detailed monitoring reports will become available on the CoM website, they will provide useful insights on the implementation of these policy instruments.

Interaction between target groups

Two policy instruments may be imposed on the same target groups or on specific sub-sets. In order to get a feeling on the extent of interaction, *please provide information for the selected policy instrument and the energy efficiency policy instrument(s) showing interlinkages and synergies on the following issue:*

- Do common target groups exist, and if yes, which are these target groups?

Target groups of a SEAP depend on the sectors targeted and by the actions included in the plan. In general terms, a SEAP can target all public and private actors of a specific local context. JRC (2010) provides a list of stakeholders that could be important for a SEAP:

- local administration: relevant municipal departments and companies (municipal energy utilities, transport companies, etc.);
- local and regional energy agencies;
- financial partners such as banks, private funds, ESCOs;
- institutional stakeholders like chambers of commerce, chambers of architects and engineers;
- energy suppliers, utilities;
- transport/mobility players: private/public transport companies, etc.;
- the building sector: building companies, developers;
- business and industries;
- supporting Structures and energy agencies;
- NGOs and other civil society representatives;

⁷http://www.eumayors.eu/IMG/pdf/covenantofmayors_text_en.pdf

- representatives of the civil society, including students, workers etc.;
- existing structures (Agenda 21, ...);
- universities;
- knowledgeable persons (consultants, ...);
- where relevant, representatives of national/regional administrations and/or neighbouring municipalities, to ensure coordination and consistency with plans and actions that take place at other levels of decision;
- tourists, whereby the tourist industry represents a large share of the emissions.

Almost all these target groups are also targeted by municipal building regulations, either for their economic activity (e.g. building companies, developers) or since they own buildings that are subject to these regulations.

Therefore there is a clear overlap between the target groups of the two policy instruments.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

Two policy instruments may interact due to tradeable permits / certificates or due to regulations. Please provide information for the selected policy instrument and the energy efficiency policy instrument(s) showing interlinkages and synergies on the following issues:

- Which market trading commodities (White Certificates, ERUs, etc.) interact with the selected policy instrument? The specific type of interaction is recognized when two policy instruments have rules for the same trading commodity, i.e. emission permits or green certificates. Therefore, the question to be answered is, does the interacting policy instruments affect the relevant market or not?

A market trading commodity interacting with municipal building regulations and SEAPs are the white certificates (also named "Titoli di Efficienza Energetica" - TEE)⁸, since there are several interventions on residential and tertiary buildings that are eligible to obtain them (e.g. interventions related to heating/cooling and water heating; small electricity production systems and cogeneration; interventions on the building envelope to reduce energy needs for heating/cooling or lighting...)⁹.

Building regulations influence the technical features of interventions that can be realized on buildings located in a specific territory, therefore they are part of the regulatory framework that must be taken into account when designing an intervention that could apply for white certificates.

SEAPs usually include several actions to reduce CO₂ emissions from energy use in buildings. Among these, some actions could generate white certificates and others could be supporting measures for

⁸ The White Certificates system was introduced in the Italian legislation by D.M. 20 July 2004 and subsequent amendments. It foresees that electricity and natural gas distributors reach annually specific quantitative goals of primary energy savings, expressed in tonnes of equivalent oil saved (TOE). A certificate is equivalent to saving 1 ton of oil equivalent (TOE). Electricity and natural gas distributors may fulfil their obligations by implementing energy efficiency projects entitle to obtain white certificates, or by buying white certificates from other parties in the Energy Efficiency Certificates Market organised by GME (Gestore dei Mercati Energetici). Projects can regard industrial processes, the residential/agricultural/tertiary sectors, public and private lighting, transport systems, efficiency in electricity/gas networks. Projects must meet a certain energy saving threshold to be eligible for applying to deliver white certificates.

⁹ See the technical information sheets of projects eligible for white certificates published by GSE – Gestore dei Servizi Energetici:

<http://www.gse.it/it/CertificatiBianchi/Modalit%C3%A0%20di%20realizzazione%20dei%20progetti/Schede%20tecniche/Pagine/default.aspx>

stakeholders to reduce energy use in buildings that could also generate certificates (e.g. supporting help-desks for companies and citizens willing to renovate their properties...).

It should be noted that projects applying for white certificates must meet a certain energy saving threshold to be eligible¹⁰, therefore some projects aggregate a certain amount of small interventions, under the management of a specific subject (e.g. ESCo).

The impact of the interaction between the two policy instruments on the market of white certificates has not been assessed. However, white certificates are combinable with other incentives for energy efficiency interventions recognized at regional and local level¹¹. Therefore it could be argued that innovative buildings regulations and SEAPs could jointly stimulate the realization of technical interventions on buildings that could generate white certificates.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

The same pertinent authorities may be responsible for the implementation of two policy instruments with the same set of responsibilities or with properly distributed – and not overlapping – responsibilities. *Please provide information on the performance of the policy instruments under the respective criteria / sub-criteria of the evaluation method AMS, i.e. (see Konidari et al. 2014)*

- capacity of the implementation network (ability of all national competent parties to design, support and ensure the implementation of the policy instruments)

The implementation network of both policy instruments is at municipal level. The implementation of municipal building regulations is usually upon a specific department of the local authority. The implementation of the SEAP can entail action from several departments, depending on the typologies of actions included in the plan. Since the implementation of building regulations can contribute to reach the SEAP objectives, it can be argued that there is a direct collaboration and synergy between the activities of departments involved in the two policy instruments.

- administrative burden (aggregate work exerted by the regulatory implementation network during the enforcement of the policy instruments)

Given the interactions between the two instruments described above, the aggregate work for their implementation can be optimized by the collaboration and synergies between the departments involved.

- financial feasibility (property of the policy instrument to be implemented with low overall costs by the pertinent regulatory authorities)

As soon as detailed monitoring reports on SEAPs implementation will become available on the CoM website, they will provide useful insights also on implementation costs and financial feasibility aspects.

¹⁰ Depending on the typology of project (“standardized”: 20 tep/year; “analytical”: 40 tep/year; “consumptive” projects: 60 tep/year).

¹¹ See: <http://www.gse.it/it/EnergiaFacile/faq/CertificatiBianchi/Pagine/default.aspx>: “Cumulabilità”.

1.1.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

Introduction

Please provide information about the following issues:

- Full name of the energy policy instrument that may contribute to improve energy efficiency

Excise tax on petrol and diesel

- Specific focus of the policy instrument and target group

The excise is an indirect tax that affects certain productions. It involves the individual production and individual consumption. It is indirect because the producer pays the tribute which subsequently falls upon the consumer. In Italy the most important excises are those relating to energy products, electricity, alcohol and tobacco.

- Objective of the policy instrument

The excise duties in Italy are regulated by the legislative decree n. 504/1995 (Dlgs. 26 October 1995, n. 504: “*Testo Unico delle disposizioni legislative concernenti le imposte sulla produzione e sui consumi e le relativi sanzioni penali e amministrative*”). The second chapter defines how the fuel price is composed: i) the excise tax; ii) a regional tax ; iii) the value added tax (Dlgs. n. 504/1995).

The excise is a *purpose tax* that is applied to achieve certain goals and it was introduced to finance interventions to cope with natural and other events.

However, with regard to energy taxation, the definition of the structure and the amount of tax on mineral oils have been influenced by other factors. These factors are: *transport policy* (competition between different types of transport or the transparent distribution of infrastructure costs), *environmental policy* (less pollution, eg. by establishing minimum levels of excise duties for different gasoline and unleaded), the overall *energy policy* (balance between different energy sources, such as coal, oil, natural gas, nuclear power, etc., and between local energy sources and imported,) *agricultural policy* (eg. the proposal, withdrawn in 1999 on reduced rate of excise duty on biofuels), and finally the *employment policy* (fiscal strategy to encourage a switch from the taxation of labour to that of other sources of revenue, including taxing the use of raw materials and energy) (Kolassa, 2014).

The rates of excise duties on energy products mentioned with effect from 1 January 2015 are set forth with determination of the Director of the Customs Agency n. RU 88789 of 9 August 2012 and confirmed by art. 1, paragraph 487, L. 24 December 2012, n. 228..

Specifically, on the basis of the mentioned legal sources, from 1 January 2015 the rates of excise duty on petrol and leaded petrol and gas oil used as fuel are applied as follows:

- Petrol and leaded petrol: 728,40 €/1000 l;
- Diesel used as fuel: 617.40 €/1000 l (Agenzia delle Dogane, 2015).

**Figure 1: Road fuel prices and taxes^a
1995-2011**

a) At constant 2005 prices.
b) Unleaded premium (95 RON).
Source: OECD-IEA (2012), *Energy Prices and Taxes*.

Source: OECD-IEA, 2012.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Please provide information about the following issues:

- Are there already impacts on energy efficiency due to the policy instrument? Are the impacts positive or negative?

In Italy oil products are subjected to high taxation and the demand for fuel consumption is considered inelastic (Graham and Glaister, 2002), so the excise duties are an instrument to ensure certain revenue for the state and were increased during the years with no evident consequences on the consumes. In Italy since 2005 the excise affected the use of fuel, also with the emergence of the first signs of the economic crisis. This phenomenon has increased over the years, generating a significant decline in consumption: the growth of the excise corresponded to a decline in fuel consumption (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Italy – Consumption of petroleum products (Millions of tons)

Source: Unione Petrolifera, 2015

The phenomena described are represented in the graph below, which shows the trend in consumption of petrol and diesel against the trend registered by its withdrawal. At a 54% increase in the level of taxation, consumption reported a decrease of 21% (FAIB Confesercenti, 2013).

Figure 3: Petrol and diesel: rise of taxation, fall of consumption

(Consumption of petrol and diesel (blue line); Tax/liter petrol and diesel (pink line))

Source: FAIB Confesercenti, MISE data elaboration, 2013

- What are existing barriers / reasons for not considering energy efficiency so far by the policy or measure?

In Italy in 2008, the excise tax on gasoline (0.562 euro per litre) implied a carbon price of 247 €/t, while that on diesel (0.421 euro per liter) a rate of 161 €/t (Cingano, Faiella, 2013). These values are higher than the prices of the EU ETS and than the external costs of climate change (Lombard et al., 2005). We may conclude that the taxation of greenhouse gas emissions implied in excise duties is therefore already very high (Cingano, Faiella, 2013). Revenue from environmentally related taxes, even if only a limited share of it has been used for environmental purposes, accounted for 2.6% of GDP and 6.1% of total tax receipts in 2010, higher than the corresponding shares for the OECD as a whole (OECD, 2013). However, their role declined during the last decade, and the real tax burden on energy decreased. Nevertheless, the tax burden on energy, and the tax rates on petrol and diesel, are among the highest in Europe. From an environmental point of view, there is scope to restructure these taxes to better capture environmental externalities.

These estimates, however, consider the excise tax on fuel as well as Pigouvian taxes intended for correction of externalities related to CO₂ emissions (Cingano, Faiella, 2013). Instead only a small part of the external costs generated by transport is environmental, in fact the main component related to traffic congestion and the costs arising from accidents is not covered by insurance (Cingano, Faiella, 2013). Taking into account these additional costs, the implicit price of CO₂ emissions is reduced and can become negative. These considerations suggest that, despite the high level of taxation on energy products, there is room to draw a policy to reduce emissions of the transport sector that will integrate measures for energy efficiency and the spread of biofuels, using the taxation (OECD, 2013).

For example, excise duties vary greatly among fuels and users and do not provide a consistent price for carbon. The excise duty on diesel was still 23% below that on petrol in 2011, a difference that is not environmentally justified (OECD 2013). Vehicle taxes do not take full account of CO₂ and other emissions, especially for freight vehicles. Several partial or total exemptions apply to different uses of fuel, which lower end-use prices and reduce incentives to use energy efficiently. For example, such exemptions apply to fuels used for electricity generation, in agriculture, in industrial facilities, and for road freight transport. Special tax provisions on energy and transport were estimated to result in revenue losses of 0.2% of GDP in 2010 (OECD, 2013).

There are duties on all fuels used for both stationary purposes (such as heating and industrial processes) and transport. The revenue from taxes on transport fuels is dominant. Excise rates on energy products exceed the minimum levels required under EU legislation, with the sole exception of natural gas used for transport fuel. While nominal tax rates on the main transport fuels (petrol and diesel) were increased repeatedly in the 2000s for revenue raising purposes, they have not kept pace with inflation. As a consequence, real tax rates on transport fuels have declined in the last decade. Together with the rise in world oil market prices, this has led to a decline in the share of taxes in fuel prices. In 2011, excise duties accounted for 39% of petrol prices and 32% of diesel prices (OECD, 2013).

A further barrier can be identified in the heterogeneous taxation when different regions are considered, as the excise is not the same in all Italian regions but it varies. In 1999 in Italy the fiscal federalism has been introduced with law n. 133/1999 (L. 13 May 1999, n. 133), and the Italian regions gained autonomy also in the decision for the excise value.

- Are revisions / additional measures necessary in order to address energy efficiency improvements? How big could potential benefits be?

Improvements applicable to excise regime could relate to the follow points:

1. excise duties vary greatly among fuels and users and do not provide a consistent price for carbon.
2. excise duty on diesel was still 23% below that on petrol in 2011, a difference that is not environmentally justified (OECD, 2013).
3. exemptions apply to fuels used for electricity generation, in agriculture, in industrial facilities, and for road freight transport. Special tax provisions on energy and transport were estimated to result in revenue losses of 0.2% of GDP in 2010 (OECD, 2013).
4. fiscal federalism was introduced with the law n. 133/1999, so excises vary from region to region.

It is difficult to assess what would be the benefits of implementing specific changes in the system of excise duties. A given example regards point 3: the tax provisions on energy and transport were estimated to result in revenue losses of 0.2% of GDP (OECD, 2013).

- Which actors would benefit from a full consideration of energy efficiency?

The actors that would benefit from a full consideration of energy efficiency are:

- citizens;
- biofuel producers and distributors;
- stakeholders involved with the production of LPG and electrical vehicles.

Interaction between objectives

Two policy instruments interact when they have common primary or secondary objectives. *Please provide information for the selected policy instrument and the energy efficiency policy instrument(s) showing interlinkages and synergies on the following issues:*

Excise interacts synergistically with the car incentives because the *ecobonus* incentive encourages the use and purchase of electric or LPG cars. Therefore the *ecobonus* represents an instrument able to enhance the negative trend in fuel consumption that is already determined also by the increase in excise duties. In Italy the car incentives also called *ecobonus* are in force (L. 23 December 2014, n. 190 "Provisions for the preparation of the annual and multi-state," Stability Law 2015). Cars purchased by December 31, 2014 will get a bonus of up to 20% of the total cost, the discount varying according to the amount of vehicle CO₂ emissions. Regarding the purchase of vehicles in 2015, the *eco-bonus* will be calculated up to 15% of the total cost of the car. Scrapping is no longer required in particular for companies and for individuals, if one decides to buy a car that has CO₂ emissions of up to 95 g/km. The *ecobonus* is higher for the purchase of electric and LPG or CNG or hybrid vehicles (MISE, 2014).

No official documents evaluating the interlinkage of the respective two policy instruments are available.

- Which common objectives expressed either quantitatively or qualitatively are given?

The specific objective of the excise is to cope to natural or governmental emergencies, for this reason at the moment there are no common objectives between excise and ecobonus.

The ecobonus objectives are defined to:

- Incentivize the use of alternative power sources
- Reduce CO₂ emissions
- Encourage the use of new, cleaner technologies
- Avoid dependence on non-renewable energy.

However, if the excise purpose were modified there would be overlapping on the policies objectives.

- Which impacts on objectives due to the parallel implementation of the policy instruments based on official comments or data can be regarded?

The increase in fuel excise duties over the last years has stimulated the purchase of LPG or electric vehicles fostering the use of the ecobonus incentive.

Anyway, since the excise tax and the ecobonus do not have explicit common objectives, at the time there are no studies or data that describe the impact of the parallel implementation of the two policy instruments.

Interaction between target groups

Two policy instruments may be imposed on the same target groups or on specific sub-sets. In order to get a feeling on the extent of interaction, *please provide information for the selected policy instrument and the energy efficiency policy instrument(s) showing interlinkages and synergies on the following issue:*

- Do common target groups exist, and if yes, which are these target groups?

These policy instruments can be imposed on the same target groups. In this case the target groups are: private citizens, transport companies, agriculture sector. Both the excise tax and the *ecobonus* are applied to all target groups listed. In this way a cumulative effect can be obtained, strengthening the strategy to achieve energy efficiency targets. In the case of the transport and agriculture sector this effect is less significant since annual refunds are applied for the excise on the fuel used.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

Two policy instruments may interact due to tradeable permits / certificates or due to regulations. Please provide information for the selected policy instrument and the energy efficiency policy instrument(s) showing interlinkages and synergies on the following issues:

- Which market trading commodities (White Certificates, ERUs, etc.) interact with the selected policy instrument? The specific type of interaction is recognized when two policy instruments have rules for the same trading commodity, i.e. emission permits or green certificates. Therefore, the question to be answered is, does the interacting policy instruments affect the relevant market or not?

In Italy there are exonerations or reductions of the excises for the some uses of fuels: these exonerations can represent a disincentive for energy efficiency. These exemptions, for example, concern the fuels used to produce electricity, which result in a loss of revenue of 0.2% of GDP in 2010

(OECD, 2013) as well as a disincentive for reducing the use of polluting substances. In 2010 the Ministry of Finance launched the first comprehensive analysis of the effects of tax exemptions (GSE, 2014). This is an important initiative to identify and change the incentives and tax exemptions that are economically, socially and environmentally inefficient.

White certificates are negotiable instruments that certify the achievement of energy savings in end-use energy through actions and projects to increase energy efficiency (GSE, 2014). These require distributors of electricity and natural gas annually to reach certain targets of primary energy savings, expressed in tons of oil equivalent saved (TEP). A certificate is equal to the saving of one ton of oil equivalent (TEP). The companies can carry out their obligation realizing energy efficiency projects (GSE, 2014). So the white certificates, which are directly addressed to companies that produce and distribute energy as an instrument of market trading commodities, are effective in containing the negative impact produced by the excises exemptions on excise for companies producing electricity.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

The same pertinent authorities may be responsible for the implementation of two policy instruments with the same set of responsibilities or with properly distributed – and not overlapping – responsibilities. *Please provide information on the performance of the policy instruments under the respective criteria / sub-criteria of the evaluation method AMS, i.e. (see Konidari et al. 2014)*

- capacity of the implementation network (ability of all national competent parties to design, support and ensure the implementation of the policy instruments)

The main stakeholders of the implementation network for the management of the excise are the Ministry of Economy and Finance, the *Agenzia delle Dogane e dei Monopoli* (Italian Customs Agency) and the Regions. Instead, for the *ecobonus* management the main actors are the Ministry of Economic Development and the *Agenzia delle Entrate* (Italian Revenue Agency). In this case there are no overlapping of competences and the management of the two instruments in object is independent of each other.

- administrative burden (aggregate work exerted by the regulatory implementation network during the enforcement of the policy instruments)

As outlined in the previous point, the bodies that are responsible for the management of the two policy instruments are different and independent of each other. So, in this case since there is no overlap of responsibilities the administrative burden is equally distributed.

- financial feasibility (property of the policy instrument to be implemented with low overall costs by the pertinent regulatory authorities)

The two policy instruments have opposite nature: the excise is a tax and the *ecobonus* is an incentive. The excise implementation costs are really low because of the nature of the instrument: it is an indirect tax that involves the individual production and individual consumption, hence the producer pays the tribute which subsequently falls upon the consumer.

The ecobonus is a governmental incentive so the costs of implementation weighs entirely on the state. The State provides incentives for a total of 100 million euro (EIB funds) for the period 2013-2015 to promote the purchase of low-emission vehicles (law n. 134/2012).

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.2.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

Introduction

- Full name of the policy instrument not directly related to energy that however may contribute to improve energy efficiency

National Fund for Sustainable Growth

In order to guarantee a flourishing and effective research development in the EU countries, the EU Commission promotes specific actions aimed at sustaining economic efficiency and the state-of-the-art in the research processes in the EU industrial context (EU Commission, 2006). In Italy, the most important instrument devoted to this aim is the *Fund for Technological Innovation* ('Fondo Rotativo per l'Innovazione Tecnologica', FIT), initially established in 2001. The fund was provided by the Ministry of Economic Development (MISE) within the larger National Operational Plan for Research and Competitiveness (POE) 2007-2013¹². The FIT envisaged financial support to research areas identified by the MISE (9 research areas, in which energy and energy efficiency is explicitly mentioned) and strictly related to 'sustainable industrial activities'. The research activity referred to new products and prototypes, processes, or modification of these as far as the existent technology is significantly improved. In 2012, the FIT has been adapted to the new European context and replaced by the *National Fund for Sustainable Growth* ('Fondo per la Crescita Sostenibile', FCS)¹³. Among different research areas to be financed, the MISE program envisages specific interventions aimed at sustaining R&D projects within the Horizon 20-20 (H2020) framework, in particular those projects proposing significant technological advances in strong relationship with the H2020 objectives, including energy efficiency¹⁴. In addition, the D.M. 8 March 2013 explicitly mentions as a priority those projects aimed at minimizing the environmental impacts and at favouring the 'green transition' (MISE, 2013).

¹² POE represents the instrument through which Italy contributes to the Development and Cohesion Policies envisaged by the EU Commission in favour of the most disadvantaged areas. At 2014, one billion Euro have financed 154 projects of industrial research. Further details at: <http://www.ponrec.it/programma/interventi/ricerca-industriale/>

¹³ See Italian Law n. 134/2012.

¹⁴ <http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/index.php/it/incentivi/impresa/fondo-per-la-crescita-sostenibile/caratteristiche-del-fondo>

- **Specific focus of the policy instrument and target group**

All industrial and transport firms can benefit from the FCS, including independent research centres which operate in behalf of specific private companies. Recipient firms can also participate to the selection process in collaboration with universities or public institutions, as long as private subjects detain a minimum of 30% of risk capital. In some cases the MISE can also identify a series of specific categories of subjects to be specifically targeted by the fund.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

- **Are energy questions already considered indirectly in some part by the policy? If yes, please give details.**

Although the FCS aims at financing research on those firms producing energy efficient products, the final objective of reducing the energy consumption, through the adoption of such new products, is not explicitly considered. Nevertheless, this policy instrument provides effective support to the technology deployment in the residential sector, and in particular, at household level. For instance, in the case of 'white goods' for households, the mechanism is straightforward. By participating to some extent to capital risk, FCS provides firms with R&D subsidies in order to reduce the uncertainty of research outcome. Hence, firms can efficiently conduct research and generate new technical change to be embodied in new appliances. Once new energy-efficient appliances are produced, available on the market and purchased by households (which can benefit from eco-bonus¹⁵), a large amount of energy can be saved in consequence of using more efficient appliances.

Although there are no studies or statistics which put in relationship the impact of R&D subsidies and the amount of energy saved, there exists large evidence on the positive effects of R&D subsidies to boost eco-innovation, including energy efficiency, and on the crucial role of public policies in sustaining technical change to address the issue of energy saving (Verdolini and Galeotti, 2011; Noailly, 2012; EU Commission, 2011; Costantini *et al.*, 2014; Filippini *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, the EU Eco-Innovation Action Plan highlights the importance of supporting sustainable innovation, of which energy efficiency is relevant part, both in terms of invention and diffusion of technologies (OECD, 2011).

Official statistics on the amounts received by candidate companies are partially available on the MISE website. With respect to the requests obtained in 2013, data describe a financial endowment of Eur. 524 Mil., of which around 70% allocated to SMEs (Table 1) and 23,62% devoted to the promotion of H-2020 targets (MISE, 2014).

¹⁵ The Eco-bonus represents tax deductions which aim at facilitate the renewal of dwellings and substitution of furniture. They include insulated windows and roofs, heating systems and 'white goods' to be substituted with more efficient equipment or devices. In the case of appliances, the Eco-bonus requires the purchase of devices with a minimum energy consumption class equals or higher than A+. Currently (2015), the amount of tax deduction (50%) is split over ten years with a maximum of Eur 10,000.

Table 1: FCS financial endowment and recipient companies by size

Company size	Number of requests	Financed investment (Euro)
Large	86	205.818.645,19
Medium	101	200.116.706,88
Small	84	118.993.639,12
Total companies	271	524.928.991,19

Source: MISE (2014)

- What are existing barriers / reasons for not considering energy efficiency so far by the policy or measure?

Barriers are not explicitly related to energy efficiency, as the MISE-FCS is not specifically aimed at diffusing new energy efficiency technologies. Some (indirect) barriers can be identified in the difficulty in presenting necessary documentation to access the fund, although the requests in both 2013 and 2014 have exceeded the resources previously assigned to the Ministry, with an extra allocation of Euro 535 Mil in 2014¹⁶. Moreover, the candidature process has been significantly improved by implementing a digital platform which allows companies for directly accessing and sending all the necessary documentation¹⁷.

- Are revisions / additional measures necessary in order to address energy efficiency improvements? How big could potential benefits be?

Although the single contribution in energy saving of a more efficient appliance is modest, their aggregated sum, due to the large diffusion of white goods among Italian households, is able to produce a large impact. However, additional measures to the supply side, which would target both Italian and international producers of most energy efficient appliances as specific beneficiaries with preferential access to the FCS, could generate additional effects in terms of technology invention.

- Which actors would benefit from a full consideration of energy efficiency?

In the case of 'white goods', Italian and international companies producing appliances in the Italian territory with specific innovative content aimed at reducing energy consumption.

Interaction between objectives

Two policy instruments interact when they have common primary or secondary objectives. *Please provide information for the selected policy instrument and the energy efficiency policy instrument(s) showing interlinkages and synergies on the following issues:*

- Which common objectives expressed either quantitatively or qualitatively are given?

No common objectives with other instruments are expressed within the MISE-FCS guidelines.

¹⁶ See <http://www.ponrec.it/programma/interventi/ricerca-industriale/>

¹⁷ <https://fondocrescitasostenibile.mcc.it/mise-fcs/>

- Which impacts on objectives due to the parallel implementation of the policy instruments based on official comments or data can be regarded?

No data or official comments exist for measuring the impacts of parallel implementation with other instruments in order to obtain energy efficiency gains. However, since firms receiving R&D incentives can efficiently generate technical change embodied in the appliances aimed at reducing the amount of energy used, once new energy-efficient appliances are available on the market, households can benefit from energy saving by purchasing new and more efficient appliances. The diffusion of new appliances might be significantly enlarged with further economic policy instruments on the demand side, such as Eco-bonus, in order to induce households to substitute old appliances with more efficient ones (i.e. appliances classified in Italy as Class AA/AA+).

Interaction between target groups

Two policy instruments may be imposed on the same target groups or on specific sub-sets. In order to get a feeling on the extent of interaction, *please provide information for the selected policy instrument and the energy efficiency policy instrument(s) showing interlinkages and synergies on the following issue:*

- Do common target groups exist, and if yes, which are these target groups?

There are no common target groups. Households and firms are different subjects and the two policy instrument do not envisage interaction between the two subjects.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

Two policy instruments may interact due to tradeable permits / certificates or due to regulations. Please provide information for the selected policy instrument and the energy efficiency policy instrument(s) showing interlinkages and synergies on the following issues:

- Which market trading commodities (White Certificates, ERUs, etc.) interact with the selected policy instrument? The specific type of interaction is recognized when two policy instruments have rules for the same trading commodity, i.e. emission permits or green certificates. Therefore, the question to be answered is, does the interacting policy instruments affect the relevant market or not?

None.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

The same pertinent authorities may be responsible for the implementation of two policy instruments with the same set of responsibilities or with properly distributed – and not overlapping – responsibilities. *Please provide information on the performance of the policy instruments under the respective criteria / sub-criteria of the evaluation method AMS, i.e. (see Konidari et al. 2014)*

- capacity of the implementation network (ability of all national competent parties to design, support and ensure the implementation of the policy instruments)

The MISE is responsible of the fund allocation. In order to guarantee an efficient and regular fund allocation, the MISE subscribes specific agreements with banks ('dealers') which assume the responsibility to evaluate all the administrative requirements of the candidate companies as well as the technical and economic feasibility of their projects. For what concerns the assessment of the

technological feasibility of the projects, the dealers take advantage of specific commissions of external experts, chosen by the MISE¹⁸.

- administrative burden (aggregate work exerted by the regulatory implementation network during the enforcement of the policy instruments)

There are no coordination mechanisms between the FCS and other instruments. It is worth mentioning that when also Eco-bonus is considered, the two policies are managed by different institutions, namely MISE for FCS and Agenzia delle Entrate (an Agency managed by the Ministry of the Economy and Finance) for Eco-bonus allocation. As a consequence, the burden for administrative management can be relevant and could be significantly reduced whereby both the FCS and the Eco-bonus would be implemented by the same institution.

- financial feasibility (property of the policy instrument to be implemented with low overall costs by the pertinent regulatory authorities)

For the reasons previously explained, when considering the joint mechanism due to the coordinated action given by the combination of technology-push FCS measure and demand-pull Eco-bonus, the administrative policy cost-efficiency is also relevant, as the two policies are currently managed by different institutions and follow different guidelines, with absence of coordination.

1.2.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

Introduction

Please provide information about the following issues:

- Full name of the policy instrument not directly related to energy that however may contribute to improve energy efficiency

Ecopass/Area C urban road pricing, enforced by the City of Milan (Italy)

Full name: “Measures to contain vehicular traffic. Approval of access regulation to the Limited Traffic Zone Cerchia dei Bastioni” - Deliberation n. 588/2013 of 27/03/2013 of the City Council (title of the deliberation defining the policy as structural measure, after an experimental period started in 2012 and previously - from 2008 until 2011 - with a pollution charge named “Ecopass”).

- Specific focus of the policy instrument and target group

Located in Lombardy, Northern Italy, the city of Milan has 1,3 million inhabitants and is the centre of the largest metropolitan area of the country, a conurbation with more than 3,5 million inhabitants.

The Milan area is crossed every day by intense flows of passengers and freight vehicles. According to 2012 data, collected at the municipal boundary, about 750.000 vehicles enter every day the city of Milan, of which about 15% are commercial vehicles. The car flows are composed for 60-65% by

¹⁸ For further details, see <http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/index.php/it/incentivi/impresa/fit-fondo-innovazione-tecnologica>

people living outside Milan who enter the city, the remaining quota by Milan residents coming back home (Comune di Milano, AMAT, 2013).

Traffic, together with heating, is among the major sources of air pollution, which is one of the most severe environmental problems for the city, the metropolitan area and the region. In the city of Milan alone, PM10 daily limit values have been exceeded for 106 days in 2009, 85 in 2010, 132 in 2011, 107 in 2012 and 81 in 2013 (Comune di Milano, AMAT, 2015a) much more than the maximum number of days allowed by EU regulations (35 days).

The severe congestion and pollution problems of the city have led to the decision of implementing since January 2008 a pollution charge ("Ecopass"), charging vehicles proportionally to their PM10 emissions to enter the densest city area, the inner historical centre. In January 2012, Ecopass was replaced by a congestion charge ("Area C"), characterized by a flat charge. The concerned area of both Ecopass and Area C coincides with a Limited Traffic Zone (ZTL - Zona Traffico Limitato) named "Cerchia dei Bastioni". It is 8,2 kmq and corresponds to about 4,5% of the total municipal area (Comune di Milano, AMAT, 2015b). This area is a major attractor because of the activities and services localized here, attracting daily about 500,000 people. The main focus of the Ecopass/Area C road pricing policy instrument is therefore the regulation and reduction of traffic congestion and related externalities within this specific area, targeting both vehicles for the transport of people and of goods.

Several deliberations adopted over time¹⁹ have defined the system regulating the access to the charged area (ZTL Cerchia dei Bastioni). Currently, the limitations to the circulation of vehicles are active from 7.30 AM to 7.30 PM during working days between Monday and Friday and foresee²⁰:

- a total prohibition to enter Area C for most polluting vehicles;
- free access for ecological vehicles and specific categories of authorized vehicles;
- access subject to the payment of a daily charge (5€) for the remaining vehicles.

- **Objective of the policy instrument (qualitative information might be sufficient)**

The **objectives** of "Area C" are (as stated by the City of Milan)²¹:

- decreasing road traffic in "Cerchia dei Bastioni";
- improving public transport networks;
- raising funds for soft mobility infrastructures: cycle lanes, pedestrian zones, 30kph zones;
- improving the quality of life by reducing the number of accidents, uncontrolled parking, noise and air pollution.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Please provide information (if available) about the following issues:

- Are energy questions already considered indirectly in some part by the policy? If yes, please give details.

¹⁹ For Ecopass: n. 1788/2007 of 20.07.2007 and following modifications; For Area C: n. 2526/2011 of 4.11.2011; n. 1402 of 29.06.2012; n. 1404 of 29.06.2012; n. 1694/2012 of 6.9.2012; n. 588/2013 of 27.03.2013.

²⁰ Except on Thursdays, during which limitations end at 6 pm. Information on the functioning of Area C are from: Comune di Milano, AMAT, 2015.

²¹ http://www.comune.milano.it/wps/portal/ist/en/area_c

Ecopass/Area C is focused on the reduction of traffic and related externalities, namely accidents, noise and of local air pollutants, which as shown above is a key environmental problem for the city. Nonetheless, energy questions are indirectly considered by the policy, since the policy aims to create the conditions to improve, protect and develop the public transport network and sustainable mobility (namely walking, biking, low-speed traffic) in the area, thus also creating the conditions for a more energy efficient transport. The policy also aims to raise monetary resources that are to be devoted to the development of sustainable mobility, thus further contributing to support energy-efficient mobility in the city centre and the wider city area, an example of ‘win-win’ policy.

- Are there already impacts on energy efficiency due to the policy instrument? Are the impacts positive or negative?

The Ecopass/Area C scheme has obtained traffic and congestion reduction, which also have an impact in terms of energy use and GHG emissions reduction thanks to the decrease of the number of circulating vehicles, reduction in vehicle travel and the increase of the efficiency of traffic flows. Between 2008 and 2010, Ecopass has reduced traffic in the charged area by 16,2 % with respect to the pre-Ecopass situation (AMAT, 2011a). Between January 2012 and June 2014, Area C has reduced traffic by 28-30% (Comune di Milano, AMAT, 2015b).

Positive impacts in terms of energy saving have already been achieved by the policy and estimated by AMAT (2013) in terms of a CO₂ emissions reduction from circulating vehicles.

In the period 2008-2011, average daily CO₂ emissions from road traffic referred to the first semester have decreased by 18%, from 146 ton/day in the pre-Ecopass period to 120 ton/day in 2011 (AMAT, 2011b)

Figure 4: Historical trend of average daily emissions from road traffic in the Ecopass Area
Average daily carbon dioxide emissions

Source: AMAT (2011b)

Between 2010 and 2013, average daily CO₂ emissions due to circulating vehicles in Area C during daytime of working days in the monitoring period (January-June) have decreased by 29%, and total

CO₂ emissions in the monitoring period (all days included) have decreased by 21% in the same time frame (AMAT, 2013b).

**Figure 5: CO₂ average daily emissions during daytime (ton/day) (left graph)
CO₂ total emissions (kton) in the monitoring period (January-February) (right graph)**

Source: AMAT (2013b)

A further element to be considered is the decrease of the average CO₂ emission factor of vehicles circulating in the charged area. Ecopass has stimulated relevant changes to the composition of vehicles entering the area. In fact, between the pre-Ecopass situation and June 2011, the number of most polluting vehicles (in terms of local pollutants) had diminished by 48,1% and the number of ecological vehicles had increased by 478% (namely: electric, hybrid, methane and LPG-fuelled vehicles) (AMAT, 2011a). The AMAT study shows also that the increase of new ecological vehicles is evident also within the Milan city and province area, with a rate significantly higher than the increase rate at national level (32%-82% in comparison with the national rate of 14%-27%) (AMAT, 2011a).

Between 2008 and 2011, comparing the first semester of each year, the average CO₂ emission factor of circulating vehicles has decreased from 285 g/km (pre-Ecopass value) to 259 g/km in 2011 (- 9% reduction over the entire period and average annual reduction of -2%) (AMAT, 2011b).

The following graph shows the average CO₂ emission factor of vehicles circulating in the charged area:

Figure 6: Average CO₂ emission factor

Source: AMAT (2011b)

The impact of Ecopass/Area C on energy saving must be placed within the overall context of CO₂ emissions and energy use from transport in the overall Milan city area. CO₂ emissions from vehicles circulating in the charged area are 3% of total CO₂ emissions of the city due to traffic (AMAT, 2013b). Looking at the trends of CO₂ emissions due to circulating vehicles in the overall city area, emissions have decreased by 5% between 2010 and 2013, for the effects of two phenomena: the reduction of kilometres travelled with motorized vehicles and the renewal of the circulating vehicles stock (average CO₂ emission factor has decreased by 2%) (AMAT, 2013b). The pollution and congestion charge have contributed to these two phenomena.

Figure 7: Carbon dioxide due to circulating vehicles in Milan (divided according to zones)

Source: AMAT (2013b)

- What are existing barriers / reasons for not considering energy efficiency so far by the policy or measure?

As recalled above, Milan has a severe problem of local air pollution, which is exacerbated also by local geographic and climate conditions which limit the dispersion of particulate matter (Comune di Milano, AMAT, 2015b). Therefore, the main policy priority of Milan's road pricing policy, beyond road traffic reduction, regards the pollutants reduction. Nonetheless, the City of Milan is committed to climate protection and sustainable energy policies and has adhered to the Covenant of Mayors. Within the CoM, the city has the target to reduce overall CO₂ emissions by 20% below 2005 levels by 2020 (Comune di Milano, AMAT, 2015c). Therefore, sustainable mobility measures promoted by the city, including also the congestion charging scheme, can be referred to a broader view on sustainable mobility which also considers CO₂ emission reduction, energy efficiency and energy saving.

- Are revisions / additional measures necessary in order to address energy efficiency improvements? How big could potential benefits be?

Different options for revising the system have been considered, including: (i) the extension of the area subject to charge; (ii) the extension of the area subject to charge coupled with the creation of two concentric areas delimited by cordons and the application of a charge when passing each cordon; and (iii) the variation of the charge. Critical aspects have been identified for the area extension option (possible traffic increase in the city centre) and the two-cordons option (possible implementation difficulties) (Comune di Milano, AMAT, 2015b).

The most recent mobility strategic plan (Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan of the City of Milan - PUMS Piano Urbano della Mobilità Sostenibile)²² defines the revision of the policy as a long-term horizon intervention, and it focuses on a solution which would extend the area subject to charge and reduce the charge by 50%. The plan binds the implementation of this solution to the realization of further improvements to accessibility to the area and to parking regulation controls, which are considered as necessary for an effective implementation of this policy revision.

The mobility plan estimates that this revision of Area C (extension of the area coupled with reduction of the charge) would further reduce energy use by 3% in addition to reductions deriving from the implementation of the other policies set by the plan. It should be noted that energy efficiency improvements would not be the main focus of this policy revision, but would be coupled with the other objectives that the policy is targeting.

- Which actors would benefit from a full consideration of energy efficiency?

A full consideration of energy efficiency in the revision of the policy would need to be coupled with the other targets that the policy is currently prioritizing (i.e. air pollutants reduction).

A strengthened urban road pricing policy would benefit users of public transport, since public transport supply in the area would be further improved; pedestrians and bicyclers, thanks to a further reduction of traffic, congestion and circulating vehicles; car users and freight vehicles, who would benefit from more fluid traffic flows and improved speeds; local residents, who would benefit from improved air quality and reduced noise.

²² Approved in March 2015 by the City Council, the PUMS is a strategic "plan of policies" setting directions for the development of mobility in Milan for the next decade, also considering the newly established Metropolitan City Area (previously named Province of Milan).

Interaction between objectives

Two policy instruments interact when they have common primary or secondary objectives. *Please provide information for the selected policy instrument and the energy efficiency policy instrument(s) showing interlinkages and synergies on the following issues:*

- Which common objectives expressed either quantitatively or qualitatively are given?

A policy instrument addressing greenhouse gases reduction and energy efficiency interacting with Ecopass/Area C is the set of European policies aimed to reduce CO₂ emissions from vehicles. This includes binding targets for CO₂ emission reduction of new cars²³ and vans²⁴, CO₂ labelling of cars²⁵ and measures to reduce GHG intensity of vehicles fuels²⁶. The European legislation on this topic aims to reduce GHG from road transport, unique sector in Europe where GHG emissions are still increasing and which still contributes in a significant way to EU total CO₂ emissions (one-fifth).

Since Milan's road pricing policy is focused on congestion reduction and local air pollution, whereas this set of EU policies are focused on CO₂, no common objectives can be identified. However certain interactions can be identified looking at the impacts of the two policies (see next paragraph). No official documents describing and evaluating the interlinkage between the two instruments are available.

- Which impacts on objectives due to the parallel implementation of the policy instruments based on official comments or data can be regarded?

The urban road pricing scheme has been in place since 2008 as a pollution charge (Ecopass) and since 2011 as a congestion charge (Area C). The EU regulation on CO₂ emissions from vehicles is in place since 2009 and is periodically updated. Therefore the two policy instruments are implemented in parallel.

As anticipated above, Ecopass/Area C do not set specific GHG or CO₂ reduction objectives, nevertheless it has been estimated that they have enabled a CO₂ emissions reduction from vehicles circulating in the city centre of Milan and a decrease of the average CO₂ emission factor of circulating vehicles, as detailed in the previous sections.

These results have been determined by the numerous policies on transport in place, including the application in Italy of European legislation on CO₂ emissions from vehicles. Specific studies that analyse the contribution of each policy to these results on CO₂ reduction and renovation of the stock of circulating vehicles are not available.

Interaction between target groups

Two policy instruments may be imposed on the same target groups or on specific sub-sets. In order to get a feeling on the extent of interaction, *please provide information for the selected policy instrument and the energy efficiency policy instrument(s) showing interlinkages and synergies on the following issue:*

- Do common target groups exist, and if yes, which are these target groups?

The main target groups of Ecopass/Area C are drivers of private motorized vehicles (for people and freight transport), and, indirectly, the users of public transportation.

²³ http://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/transport/vehicles/cars/documentation_en.htm

²⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/transport/vehicles/vans/documentation_en.htm

²⁵ http://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/transport/vehicles/labelling/documentation_en.htm

²⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/transport/fuel/index_en.htm

The main target groups of EU policies on CO₂ emissions from vehicles are vehicles producers (targeted by the binding targets for CO₂ emission reduction of new cars and vans), consumers (targeted by the CO₂ labelling of cars) and fuel suppliers (targeted by fuel quality legislation).

Therefore there are interlinkages among the target groups of the two policies. Purchasers of new vehicles are affected by the effects of EU policies when purchasing a new car and when purchasing fuels, at the same time they are affected by the urban road pricing policy when entering Milan's city centre.

A possible synergy between targets groups of these policy instruments could take place during information campaigns to drivers. Such campaigns could jointly communicate the rationale of the two policy instruments to raise drivers' awareness on the environmental impacts of their purchasing and driving behaviours.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

Two policy instruments may interact due to tradeable permits / certificates or due to regulations. Please provide information for the selected policy instrument and the energy efficiency policy instrument(s) showing interlinkages and synergies on the following issues:

- Which market trading commodities (White Certificates, ERUs, etc.) interact with the selected policy instrument? The specific type of interaction is recognized when two policy instruments have rules for the same trading commodity, i.e. emission permits or green certificates. Therefore, the question to be answered is, does the interacting policy instruments affect the relevant market or not?

The urban road pricing regulations define rules and criteria for the access to Milan's city centre, as well as sanctions for non compliance, which are imposed to drivers of vehicles entering the area.

European policies on CO₂ emissions from vehicles define rules and sanctions which are imposed to car manufacturers (with reference to the compliance with the binding targets for CO₂ emission reduction of new cars and vans). EU policies on fuel quality foresee the possibility for national authorities to impose penalties where samples of fuels are found to be out of the directive specification (EC, 2015).

No interactions can be identified between the rules-implementing mechanisms of the two policy instruments.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

The same pertinent authorities may be responsible for the implementation of two policy instruments with the same set of responsibilities or with properly distributed – and not overlapping – responsibilities. *Please provide information on the performance of the policy instruments under the respective criteria / sub-criteria of the evaluation method AMS, i.e. (see Konidari et al. 2014)*

Please use official comments or data if available

- capacity of the implementation network (ability of all national competent parties to design, support and ensure the implementation of the policy instruments)

The implementation network of Ecopass/Area C is mainly at local level and is composed by the following parties:

- The City Council of the Municipality of Milan, which has designed, adopted and enforced the policy instrument;
- the municipal mobility agency (AMAT – Agenzia Mobilità Ambiente Territorio), which is involved in the monitoring of the policy instrument's performances;
- the local public transport company (ATM – Azienda Trasporti Milanesi), which manages the ticketing system.

The implementation network of EU policies on CO₂ emissions from vehicles in Italy is composed by the following parties:

- Ministry of Economic Development (MISE), Ministry of the Environment (MATTM), Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport (MIT); in particular MISE, MATTM and MIT are responsible to develop annually a guide for consumers on cars' CO₂ emissions and on fuel saving²⁷; MISE and MIT collect data and communicate them to EU/EEA (European Energy Agency) in relation with the binding targets for CO₂ emission reduction of new cars and vans.

Mainly because the implementation scale is different, there are no interactions between the implementation networks of the two policy instruments and therefore on their implementation capacity.

- administrative burden (aggregate work exerted by the regulatory implementation network during the enforcement of the policy instruments)

The administrative burden weighs on different entities which operate at different levels, therefore it is not possible to foresee an interaction to optimize the aggregated work.

- financial feasibility (property of the policy instrument to be implemented with low overall costs by the pertinent regulatory authorities)

Investment costs for Ecopass amounted to 7 million € and mainly regarded the monitoring infrastructure (installation of video-cameras, system software) (Croci, Ravazzi, forthcoming). A traffic management centre was already in place in the city and was used also to manage the pollution/congestion charge scheme. This availability of technological infrastructure contributed to contain investment costs (*ibid*). Operating costs of both Ecopass and Area C schemes amount to 14 million € per year, directly funded by the scheme's revenues (entrance fees and sanctions to system violators) (*ibid*). Annual revenues changed over time (12.1 million € in 2008, 5.9 in 2011 during Ecopass; 11.2 in January-June 2012 with Area C). Revenues are mainly used to fund improvements in public transports (*ibid*).

Regarding the implementation of EU policies on CO₂ emissions from vehicles in Italy, estimates on the implementation costs are not available.

Since the instruments have diverse implementation networks, objectives and financial management, no interactions on the financial feasibility can be noticed.

²⁷ As foreseen by directive 1999/94/CE, adopted in Italy with DPR 84/2003.

ANNEXES

REFERENCES

Agenzia delle Dogane e dei Monopoli (2014): “D.Lgs.n.504/95, Allegato I. Variazione aliquote di accisa su determinati prodotti energetici - Nota”.

URL: http://www.ipsoa.it/~media/Quotidiano/2015/01/07/Accise-su-benzina-e-gasolio--variazioni-d-aliquota-per-il-2015/AdD_nota%20pdf.pdf

AMAT (2010): “Monitoraggio Ecopass. Gennaio - Giugno 2010. Indicatori sintetici”.

URL: <http://www.milanosimuove.it/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2010/10/rapportoEcopassIsem2010.pdf>

AMAT (2011a): “Valutazione nuovi scenari di regolamentazione degli accessi alla ZTL Cerchia dei Bastioni”.

URL: <http://www.amat-mi.it/it/downloads/74/>

AMAT (2011b): “Monitoraggio Ecopass. Gennaio – Giugno 2011. Indicatori sintetici”.

AMAT (2013a): “Monitoraggio Area C. Emissioni atmosferiche da traffico stradale a Milano. Periodo gennaio-febbraio 2013”.

URL: <http://www.amat-mi.it/it/documenti/dettaglio/47/>

AMAT (2013b): “Monitoraggio Area C. Emissioni atmosferiche nella Città di Milano. Periodo gennaio-giugno 2013”.

URL: <http://www.amat-mi.it/it/downloads/182/>

Camerinelli A. (2010): “Manuale delle accise 2010”.

URL: http://www.eni.com/it_IT/attachments/documentazione/bilanci-rapporti/rapporti-2010/Manuale-delle-Accise-2010.pdf

Cingano F., Faiella I. (2013): “La tassazione “verde” in Italia: l’analisi di una carbon tax sui trasporti”. Questioni di Economia e Finanza (Occasional Papers), n. 206.

URL: http://www.bancaditalia.it/pubblicazioni/qef/2013-0206/QEF_206.pdf

Commissione Ecopass (2010): “Relazione conclusiva dei lavori”.

URL: http://www.milanosimuove.it/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2011/09/Documento-Commissione-Ecopass_Rel_12.pdf

Comune di Milano, AMAT (2013): “Aggiornamento del Piano Generale del Traffico Urbano. Stato di attuazione e aggiornamento”.

URL: www.amat-mi.it/it/downloads/86/

Comune di Milano, AMAT (2015a): “Piano Urbano della Mobilità Sostenibile Milano. Valutazione Ambientale Strategica. Rapporto Ambientale”.

URL: [http://download.comune.milano.it/24_03_2015/VAS-Rapporto%20Ambientale%20febbraio%202015%20\(1427206355842\).pdf](http://download.comune.milano.it/24_03_2015/VAS-Rapporto%20Ambientale%20febbraio%202015%20(1427206355842).pdf)

Comune di Milano, AMAT (2015b): “Piano Urbano della Mobilità Sostenibile Milano. Documento di Piano”.

URL: <https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=0B1yqkoznVqZXcm45RzR5MHFrX2s&usp=sharing>

Comune di Milano, AMAT (2015c): "Proposta di PAES Piano di Azione per l'Energia Sostenibile e il Clima. Pianificare e programmare per ridurre le emissioni di gas serra". *Presentation*.

URL:

<http://mediagallery.comune.milano.it/cdm/objects/changeme:32101/datastreams/dataStream7742621732586123/content>

Costantini V., Crespi F., Orsatti G., Palma A. (2014): "Policy Inducement Effects in Energy Efficiency Technologies. An Empirical Analysis on the Residential Sector". In *Green Energy and Efficiency. An Economic Perspective*. Eds. Ansuategi A., Delgado J., Galarraga I. Springer.

Cresme Ricerche, Legambiente (2013): "Innovazione energetica in edilizia. Rapporto ONRE 2013".

URL: http://www.legambiente.it/sites/default/files/docs/sito_onre_2013_min.pdf

Croci E., Ravazzi Douvan A. (forthcoming): "Urban road pricing: the experience of Milan". In *Critical Issues in Environmental Taxation, Volume XV*, Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd.

Curcuruto A.M. (2012): "L'esperienza del Comune di Bari nell'introduzione di parametri di sostenibilità energetica ed ambientale nella regolamentazione edilizia". Presentation held at the seminar organized by the EU-funded project PATRES on 19/12/12 in Bari.

URL: http://www.patres.net/media/114590/patres_curcuruto.pptx

EU Commission (2006): "Disciplina comunitaria in materia di aiuti di stato a favore di ricerca, sviluppo e innovazione". Com. 2006/C 323/01.

EU Commission (2011): "Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions Innovation for a Sustainable Future - The Eco-innovation Action Plan (Eco-AP)". COM/2011/0899 final.

URL: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0899>

EU Commission (2012): "Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. CARS 2020: Action Plan for a competitive and sustainable automotive industry in Europe". COM(2012) 636 final.

URL: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2012:0636:FIN:EN:PDF>

EU Commission (2015): "Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council. Quality of petrol and diesel fuel used for road transport in the European Union. Twelfth annual report. (Reporting year 2013)".

URL: http://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/transport/fuel/docs/com_2015_70_en.pdf

FAIB Confesercenti (2013): "Accise e consumi sui carburanti. Studio Confesercenti: 'Ad un aumento del 54% del prelievo è corrisposto un calo consumi del 21%. Ulteriori aumenti sarebbero fortemente negativi per l'economia ed il gettito fiscale'". FAIB Informa n. 32.

URL: http://www.confesercenti.tv/attachments/article/356/faib2013_32.pdf

Filippini, M. Hunt L. C., Zorić J. (2014): "Impact of energy policy instruments on the estimated level of underlying energy efficiency in the EU residential sector". *Energy Policy*, Vol. 69(C), pp. 73-81.

Graham D.J., Glaister S. (2002): "The Demand for Automobile Fuel: A Survey of Elasticities", Journal of Transport Economics and Policy Vol. 36, No. 1.

GSE (2014): "Rapporto Annuale sul meccanismo dei Certificati Bianchi 2014 , Gestore dei Servizi Energetici".

URL:

http://www.gse.it/it/CertificatiBianchi/GSE_Documenti/Documenti/Rapporto%20Annuale%20Certificati%20Bianchi_final.pdf

JRC (2010): "How to develop a Sustainable Energy Action Plan. Guidebook".

URL: http://www.eumayors.eu/IMG/pdf/seap_guidelines_en.pdf

JRC (2015): "The Covenant of Mayors in Figures and Performance Indicators: 6-year Assessment".

URL:

http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/IMG/pdf/Covenant_of_Mayors_in_Figures_and_Performance_Indicators_6-year_Assessme---.pdf

Kolassa D. (2014): "Imposizione diretta. Accise su alcolici, tabacco e prodotti energetici".

URL:

[http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/fiches_techniques/2013/051103/04A_FT\(2013\)051103_IT.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/fiches_techniques/2013/051103/04A_FT(2013)051103_IT.pdf)

Lombard P.L., Molocchi A., Buscema I. e G. Molinario (2005): "I costi ambientali e sociali della mobilità in Italia". 5° Rapporto di Amici della terra e Ferrovie dello Stato.

Ministry of Economic Development (MISE) (2013): "Decreto 8 Marzo 2013. Individuazione delle priorità, delle forme e delle intensità massime di aiuto concedibili nell'ambito del Fondo per la crescita sostenibile, ai sensi dell'articolo 23, comma 3, del decreto-legge 22 giugno 2012, n. 83."

Ministry of Economic Development (MISE) (2014): "Esiti dell'apertura dello sportello relativo al bando 20/06/2013".

URL:

<http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/images/stories/documenti/Horizon-grafici-ott14.pdf>

Noailly J. (2012): "Improving the energy efficiency of buildings: The impact of environmental policy on technological innovation". Energy Economics, Vol. 34 (3), pp. 795-806.

OECD (2011): "Invention and Transfer of Environmental Technologies. OECD Studies on Environmental Innovation", OECD Publishing, Paris.

OECD (2013): "OECD Environmental Performance Reviews: Italy 2013", OECD Publishing.

URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264186378-en>

OECD-IEA (2012), Energy Prices and Taxes.

Tomasi F. et al. (2013): "PATRES - Public Administration Training and coaching on Renewable Energy Systems. Final Publishable Report".

URL: http://www.patres.net/media/122828/patres_final_publishable_report.pdf

Unione Petrolifera (2015): "Relazione Annuale 2015".

URL: <http://www.unione petrolifera.it/?wpdmpro=relazione-annuale-2015&wpdmdl=4803>

Verdolini E., Galeotti M. (2011): "At home and abroad: An empirical analysis of innovation and diffusion in energy technologies". *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, Vol. 61(2), pp. 119-134.

Zara M. (2007), "Il regolamento edilizio come strumento normativo per promuovere l'energia sostenibile". Presentation held at the IV Territorial Conference Altotevere for Sustainable Energy".
URL: http://www.utopieconcrete.it/download/Fiera%202007/Zara_light_1.pdf

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.3

INTERLINKAGE AND SYNERGIES BETWEEN SELECTED OTHER POLICY AREAS AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT**

NATIONAL REPORT FOR SERBIA

31. JULY 2015

Partner: Centre for Energy, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Mining and Geology

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Universiteit
Antwerpen

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: University of Belgrade – Faculty of Mining and Geology

Steering Committee member ⁽¹⁾: Prof. Dejan Ivezić

Prepared by: Prof. Dejan Ivezić, Dr. Marija Živković, Dr. Miodrag Grujić

⁽¹⁾ *The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.*

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACRONYMS 4

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY 5

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS 7

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY 7

 1.1.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR 7

 1.1.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR 9

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY 11

 1.2.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR 11

 1.2.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR 13

REFERENCES 16

ACRONYMS

DH	District Heating
EEAP	Energy Efficiency Action Plan
EUE	Efficient Use of Energy

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Relatively modestly developed policy instruments directed to improve energy efficiency in building and transport sector make even more important implementation of general, energy related policy instruments, or policy instruments from others sectors, which can contribute to energy efficiency improvements. This is especially important for achieving of energy savings proposed in the second Energy Efficiency Action Plan (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b).

As general, energy policy instruments that indirectly or/and in the synergy with energy efficiency policy instruments contribute to energy efficiency in buildings sector, **Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy for the consumers connected to district heating system** is selected, while **Introduction of electrical buses instead of diesel fueled buses in public transport in cities** is selected for transport sector.

The focus of **Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy for the consumers connected to district heating system** is the supply of thermal energy, with the objective to introduce market principles in the operation of district heating companies (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015a) and improvement of efficiency (including the energy efficiency) of production, distribution and supply of thermal energy in the district heating systems. Implemented together with **Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings** this instrument should lead to the reduction in energy consumption up to 25% in residential sector in Serbia (Jovanović Popović M. et al., 2012).

The aim of **Introduction of electrical buses instead of diesel fueled buses in public transport in cities** is the substitution of using more expensive and imported diesel fuel with significantly cheaper and domestic electricity, in public transport. According to the analysis and testing, done by the Belgrade Public transport enterprise in 2014, in Serbian conditions introduction of electrical buses in Belgrade theoretically should enable saving of up to 70% of diesel fuel and significant reduction of local pollution (Živanović et al., 2014). Implemented together with **Traffic management system**, these policy instruments should provide optimal routes for electric busses, green lines, etc. and maximize saving potential, but also verify environmental and financial results of this instrument.

Introduction of green roofs and green walls is policy instrument that includes designing and building of roofs and walls covered with vegetation, fully or partially. **Introduction of green roofs and green walls** is included in system of urban planning (Government of the Republic of Serbia 2014b). This measure creates a better microclimate and reduces the heat island effect. That's why this instrument is a significant measure for climate changes adaptation (City of Belgrade, 2015). Introduction of green roofs or walls due to their insulating properties should contribute in achievement of **energy performance requirements** and have positive influence on results of **energy audits**.

Subsidies for the purchasing of new vehicles and the replacement of old one (so called "old for new mechanism") was introduced as policy instrument with the motivation to support the Serbian automotive industry, and overall economic development of the country. The most significant results were achieved in passenger cars sector where regulation was formalized to encourage the replacement of old vehicles equipped with engines that do not meet even Euro 3 standard, with new domestic vehicles equipped with Euro 5 engines. The subsidy per vehicle varied in the range from 600 to 1,000 Euro (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2011b). The Fund for Environmental Protection subsidized old for new mechanism as an instrument of environmental and climate change policy. The total value of funds available for this purpose amounted to 20,000,000 dinars (app. 200 thousands euro), or 100,000 dinars (app. 1,000 euro) per vehicle (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b). Currently, this instrument is conducted by domestic manufacturer of cars (FCA

Serbia)¹. Energy efficiency potential of this instrument is recognized, and it is estimated that achieved shavings in period 2010 – 2012 were 0.00765 Mtoe (0.32 PJ). This instrument is compatible, and represents the support to proposed regulatory instrument - **Fuel economy standards/vehicle CO₂ - emission standards**. Simultaneous implementation of these two measures should contribute in total to 3.85 PJ of energy savings in period 2010 – 2018 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b).

¹ <http://www.fiatsrbija.rs/> (04.08.2015.)

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.1.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

Introduction

Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy for the consumers connected to district heating system is policy instrument legally supported by Energy Law (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014a), Law on Efficient Use of Energy (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013a) and Methodology for determination of heat energy price (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015b). Horizontal measure with the same name was also proposed in the second EEAP (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b). Focus of this instrument is the supply of thermal energy and the target groups are district heating companies, as well as the consumers of their service. Objective of this policy instrument is the introduction of market principles in the operation of DH companies (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015a) and improvement of efficiency (including the energy efficiency) of production, distribution and supply of thermal energy in the DH systems.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Dominant, current practice in the most of Serbian DH systems is billing based to heated area (flat rate) (Econoler, 2012). Such practice makes operation of DH systems non-transparent. In such surrounding there is no motivation for consumers to save energy or to invest in energy efficiency improvement, as their bill is going to be the same anyway. On the other side, DH companies (mostly public) are not motivated to invest in more efficient production and distribution of energy, since they will be unable to transfer their costs and losses to end users.

By the Energy Law, DH systems are under the jurisdiction of local self-governments, and out of 57 municipalities with DH systems (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015a), billing based on consumption was introduced in just few of them², although the mandatory term for introduction of billing based to actual consumption of heat energy was six months after the adoption of Law on EUE.

The main reasons for this delay is the fact that due to transition to new billing method, roughly 30-40 % (CEDEF, 2015) of consumers would have to pay higher bills, because of poor insulation of their buildings. Therefore local authorities started to prepare social programs, which would last a few years, for these consumers. In this period, they should have the same billing method as before, but they also should invest in improving of energy efficiency of their facilities.

This instrument also requires some technical preparations to be performed before application. However, installing of new equipment for measuring and adjusting in substations, heat meters, heat cost allocators, valves and other equipment should be very attractive for many companies who

² <http://www.toplanasabac.rs/>, <http://www.nitoplana.co.rs/>

produce or sell equipment. The estimated value of these investments in Serbia is up to 200 million € (Grujic, 2008).

The main benefit of this instrument should have the consumers of heat energy, as they will be able to manage their own energy consumption and pay according to it. In the case of full implementation of energy efficiency their bills should be significantly less. In that case, due to less energy consumption in DH systems, even the import dependency of the state should be less, as imported natural gas is the main fuel used in DH systems (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2014).

Interaction between objectives

Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings is energy efficiency policy instrument created to ensure increase of quality of design, used materials and building technology in construction of new buildings and renovation of existing ones in order to achieve improvement in energy performance of the buildings. This instrument is compatible with **Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy for the consumers connected to district heating system**. Implemented together, these instruments lead to the reduction in energy consumption up to 25% in residential sector in Serbia (Jovanović Popović M. et al., 2012).

Some recent demo cases from Belgrade show that implementation of **Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy for the consumers connected to district heating system** enable some energy savings, while the level of savings depends of building characteristics (building envelope, internal installation, etc.). Although the costs in financial terms do not correspond linearly to energy consumption, experience from the same demo cases show that the costs of energy in the building with implemented **Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings** were 13% less than in the case of flat rate billing, while in the case of building that was not reconstructed the bill was 31% higher³.

Interaction between target groups

Users of buildings connected to DH system should benefit due to implementation of **Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings**, as thermal comfort in their buildings should be significantly improved, while the **Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy for the consumers connected to district heating system** gives them possibility to manage their consumption, as well as to reduce costs.

Installation of equipment for heat measuring and energy rehabilitation of buildings should be done by local companies, so the instruments should have positive impact to local economy.

As jointly implemented these instruments make the reduction of energy consumption, State's benefit is the reduction of imported fuel consumption.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

Application of **Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings** leads at the end to improving energy performance of buildings, which affects the "energy passport" of the building and increase of its market value. **Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy for the consumers connected to district heating system** has no direct influence to "energy passport", but implementation of this instrument and its benefits for end users, also increase market value of building.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

³<https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=0B5otVVm41sb5fjZHzy1IbDR4bXitS2NqWlByTOVPdDFxQWNFYzk0c0ZmMEEExTS00Z1g3LUE&usp=sharing> (31.07.2015.)

Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy for the consumers connected to district heating system, as a policy instrument is under the jurisdiction of local self-government (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014a). In the case of **Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings** implementation network consists of the Ministry for construction, transport and infrastructure that oversees and regulates the processes, and Chamber of Engineers which is in charge for training of energy auditors and organizations licensed for issuing energy certificates for buildings (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014b). According to the second EEAP (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b), it is necessary to strengthen further the capacity of both local administration and all other institutions involved in implementation and monitoring of these policy instruments.

Generally, there is no administrative burden for full implementation of these instruments. For **Billing based on actual (measured) consumption of thermal energy for the consumers connected to district heating system** local administration is obliged to adopt municipal decision about the introduction of the instrument and to provide all necessary regulations for its implementation (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014a).

Costs of implementation of proposed policy instruments are related to end-users. However, it is expected that the instruments will be implemented by means of loans extended by commercial banks at favorable repayment terms provided through the Budget Fund for Energy Efficiency or funds of the autonomous province or local self-government, and other favorable credit lines supported by international financial institutions or the commercial banks (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b).

1.1.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

Introduction

Introduction of electrical buses instead of diesel fueled buses in public transport in cities (City of Belgrade, 2015) is the policy instrument that should enable replacement of diesel buses by new electrical buses. It is related to public and private transport companies that provide service of passenger transport in the cities. So far, there are only individual cases of using electrical buses in Serbia.

The focus of this policy instrument is on substitution of using more expensive and imported diesel fuel with significantly cheaper and domestic electricity, in public transport. Initially, this policy instrument is envisaged for implementation in the city of Belgrade. According to the analysis and testing, done by the Belgrade Public transport enterprise in 2014, in Serbian conditions introduction of electrical buses in Belgrade theoretically should enable saving of up to 70% of diesel fuel and significant reduction of local pollution (Živanović et al, 2014).

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Effects of introduction electrical busses in the city public transport will have positive financial and environmental results due to low price of electricity in Serbia and no local pollution in final energy use. However, impact to overall energy efficiency should be further determined. Electricity production in Serbia is based on low caloric lignite (Jovančić et al. 2011) and thermal power plants which average efficiency is 35% (Statistical office of the Republic of Serbia, 2014). Also the, transport and distribution losses in electricity grid are significant - approx. 17% (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2014). On the other hand, positive impact to energy efficiency of proposed instrument has the share of renewable energy sources (mainly large hydro) in electricity production

in Serbia. This share is annual variable, and in 2010 it was 34.5% (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2015a), making overall efficiency of production approx. 43% (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia). According to National Renewable Energy Action Plan of the Republic of Serbia the share of renewables in gross final energy consumption will grow from 21% in 2010 to 27% in 2020, with the expected average share of renewable energy sources in the electricity production of 36.6% (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environmental Protection, 2013).

This is policy instrument which implementation delayed because the lack of financial resources. It is expected that the first – demo contingent will be used for demonstration of their efficiency.

Interaction between objectives

This policy instrument can be linked with the traffic-planning instrument **Traffic management system**. Traffic management system as policy instrument can be used in traffic control, incident management, travel demand management, operation and maintenance, environmental conditions monitoring, automated dynamic warning and enforcement and non-vehicular road user safety, so joint implementation of these two instruments should provide optimal routes for electric busses, green lines, etc. and maximize saving potential, but also verify environmental and financial results of this instrument.

Interaction between target groups

Traffic management system is targeting all transport modes and numerous different target groups. However, passengers in public transport, as well as public transport providers (public and commercial) are the common target groups. Passengers should benefit from using new, environmentally friendly busses in well-managed transport systems in the cities. The owners of transport enterprises (public and commercial) should realize significant savings because of lower operational costs and better-organized transport system.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

Introduction of electrical buses instead of diesel buses in public transport in cities should increase competitiveness of the bus market and potentially it could influence to **Fuel economy standards/vehicle CO₂ - emission standards** as regulatory instrument. Currently all new imported vehicles must be equipped with engines that meet at least Euro 5 standard (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b), while for the import of used vehicles minimum Euro 3 standard is required (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2010b). Wider implementation of electric buses should make **Fuel economy standards/vehicle CO₂ - emission standards** more restrictive.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

Road traffic safety Agency, Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure and Ministry of Interior are key players in proposed energy efficiency instruments in transport sector. According to Law on Communal Utility Activities (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2011a) passenger transport in the cities is under the jurisdiction of local self-government. According to the second EEAP (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b) it is necessary to strengthen further the capacity of both local administration and all other institutions involved in implementation and monitoring of these policy instruments. Although there is no visible administrative burden for the implementation of selected instruments, their implementation could be delayed due to different lists of priorities. High initial costs are the key financial problem for introduction of electrical buses.

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.2.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

Introduction

Introduction of green roofs and green walls is policy instrument that includes designing and building of roofs covered with vegetation, fully or partially. This is instrument of climate change policy, well recognizable as simultaneous action in adaptation and mitigation area. Legal bases for implementation of this policy instrument are strategic documents and law related to climate change issue (Government of the Republic of Serbia 2008, 2010a), (National Assembly of the Republic of Serbia, 2007). As a policy instrument, **Introduction of green roofs and green walls** is included in system of urban planning (Government of the Republic of Serbia 2014b).

Vegetation, which consists of trees or plants well adapted to the local weather conditions, is planted over a waterproof membrane. The growing medium may be sand, gravel or soil. The green roofs can range from the extensive green roofs, to the intensive green roofs with higher soil layer in order to include trees and shrubs, which means additional weight and lower slope. The intensive green roof requires more maintenance, while the extensive is self-sustaining with minimal maintenance. The green walls are vertical green spaces which are formed by planting plants that grow on facades or near the objects⁴.

In cities, the most suitable areas for building green roofs or walls are the central or urban areas, as well as new projected or existing buildings in commercial and industrial areas. The most suitable buildings for implementation of this measure are those with flat roof. Application of the measure in public buildings, with a large number of visitors, should raise awareness about the effects of it among the large number of people. According to results of Tabula project for Serbia, almost 30% of buildings in residential sector initially satisfy conditions for implementation of this policy instrument (Jovanović Popović et al. 2012).

This measure creates a better microclimate and reduces the heat island effect. That's why this instrument is a significant measure for climate changes adaptation. These oases of greenery, which are also places for rest and relaxation, reduce energy consumption and noise in buildings at the same time (City of Belgrade, 2015).

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Increasing of energy efficiency is usually stated as climate change mitigation measure (Ministry of Environment and Spatial Planning, 2010). In that sense, this policy instrument is connected to energy efficiency, although the adaptation and comfort themes (better microclimate, places for rest and relaxation, GHG reduction, noise reduction, etc.) are usually more dominant in its promotion. Green roofs and walls are good insulators, so they can significantly reduce heat losses in buildings. During summer, they reduce demands for cooling and electricity consumption and so additionally enhance living comfort in buildings.

It is shown that energy savings during the winter months could reach 5% (La Rochea, and Berard, 2014). For example, the main advantages of green roofs are decreasing of a building energy consumption by increasing insulation thickness of a roof, providing a natural shade against direct rays of the sun, thus decreasing temperature of inner and outer surfaces of the roof as well as decreasing

⁴ <http://www.knaufinsulation.rs/sites/rs.knaufinsulation.com/files/URBANSCAPE-Ravni-Krovovi-Brosura.pdf>

inside temperature of the building, and therefore optimizing a rate of energy consumption in a building Refahi, and Talkhabi, 2015). Reduction of daily temperature swing and reduction of the heat flow are also benefits of green architecture.

There are few examples of green roofs and walls built in Serbia⁵. But their number would be higher if some barriers were overcome. Main barriers to wider application are (Econoler, 2012):

- Many older buildings don't have a project for building permit which includes data on statics;
- Property relations are not completely solved in many public buildings;
- All owners of flats must be consistent with construction of green roofs or walls in residential buildings.

Additional measures that have to be applied in order to overcome mentioned barriers (City of Belgrade, 2015), are as follows:

- Forming the list of public buildings suitable for construction of green roofs or walls;
- Preparation of static calculation for the most suitable buildings;
- Facilitating and acceleration procedures for solving property relations;
- Raising awareness of residents regarding the benefits.

All residents/employees and visitors of buildings with green roofs/walls should benefit from the use of this instrument in the sense of indoor climate. The energy costs should be significantly lower for users/owners of buildings. Also, constructing companies, doing buildings' envelope improvement, should have additional field for work (UNDP, 2013).

Interaction between objectives

Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings and **Energy audit (mandatory)** are regulatory policy instruments aimed to reduce energy consumption in buildings. Introduction of green roofs or walls due to their insulating properties should contribute in achievement of energy performance requirements and have positive influence on results of energy audits.

Appropriate energy certificate and audit report that show the improvement of energy efficiency, have the positive influence to market price of building. Obviously, these instruments are compatible and have common objective, to reduce energy consumption in buildings.

Interaction between target groups

In residential buildings, construction of green roof or walls can be one technical measure for improvement energy performance of building related to heating under **Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings** instrument. All residents in residential buildings should benefit not just concerning heating (according to minimum energy performance requirements), but also concerning cooling and overall comfort. In public or commercial buildings where these instruments should be applied, the employees and visitors would be target groups. Both mentioned instruments provide lower energy costs and better indoor comfort, while the attractiveness of the object, also should be higher.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

Introduction of green roofs and green walls, as well as the application of **Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings** leads at the end to improving energy

⁵http://www.zinco-greenroof.com/EN/zinco_worldwide/export_details.php?id=Serbien%20%3Cbr%3EBosnien%20und%20Herzegovina%20%3Cbr%3EMontenegro

performance of buildings, which affects the energy class reported in “energy passport” of the building and increase its market value, both for selling or for renting.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

Implantation of green roofs and walls as a part of local spatial and urban plans is under the jurisdiction of local self-government (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014b). In the case of **Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings** implementation network consists of the Ministry for construction, transport and infrastructure that oversees and regulates the processes, and Chamber of Engineers which is in charge for training of energy auditors and organizations licensed for issuing energy certificates for buildings. According to the second EEAP (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b), it is necessary to strengthen further the capacity of both local administration and all other institutions involved in implementation and monitoring of these policy instruments.

Generally, there is no administrative burden for implementation of these instruments. For **Implantation of green roofs and walls** local administration is obliged to adopt municipal decision about the introduction of the instrument and to provide all necessary regulations for its implementation (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014b).

Costs of implementation of proposed policy instrument are related to investors in new or reconstructed buildings. Concerning positive impact to energy efficiency proposed instrument could be also appropriate for financing by means of loans extended by commercial banks at favorable repayment terms provided through the Budget Fund for Energy Efficiency funds or funds of the autonomous province or local self-government, and other favorable credit lines supported by international financial institutions or the commercial banks (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b).

1.2.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

Introduction

Subsidies for the purchasing of new vehicles and the replacement of old one (so called “old for new mechanism”) is the policy instrument that exist in Serbia, in different forms, for a while. The Government of Republic of Serbia passed in period 2010-2012 regulations on the conditions and manner of subsidized acquisition of vehicles (cars, trucks, and construction machineries) manufactured in the Republic of Serbia in accordance with the old-for-new policy. The purpose of this measure was stimulation and promotion of economic development of the country. The most significant results were achieved in passenger cars sector where regulation was formalized to encourage the replacement of old vehicles equipped with engines that do not meet even Euro 3 standard, with new domestic vehicles equipped with Euro 5 engines. The subsidy per vehicle varied in the range from 600 to 1,000 Euro (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2011b).

The Fund for Environmental Protection subsidized old for new mechanism as an instrument of environmental and climate change policy in period 2011-2012. In 2012, the Fund adopted a Decision on the awarding of grants to automotive companies aimed at encouraging the purchase of environmentally friendly vehicles, i.e. vehicles with CO₂ emissions below 100 g/km. The total value of funds available for this purpose amounted to 20,000,000 dinars (app. 200 thousands euro), or 100,000 dinars (app. 1,000 euro) per vehicle (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b).

Currently, this instrument is conducted by domestic manufacturer of cars (FCA Serbia)⁶. Each customer who purchases new car in this company is subsidized with 2,500 euro, if replace and recycle old car. The value of old car is also subtracted from the bill for new car, but the request is that the old vehicle is also manufactured in Serbia.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Primary motivation for introduction of this policy instrument was the support of Serbian automotive industry. This was especially supported by programs realized by Government of the Republic of Serbia, and in the current program of FCA Serbia. The program realized by the Fund for Environmental Protection insisted on reduction of emissions of pollutants (NO_x, CO, PM, etc.) and CO₂. Most of the old vehicles that were replaced had been manufactured before 1990 and had not met even Euro 3 standard. As CO₂ reduction can be achieved only if new vehicle consume less fuel than the old vehicle, it is clear that this instrument provides reduction of energy consumption and emission of CO₂ and other pollutants.

Energy efficiency potential of this instrument is recognized, and it is estimated that achieved shavings in period 2010 – 2012 were 0.00765 Mtoe (0.32 PJ), while the saving potential for period 2010-2018 amounts 0.034 Mtoe (1.42 PJ) (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b). However, for this achievement, besides voluntary approach of domestic car producers, the Government and the Ministry in charge of Economy need to continue to support this type of subsidization.

Users and/or purchasers of vehicles (both legal and natural persons) should have clear benefit (less fuel consumption and costs) of using more energy efficient cars.

Interaction between objectives

Although improvement of energy efficiency in transport sector was not primary motive for introduction of **Subsidies for the purchasing of new vehicles and the replacement of old one**, this instrument is compatible, and represents the support to proposed regulatory instrument - **Fuel economy standards/vehicle CO₂ - emission standards**.

Simultaneous implementation of these two measures should contribute in total to 3.85 PJ of energy savings in period 2010 – 2018 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b).

Interaction between target groups

Implementation of both instruments helps customers to purchase cheaper new vehicles. The vehicle producers, importers and dealers should have interest because implemented together these instruments raise demand for new vehicles. Finally, improved air quality saved energy resources and decreased import dependency are benefits for whole country and society.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

Both policy instruments are currently directed to Euro 5 standard, while in the near future introduction of Euro 6 standard is expected. In that sense, implementation of these instruments would have significant influence to Serbian new cars market.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

Implementation of **Fuel economy standards/vehicle CO₂ - emission standards** is responsibility of Road Traffic Safety Agency and the Ministry of Interior, while institutions in charge for monitoring are Road Traffic Safety Agency, Customs Administration and Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure, while the institution in charge of the implementation of **Subsidies for the purchasing of new vehicles and the replacement of old one were in the jurisdiction of Ministry in charge of**

⁶ [http://www.fiatsrbija.rs/\(04.08.2015.\)](http://www.fiatsrbija.rs/(04.08.2015.))

Economy (or currently, production/commercial company conducts it). Institutions in charge for monitoring are Ministry in charge of Economy and Customs Administration. These institutions are capable to design, support and ensure the implementation of the policy instruments, although administrative capacities must be strengthened (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b).

Concerning numerous institutions involved, the second EEAP (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b) emphasizes lack of inter-sectors communication and coordination during the policy implementation.

Lack of financial resources in Serbian budget stopped the realization of subsidies, and they are continued by commercial resources.

REFERENCES

- CEDEF Central European Development Forum (2015): Billing by Heat Consumption in Belgrade – Advantages and Challenges, Conference presentations, URL: <https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=0B5otVVm41sb5fjZHzy1IbDR4bXItS2NqWIByT0VPdDFxQWNFYzk0c0ZmMEExTS00Z1g3LUE&usp=sharing> (28.07.2015)
- City of Belgrade (2015), Climate Change Vulnerability Assessment and Adaptation Action Plan, URL: <http://www.beograd.rs/cms/view.php?id=1677444> (28.07.2015)
- Econoler, (2012), National Building Energy Efficiency Study for Serbia, Final Report
- Government of the Republic of Serbia (2008): National Sustainable Development Strategy of the Republic of Serbia, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No 57/2008, URL: <http://indicator.sepa.gov.rs/slike/pdf/o-indikatorima/nacionalna-strategija-odrzivog-razvoja-srbije>
- Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2010a), Strategy of Science and Technology Development in the Republic of Serbia for the period from 2010 up to 2015, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 13/2010, 2010, <http://mpn.gov.rs/dokumenta-i-propisi/podzakonski-propisi/nauka-i-tehnoloski-razvoj/94-strateski-i-programski-dokumenti> (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia (2011a): Law on Communal Utility Activities, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia", No. 88/2011, URL: http://www.paragraf.rs/propisi/zakon_o_komunalnim_delatnostima.html
- Government of the Republic of Serbia (2011b) Regulations on Conditions and Manner for Subsidized Purchasing of Cars Manufactured in the Republic of Serbia by Replacement Old for New in 2011, URL: http://www.podaci.net/_zakon/propis/Uredba_o_uslovima/U-unsska03v1101.htm (04.08.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia (2013a): Law on Efficient Use of Energy, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 25/2013, URL: http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/A_01_Zakon_o_efikasnom_koriscenju_energije.pdf
- Government of the Republic of Serbia (2013b): The Second Energy Efficiency Action Plan of the Republic of Serbia for the period from 2013 to 2015, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia", No. 98/2013, URL: http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/B_01_Drugi_akcioni_plan_za_energetsku_efikasnost_za_Republiku_Srbiju_za_peri_od_od_2013_do_2015_godine.pdf?uri=CELEX:32009L0028 (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia (2014a): Energy Law, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 145/2014, URL: <http://www.mre.gov.rs/dokumenta-efikasnost-izvori.php> (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2014b), Law on Construction and Planning, Official Gazette of RS, 72/2009, 132/2014, 145/2014, URL: http://paragraf.rs/propisi/zakon_o_planiranju_i_izgradnji.html (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia (2014b): Law on Planning and Construction, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 145/2014, URL: <http://www.mre.gov.rs/dokumenta-efikasnost-izvori.php> (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia (2015a): Draft of Strategy of energy sector development up to 2025, with projections to 2030, URL: http://www.parlament.gov.rs/upload/archive/files/lat/pdf/akta_procedura/2014/113-14Lat.pdf (28.07.2015)

- Government of the Republic of Serbia (2015b): Regulation on determination of methodology for determination of price for supply of end user by heat energy, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 64/2015, URL: http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/uredba_metodologija_toplotna_energija0138_cyr.pdf (28.07.2015)
- Grujic, M. (2008): Introduction of Heat Energy Measurement and Measurement Based Tariff in Belgrade – Through Regulations and Practice (in Serbian), KGH Conference Proceedings, Belgrade, 2008, 367-375.
- IEA (2014): Capturing the multiple benefits of energy efficiency. URL: <https://www.iea.org/Textbase/npsum/MultipleBenefits2014SUM.pdf> (2015-05-28)
- Jovančić, P., Tanasijević, M., Ivezić D. (2011): Serbian energy development based on lignite production, Energy Policy, 39 (3), 1191-1199
- Jovanović Popović M. et al. (2012): National Typology of Residential Buildings in Serbia, University of Belgrade - Faculty of Architecture, GIZ - Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit, Belgrade.
- La Rochea, P., Berard, U., (2014): Comfort and energy savings with active green roofs, Energy and Buildings, Vol. 82, pp 492–504
- Ministry of Energy, Development and Environmental Protection (2013): National Action Plan for Renewable Energy Sources Use in the Republic of Serbia, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 53/2013, URL: <http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/02%20Nacionalni%20akcioni%20plan%20za%20koriscenje%20obnovljivih%20izvora%20energije%20u%20Republici%20Srbiji1.pdf> (28.07.2015)
- Ministry of Environment and Spatial Planning, (2010): Initial National Communication of the Republic of Serbia under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, URL: <http://unfccc.int/resource/docs/natc/srbnc1.pdf> (28.07.2015)
- National Assembly of the Republic of Serbia, (2007), Law on Ratification of the Kyoto Protocol to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, Official Gazette of the RS - International agreements, No. 88/2007, URL: <http://www.aarhussu.rs/docs/usvojeni-propisi/zakoni/Zakon-o-potvrdivanju-kjoto-protokola-uz-okvirnu-konvenciju-un-o-promeni-klime.pdf> (28.07.2015)
- Refahi, A.H., Talkhabi, H., (2015): Investigating the effective factors on the reduction of energy consumption in residential buildings with green roofs, Renewable Energy, Vol. 80, pp 595-603,
- Statistical Office of the Republic Serbia, (2014): Energy Balances for 2013, <http://webzrs.stat.gov.rs/WebSite/userFiles/file/Energetika/2014-10-06/Ukupan%20energetski%20bilans,%202013.pdf> (04.08.2015) (30.07.2015)
- UNDP (2013): Green Economy, Scoping Study: Serbia URL: http://www.unep.org/greeneconomy/Portals/88/Research%20Products/Serbia_GESS.pdf (30.07.2015)
- Živanović, Z., Mišanović, S. (2014) Fully electric buses are promising technology in the future, Mobility and Vehicle Mechanics, Volume 40, Number 2, 2014, 65-99. <http://oaji.net/articles/2014/766-1420109831.pdf>

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.3

**INTERLINKAGE AND SYNERGIES BETWEEN
SELECTED OTHER POLICY AREAS AND ENERGY
EFFICIENCY – NATIONAL REPORT FOR UK
DATE 07 AUGUST 2015**

Partner: “Oxford Brookes University”

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: Oxford Brookes University, UK

Steering Committee member ⁽¹⁾: Prof Rajat Gupta

Prepared by: Prof Rajat Gupta, Laura Barnfield, Mariam Kapsali, Matt Gregg, , Low Carbon Building Group, Oxford Institute for Sustainable Development, Oxford Brookes University, UK

⁽¹⁾ The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS **4**

ACRONYMS **5**

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY **7**

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS **8**

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY **10**

 1.1.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR: THE GREEN DEAL PROGRAMME 10

 1.1.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR: THE RENEWABLE FUEL OBLIGATION..... 14

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY **17**

 1.2.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR: DECENT HOMES PROGRAMME 17

 1.2.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR: CONGESTION CHARGES..... 20

REFERENCES..... **23**

Table of Figures

No table of figures entries found.

Table of Tables

No table of figures entries found.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

ACRONYMS

ALMO	Arms Length Management Organisation
ASA	Advertising Standards Authority
CC	Congestion Charge
CERO	Carbon Emissions Reduction Obligation
CO₂	Carbon Dioxide
CO₂e	Carbon Dioxide equivalent
DCLG	Department for Communities and Local Government
DECC	Department of Energy and Climate Change
DfT	Department for Transport
DH	Decent Homes
DHS	Decent Homes Standard
DWP	Department for Work and Pensions
ECO	Energy Companies Obligation
EU	European Union
GD	Green Deal
GDC	Green Deal Cashback
GDFC	Green Deal Finance Company
GDHIF	Green Deal home Improvement Fund
GD ORB	Green Deal Oversight and Registration Body
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GLA	Greater London Authority
HCA	Homes and Communities Agency
HHSRS	Housing Health and Safety Rating System
HIA	Home Improvement Agencies
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
ILUC	Indirect Land Use Change
LA	Local Authority
LEZ	Low Emissions Zone
NRMM	Non-road mobile machinery
MTS	Mayor's Transport Strategy
PCN	Penalty Charge Notice

PFI	Private Finance Initiative
RED	EU Renewable Energy Directive 2009/28/EC
RHI	Renewable Heat Incentive
RSL	Registered Social Landlord
RTFCs	Renewable Transport Fuel Certificates
RTFO	Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation
SAP	Standard Assessment Procedure
TfL	Transport for London
UCO	Used Cooking Oil
UK	United Kingdom
ULED	Ultra Low Emission Discount
ULEVs	Ultra Low Emissions Vehicles
VAT	Value-added Tax
VED	Vehicle Excise Duty
VRN	Vehicle Registration Number

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In current debates the multiple benefits of energy efficiency are broadly discussed and available analyses are growing in number (e.g. IEA 2014 report on multiple benefits). However, in some cases energy savings can rather be seen as the co-benefit of other policies or measures, which do not target energy efficiency by design.

This report outlines four cases studies; two policy instruments targeting the buildings sector and two policy instruments targeting the transport sector. They include two (one building and one transport) policy instruments that have a direct link to energy; the Green Deal Programme and the Renewable Fuels Obligation, and two policy instruments that have an indirect link to energy; the Decent Homes Programme and Congestion Charges.

Each policy instrument is described in terms of its focus, target groups and objectives, its relationship with energy efficiency, as well as the interactions between the rules-influencing mechanisms, and the policy instruments implementation network/governance structures.

CHAPTER 1: ACHIEVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY THROUGH INTEGRATION IN OTHER POLICY AREAS

In current debates the multiple benefits of energy efficiency are broadly discussed and available analyses are growing in number (e.g. IEA 2014 report on multiple benefits). However, in some cases energy savings can rather be seen as the co-benefit of other policies or measures, which do not target energy efficiency by design.

The aim of this task is to identify policy areas suitable for combination with energy efficiency policies and systematically analyse how they may contribute to improve energy efficiency, particularly if untapped energy saving potentials still exist.

Within UK policy, there are many overlaps within policy instruments and measures between energy efficiency and renewable generation as well as more socio-economic and environmental issues, such as fuel poverty, physical and mental health, and air quality.

Official documents that describe such interlinkages between policy instruments include:

- Department of Energy and Climate Change (2012). The Energy Efficiency Strategy: The Energy Efficiency Opportunity in the UK. London: DECC. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/65603/6928-the-energy-efficiency-strategy-statistical-strat.pdf
- Department of Energy and Climate Change (2011). UK Renewable Energy Roadmap. London: DECC. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/48128/2167-uk-renewable-energy-roadmap.pdf
- HM Government (2015). Cutting the cost of keeping warm – a fuel poverty strategy for England. London: HM Government. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/408644/cutting_the_cost_of_keeping_warm.pdf
- Energy and Climate Change Committee (ECCC) (2014). The Green Deal: watching brief (part 2). Third Report of Session 2014-15. In: Commons, H. o. (ed.). Available: <http://www.publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201415/cmselect/cmenergy/348/348.pdf>
- Environment, Food and Rural Affairs Committee (EFRAC) (2008). Energy efficiency and fuel poverty. Third report of session 2008-09. In: Commons, H.o. (ed.). Available: <http://www.publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm200809/cmselect/cmenvfru/37/37.pdf>
- HM Government (2011). Creating growth, cutting carbon: making sustainable local transport happen. London: HM Government. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/3890/making-sustainable-local-transport-happen-whitepaper.pdf

This is not an exhaustive list, as much of the UK's policy strategy acknowledges the interlinkages between energy efficiency and other policy areas, but does not always explicitly mention and evaluate the links. Policy Connect (www.policyconnect.org.uk) also provides useful documentation

on the UK's policy and recommendations from a network of Parliamentary groups, research commissions, forums and campaigns working to inform and improve UK public policy.

It must be noted that in May 2015, the UK Government changed and much of the policies relating to energy efficiency and other policy areas are undergoing review.

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH A DIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.1.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR: THE GREEN DEAL PROGRAMME

Introduction

The Green Deal programme was launched in January 2013, alongside the regulatory policy instrument, the Energy Company Obligation (ECO), and was expected to be a 20-year programme to reduce consumer bills, whilst carbon savings continued to be delivered. The Green Deal was both an economic (loan system) and dissemination and awareness policy instrument. Its design was a process of assessment (Green Deal advice report) and financial incentives to ensure low or no upfront costs for the installation of energy efficiency measures. The financial mechanisms in place, as part of the Green Deal programme, included an upfront loan (through Green Deal Finance Company (GDFC)), that was paid back through the consumers energy bills or one-off incentive payments (Green Deal Cashback (GDC) or Green Deal Home Improvement Fund (GDHIF) payment). It also aimed to provide and build a framework of 'trusted' and accredited market participants in the energy efficiency market.

The Green Deal supported consumers (domestic and non-domestic) to install a variety of suitable energy efficiency measures including: insulation (loft, cavity or solid wall), draught-proofing, improved heating controls, improved glazing, and renewable energy technologies (heat and generation) (DECC, 2014). Its focus was on raising consumer awareness and implementation of energy efficiency measures within existing buildings (domestic and non-domestic); with the target groups being mainly households (private rented as well as owner occupied), alongside small businesses. It also aimed to shift Government-led energy efficiency schemes from supplier obligations to an integration of a competitive market-based mechanism; thus improving the energy efficiency market in the UK (ECCC, 2014).

The main objectives of the Green Deal (alongside the Energy Company Obligation (ECO)) were (ECCC, 2014) to:

- Reduce UK's Greenhouse Gas emissions;
- Address the drivers of fuel poverty;
- Maintain the security of the UK's energy supply;
- Address market failures and barriers, and drive demand for cost-effective energy efficiency measures.

The estimated energy saving (dwelling and non-dwelling) from the Green Deal programme was expected to be 0.7 TWh by 2015 (DECC, 2014); with around 230,000 low-income households benefiting from heating and insulation measures each year. By 2020 the Green Deal and ECO are expected to reduce UK household and business carbon emissions by 4.5 million tonnes per year (DCLG, 2015b).

It must be noted that as of July 2015, the UK Government has stopped funding for the Green Deal Finance Company, effectively rendering an end to the Green Deal programme as it stood.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

In March 2013, the then Minister of State for Energy and Climate Change anticipated that at least 10,000 households would have signed up to Green Deal Plans by the end of the year (Pitt, 2014). However, the House of Commons Energy and Climate Change Committee's Third Report of Session 2014-15 on the Green Deal (ECCC, 2014), stated that only approximately 4,000 plans had been (or were in the process of being) set up at the time of the report's writing. The Report also highlighted the fact that the estimated carbon savings through the Green Deal programme was minimal; 0.04MtCO₂ through Green Deal finance and 0.07MtCO₂ through the Cashback scheme (ECCC, 2014).

At the end of 2013, it was estimated (CCC, 2014) that 4.5million cavity walls, 7million solid walls and 9million lofts remained uninsulated to adequate standards (with an estimated carbon saving potential of 2MtCO₂, 5MtCO₂, and 0.7MtCO₂ respectively). The Green Deal has enabled 44,106 individual energy efficiency measures, across 35,278 individual households from its inception in January 2013 to January 2015; of which 693 were cavity wall insulation, 16,930 were solid wall insulation and 1,733 were loft insulation. Such figures demonstrate the failures of the Green Deal programme, as a financial mechanism. In terms of assessment, over the same period, 501,906 Green Deal assessments were undertaken (DECC, 2015a).

The barriers hindering the success of the Green Deal were outlined in the House of Commons Third Report of Session 2014-15 (ECCC, 2014); a) financial barriers, b) communication and trust barriers, and c) behavioural barriers. These barriers have meant that it has been slow to attract uptake; with consumers able to find cheaper and more straightforward finance mechanisms elsewhere, and the confusing and complex communication strategy and process, alongside incidences of rogue traders has put off many potential households (low-middle income), and market investors. The Green Deal Finance Company credit threshold enabled 80% of the population to access loans, however, due to the 'Golden Rule', and the high interest rates, often the installation of higher cost measures was prevented, particularly in low-income households. Changes in the ECO in terms of enabling low-cost measures to be installed, for free through ECO, has also helped undermine the Green Deal programme and its uptake by 'able-to-afford' households (ECCC, 2014). In addition, reports from Green Deal providers indicate that consumers are put off by the need to pay for the initial assessment, and do not see it as worthwhile (ECCC, 2014).

There have also been suggestions that, although the available funding for incentives such as the Cashback scheme was used in a shorter period of time than expected, it had not encouraged wider take-up; rather it was used to replace boilers and other energy efficiency measures that would have happened anyway. The Green Deal Home Improvement Fund was also popular, and was positive in the fact that it highlighted that there was an appetite for energy efficiency measures. However, its sudden and unexpected closure has not helped build confidence in both the consumer and wider energy efficiency market (ECCC, 2014). It has also been found that potential consumers in rural areas have found it difficult to access Green Deal providers, which again has significantly hindered uptake by households that would be target groups.

Interaction between objectives

The Green Deal programme has common objectives with several other energy efficiency policy measures including; the Energy Company Obligation (ECO), the Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI). ECO and the Green Deal were to be complementary mechanisms that were implemented alongside each other; with the same objectives. Whilst the ECO was aimed at ensuring suppliers install more costly energy efficiency measures such as solid wall and hard-to-treat cavity wall insulation, the Green Deal was aimed at facilitating the installation of low-cost measures (using the Golden Rule; "the expected

financial savings from installing energy efficiency measures must be equal to or greater than the cost attached to the energy bill” (ECCC, 2014)).

However, as noted above, changes in the ECO programme operation appear to have been counter-productive in terms of the common objective of encouraging uptake of energy efficiency measures. This has been due to the allowance of loft and cavity wall insulation (relatively low-cost measures) to be installed under the ECO’s Carbon Emissions Reduction Obligation (CERO); which has the potential to undermine the Green Deal in which the Golden Rule prevents the installation of high-cost energy efficiency measures (ECCC, 2014).

The Green Deal and the Domestic Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI) also have several common objectives, namely again, at the encouragement of uptake and the reduction of market barriers. In order to be eligible for the Domestic RHI, a household must undergo a Green Deal Assessment. Whilst this makes practical sense (ensure the building has sufficient physical energy efficiency measures prior to the installation of heating systems), the additional cost and administration of the Assessment could lead to reductions in uptake; indeed in February 2015 the DECC removed the obligation of Social Landlords to undertake a Green Deal Assessment prior to application for the RHI (DECC, 2015b).

Interaction between target groups

The building sector is a key area of focus in terms of both carbon reductions and improved energy efficiency. Within the building sector, households are seen as critical to these two goals; therefore common target groups exist between the Green Deal and many other policy instruments and measures; including financial instruments such as the RHI, the Warm Front Scheme, Home Energy Efficiency Programmes (Scotland) but also broader regulatory instruments including the ECO, the Energy Act 2011, and the Decent Homes Standard.

These target groups include; households in fuel poverty, the private rented sector (landlords and tenants), social rented households and owner-occupied households. An example is of the Energy Act 2011 ensuring regulation that addressed energy efficiency in the private rented sector; through empowering tenants in requesting energy efficiency measures, and introducing minimum energy efficiency standards for domestic dwellings. The Green Deal has complemented these regulations by providing financial incentives for both the landlord and tenant, and reducing the potential for net or upfront costs to be incurred by either party (ECCC, 2014).

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

The Green Deal is an economic mechanism to encourage and enable take-up of energy efficiency measures. Participation from the consumer is voluntary, however, GD providers require certification and must abide by the GD Code of Practice (further described in following section).

Despite this, an example of where the Green Deal interacts with both regulatory and other economic policy instruments is in relation to the private rented sector. Domestic private landlords will not be able to unreasonably refuse requests for consent to energy efficiency improvements from their tenants, where financial support is available, such as Green Deal finance or ECO, with the first tenants’ energy efficiency improvements regulations coming into force by 1 April 2016 (DECC, 2015c). Because it is the bill payer in rented dwellings that benefits from EE improvements, the Landlords Energy Saving Allowance, a financial incentive, allows landlords of domestic rented property to claim tax relief of up to £1,500 per property for the costs of buying and installing energy-saving products (DECC, 2014). The Green Deal was expected to work alongside the vast majority of existing energy efficiency policy instruments and measures to ensure growth in a sustained energy

efficiency market. However, due to the low uptake of GD Plans and unsurety around the funding and security of financial incentives such as the GDHIF, GDC and FiTs, it does not appear to have made the same impact as expected, or desired on the energy efficiency market.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

The Green Deal Oversight and Registration Body (GD ORB), on behalf of the Secretary of State, manages the authorisation scheme for participants in the Green Deal and is responsible for a number of functions aimed at providing effective administration and oversight of the scheme. The GD ORB is responsible for maintaining a register of all authorised Green Deal Providers, Certification Bodies, Assessors and Installers; maintaining the Green Deal Code of Practice and controlling the use of the Quality Mark; ongoing monitoring of Green Deal Participants against the Code of Practice; producing an annual Green Deal report; and gathering evidence of non-compliance and referring participants to the Ombudsman or the Secretary of State where appropriate and imposing sanctions when directed (DCLG, 2015b). The Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC) is the Government body that oversees the implementation of the Green Deal, alongside several other energy-related policy instruments and measures such as the ECO, RHI, Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs).

As a UK Government-led policy mechanism, the Green Deal is subject to an Impact Assessment prior to its implementation in order to ensure satisfactory networks, structures and capacity are in place to ensure its successful delivery. In relation to the Green Deal, much has been written in terms of its failures to meet expectations. In part, this appears to be due to issues within its implementation network and governance structures; particularly in terms of the promotion of the Green Deal to consumers (ECCC, 2014). In terms of capacity, the Green Deal has suffered from a lack of suitable providers and assessors; particularly in rural areas (ECCC, 2014). In addition, the complexities, administrative burden and lack of clarity throughout the supply chain of the Green Deal programme appears to have also affected its success significantly (ECCC, 2014); with rogue traders operating due to a lack of clear branding, and suitable certification mechanisms. This has led to a lack of consumer confidence in the implementation network itself. This has not been helped by Government communications on the Green Deal being found to have mis-sold Green Deal advertisement by the Advertising Standards Authority (ASA) (ASA, 2014). The Green Deal also suffers from a lack of framework that outlines specific targets in terms of delivery and/or carbon reductions (UKGBC, 2014).

In terms of financial feasibility, it is apparent that the investment provided was inadequate; the allocated £120million first release budget for the Green Deal Home Improvement Fund was taken in under seven weeks (ECCC, 2014). Whilst this has been support by a second and third release of funds, the messages around the sustainability of the funds have been unclear, which has the potential for undermining confidence in the Government's ability to ensure the sustainability and consistency of its energy efficiency policies, which, in turn, has negative implications upon sustained growth within the UK's energy efficiency market and supply chain. In July 2015, the UK Government also stopped funding of the Green Deal Finance Company (GDFC, 2015), and although the Green Deal Assessment framework remains open, this is likely to further strain the implementation network of energy efficiency measures within the existing domestic building sector.

1.1.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR: THE RENEWABLE FUEL OBLIGATION

Introduction

The Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (Amendment) Order 2013 (RTFO) first came into legislation in 2007, and was subsequently amended in December 2011 to “transport the transport elements of the EU Renewable Energy Directive (RED) 2009/28/EC” (DfT, 2012), and then further amended in 2013 to “implement the closely related requirements of articles 7a-e of the EU Fuel Quality Directive 2009/30/EC” (DfT, 2012).

The RTFO supports the government’s policy on reducing greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) from vehicles by encouraging the production of biofuels that don’t damage the environment. Under the RTFO, suppliers of transport and non-road mobile machinery (NRMM) fuel in the UK must be able to show that a percentage of the fuel they supply comes from renewable and sustainable sources (DfT, 2012). The RTFO targets fuel suppliers (both suppliers of biofuels and fossil fuels) who supply at least 450,000 litres of fuel a year.

The objectives of the RTFO are:

- Driving a market for biofuels in the UK;
- Reduction in transport-related GHG emissions (estimated savings of 4.3MtCO₂e per annum in 2020 (DfT, 2013));
- Mandatory target of a minimum 10 % share of biofuels in transport petrol and diesel consumption by 2020 (as per the EU Renewable Energy Directive (RED) 2009/28/EC);
- Incentivise the supply of non-crop biofuels by ‘double-counting’ biofuels derived from waste and residues (DfT, 2013).

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Under the RTFO, the average GHG saving from the biofuels was 69% in 2013-2014, compared to fossil fuels, which represents a total saving of almost 2.8MtCO₂e (DfT, 2015). As of 2013-2014, the RTFO is generally meeting its objective of reducing carbon emissions from road transport, and increasing energy efficiency within the transport sector; overall savings have been lower than in the original impact assessment, but this has been attributed mainly to the reduction in RTFO targets due to concerns about ‘indirect land use change’¹ (ILUC). Revisions to the 2007 Order in 2011 ensured that renewable fuels passed greater sustainability criteria, incentivise the supply of non-crop biofuels (by ‘double-counting’ biofuels derived from waste and residues) and that not only suppliers of road transport fuel were covered, but also suppliers of fuel for use in NRMM (DfT, 2013). This in turn meant that in 2013, an amendment to the ‘specified amount’ in article 4 of the RTFO was made to slightly lower the obligation level “from 5.2632%” to “4.9870%”; to ensure the overall amount of biofuel supplied in the UK for transport remained the same, despite the expansion in scope.

¹ “When an existing crop is displaced to enable a biofuel crop to be grown, additional agricultural land may be created to accommodate the displaced crop. If ILUC occurs, there is a risk that there will be a loss of carbon stock from that land and therefore additional carbon emissions.” DfT (2015). Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation. Annual Report 2013-14 *In: Transport, D. f. (ed.)*. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/415132/cm-9026_accessible.pdf

The 2014 Post Implementation Review Impact Assessment (DfT, 2014) indicates that RTFO targets need to be substantially increased in order to meet the EU's 2020 renewable energy and carbon targets. In terms of improvements, larger industry actors have called for a set target supply trajectory towards the Renewable Energy Directive's (RED) of 10% in 2010 in order to provide greater certainty within the wider industry, and smaller producers have called for a wider variety of measures to enhance support for the UK's Used Cooking Oil (UCO) supply (DfT, 2014).

Interaction between objectives

The RTFO shares common objectives, in terms of driving a market for biofuels in the UK with the Energy Act 2004 (Part 2, Chapter 5 outlines), The Climate Change Act 2008, The Biodiesel Duty Regulations 2010, HM Revenue and Customs note on the extension of the duty differential for biodiesel from used cooking oil, the Biodiesel and Bioblend Regulations 2002 and the Hydrocarbon Oil Duties Act 1979 (DfT et al., 2015). It is the UK's mechanism of implementing the EU's Biofuel Directive (2003/30/EC), and its subsequent amendments were brought about in order to incorporate and address the quantitative objectives of the EU-wide Renewable Energy Directive (2009/28/EC).

The RTFO also has an important interlink with the UK's policy instruments and measures surrounding ultra-low emission vehicles (ULEVs) in terms of both reducing transport-related GHG emissions, but also driving a market for biofuels in the UK; developments in ULEVs need to support and promote the uptake of biofuels through the production and development of technology suitable to using biofuels.

Interaction between target groups

The RTFO's target groups are generally all encompassing; both suppliers of road and NRMM fuel are targeted. Other UK transport policy instruments and measures do not directly target the same groups; instead most focus on the users of transport, rather than the suppliers.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

The RTFO's rules and influencing mechanisms are largely self-sustained, as it operates through tradable Renewable Transport Fuels Certificates (RTFCs) (DfT, 2015). As the Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation Annual Report 2013-14 states:

"The RTFO operates on an annual basis starting each year on 15 April. Each supplier of fuel to the UK market is required to demonstrate that biofuel has been supplied to cover a set proportion of their overall fuel supply. For the 2013-14 year, this proportion was 4.75%. Suppliers can meet this obligation by redeeming certificates that they have received for their own biofuel supply, or by redeeming certificates that they have bought from other suppliers of biofuel. Suppliers also have the option to buy-out of their obligation, paying 30 pence per litre of biofuel for which they have not redeemed an RTFC. This protects consumers from excessive increases in fuel prices by setting a maximum value for RTFCs. Any money received from suppliers buying out is distributed between suppliers who have redeemed RTFCs and those who have chosen to surrender additional RTFCs for this purpose. Fuel suppliers can meet up to 25% of their obligation with certificates issued in the previous year. This reduces the impact of unexpected events and provides some protection against year to year volatility of fuel prices."

The Administrator of the RTFO, the Department for Transport (DfT), is responsible for the operations and processes of the RTFC.

In terms of the RTFO's effect on the market, the additional costs of biofuel supply were not felt until 2012-13 due to the 20ppl fuel duty incentive for biofuels. In 2013-13, the true petrol equivalent per

litre basis (0.81p incl. VAT) reflected the actual additional cost experienced by motorists, and was the equivalent to only 0.6% of the average retail price of fuel; for an average car, this was the equivalent to approximately an £8 (plus VAT) increase in the annual fuel bill (DfT, 2013). In terms of sustaining the use and supply of biofuels, without Government mechanisms such as the RTFO, the quantity of biofuel supplied is expected to fall due to the fact that on a per unit basis, sustainable biofuels remain more expensive than fossil fuels (DfT, 2014).

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

Registration and compliance is managed by the RTFO Compliance Team in the DfT; it operates systems and processes designed to prevent and detect fraudulent applications, and also has the powers to impose civil penalties if requirements of the RTFO are not complied with (DfT, 2015). The fuel suppliers are responsible for contacting and registering with the RTFO Compliance Team. The Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation: Post Implementation Review Impact Assessment 2014 (DfT, 2014) acknowledges that the regulatory framework of the RTFO has become more complex overtime, and that legislative proposals under discussion at European level to address ILUC sustainability concerns may add further complexity to the regulatory framework.

In terms of financial feasibility, the RTFO represented a net cost to society; the costs (£2,215million) are estimated to outweigh the benefits (£301million) by £1,914million over the first five years of the scheme (DfT, 2014). Despite this, Government administration costs reduced in 2012-13 (Year five), despite the fact that costs were anticipated to increase following the 2011 amendments. The administration costs for the fuel suppliers is estimated to be around £0.5million for each large obligated company; including the costs of reporting, trading, verification, policy, audit, marketing, general management and technical issues (DfT, 2014).

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS WITH AN INDIRECT LINK TO ENERGY

1.2.1 CASE STUDY FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR: DECENT HOMES PROGRAMME

Introduction

The Decent Homes Standard (DHS) was a technical standard for social housing introduced by the UK Government in 2000, and set a target to 'ensure that all social housing meets set standards of decency by 2010' (UK Parliament, 2010), and was implemented through the Decent Homes Programme. A further target was set in 2002 of 70% of vulnerable household in the private sector should be in decent housing by the same date (National Audit Office, 2010). In 2006, the standard was further updated in line with the Housing Act 2004 (DCLG, 2006), which included the more demanding risk assessment procedure, the Housing Health and Safety Rating System (HHSRS). The decent home standard is not an enforcement standard, and authorities do not have powers to require owners to comply (ODPM, 2004).

In 2001, 39% of all social housing was classified as 'non-decent'; 1.6million homes (National Audit Office, 2010), and there was an estimated 1.2-1.4million private sector vulnerable households living in homes classified as 'non-decent'. The HHSRS increased the number of households classified as living in 'non-decent' homes; the percentage of vulnerable households in the private sector in decent homes dropped from 68% in 2006 to 61% in 2007 (National Audit Office, 2010). Of the 1.2 million 'non-decent' homes in the private sector in 2001, 700,000 failed solely on the provision of thermal comfort criterion.

The minimum standards stated that a decent home should (DCLG, 2006):

- Meet the current statutory minimum standard for housing (contains one or fewer hazards assessed as serious ('Category 1') under the Housing Health Safety Rating System (HHSRS));
- Be in a reasonable state of repair;
- Have reasonably modern facilities and services;
- Provide a reasonable degree of thermal comfort.

The Decent Homes Programme has continued since 2010, through the provision of Government funding and the 2010 to 2015 Government's policy relating to the rented housing sector.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

One of the four minimum standards outlined within the Decent Homes programme is that a decent home should 'provide a reasonable degree of thermal comfort'. Therefore, improving the energy efficiency of the dwelling is considered indirectly through the Decent Homes programme. Although actual energy saving figures due to the Decent Homes programme are unknown, the programme has had relative success in bringing a vast number of homes up to the Decent Homes Standard; with approximately 85% of social rented homes (total number of social rented homes in 2013 was approximately 3.9million), and 71% of homes in the private rented sector (total number of private rented homes in 2013 was 4.4million) meeting the standard in 2013 (DCLG, 2015a).

In terms of additional measures necessary in order to address energy efficiency improvements within the Decent Homes (DH) programme, research (Darby, 2005) suggests that whilst the DH programme

has done more to improve thermal comfort than other mechanisms, the thermal comfort measures in the DHS are generally relatively low; for example, the minimum acceptable loft insulation is 50mm (in dwellings with gas/oil programmable heating) but the recommended levels for acceptable energy efficiency levels is 270mm. Furthermore, the fact that a SAP (2005) rating of only 35 is indicative of a Category 1 risk in the HHSRS, and therefore a potential failure in terms of the DHS, highlights the fact that the DHS includes minimum standards only, and does not aim to significantly increase energy efficiency in homes or push for higher standards (as required if national carbon reduction and energy efficiency targets are to be achieved). A further barrier to the DH programme addressing energy efficiency measures in more depth is that it is “a standard that triggers action, not one to which work is necessarily carried out” (DCLG, 2006).

Whilst non-decent homes were spread fairly evenly amongst the sub-groups of the population in the social rented sector, in the private rented sector, non-decent homes were more likely to be accommodating unemployed households, low income households, older renters, those living alone and/or those who have been resident for ten years or more (DCLG, 2015a).

Interaction between objectives

The Decent Homes programme, and standard have similar objectives to UK fuel poverty policy instruments, such as the Fuel Poverty Strategy, as required under the Warm Homes and Energy Conservation Act 2000; in terms of targeting vulnerable households and ensuring adequate levels of thermal comfort. Whilst the DHS only provides minimum standards, the Fuel Poverty Strategy builds on criticisms of the DHS in terms of providing specific SAP-based targets to raise homes in the UK out of fuel poverty. Cross-links between the two policy instruments include the reference to national and local fuel poverty financial schemes such as Affordable Warmth within the DHS.

Interaction between target groups

The Decent Homes programme and standard specifically target vulnerable households; including unemployed households, low income households, older renters, those living alone and/or those who have been resident for ten years or more. Much of the UK’s energy efficiency policy instruments also target vulnerable households, including the Green Deal as well as fuel poverty-related financial and regulatory policy instruments.

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

The DHS is not an enforcement standard, and authorities do not have powers to require owners to comply (ODPM, 2004). However, the DHS is based primarily on the HHSRS, which is a regulation (SI 2005 No.3208) and enforcement powers are given to local housing authorities in terms of assessing and acting upon housing fitness within their area by the Housing Act 2004. The Warm Homes and Energy Conservation Act 2000 also sets legislative powers in relation to improving the quality of homes in the UK.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

The Decent Homes programme is overseen by the Department for Communities and Local Government (DCLG) and run, on behalf of the DCLG, by the Homes and Communities Agency (HCA), an executive non-departmental public body (except in London, where decisions are made by the Mayor) (DCLG and HCA, 2015). In terms of implementation, the local authorities (LAs) are responsible for their administrative areas. Where local authorities require additional resources in order to

implement the programme, three options for the future management of the stock are available (National Audit Office, 2010):

- An Arms Length Management Organisation (ALMO); a company set up by the LA to manage and improve the housing stock. The housing stock remains in the ownership of the LA but the ALMO takes day-to-day responsibility.
- A Private Finance Initiative (PFI) provider; public sector enters into a long-term contractual with a private sector company to design, build, finance and operate an asset.
- Transfer of stock to an RSL following a tenant ballot.

In terms of the implementation of the Decent Homes programme in the private sector, Home Improvement Agencies (HIAs) are seen as having an important delivery role; they cover approximately 80% of the LAs in the UK and assess the needs of elderly, disabled and vulnerable people living independently. In addition, the reliance on enforcement action alone is not felt to be adequate in terms of ensuring the private sector meets the DHS; as such LAs often work with partner agencies. Despite the many stakeholders within the implementation network, an evaluation of the DH programme suggests that it has actually improved asset management processes, and many RSLs have improved their purchasing efficiency and economies by using procurement consortia (National Audit Office, 2010).

From 2011-2015, the Government provided £1.6billion to the DH programme, with a further £160million having been allocated for 2015-16 (DCLG and HCA, 2015). In terms of financial feasibility, it is difficult to assess the actual costs of the Decent Homes programme as much of the funding used to implement the DHS was through a variety of channels, including the LAs Major Repairs Allowance and the Regional Housing Pot (National Audit Office, 2010). In addition, many of the improvements within homes owned and maintained by RSLs are done at no direct cost to the taxpayer. This was due to the DCLG enabling, through the regulatory system, RSLs to implement the DHS at their own expense, even though it is not a statutory requirement (National Audit Office, 2010). However, the improvements in RSL purchasing efficiencies due to the DH programme is estimated to have potential savings of up to £590million within this sector.

At Government level, there is little direct overlap between the department responsible for the Decent Homes programme, and the department responsible for most household energy-related policy; the Department for Energy and Climate Change (DECC). However, at local level, whilst the LAs are mainly responsible for the actual implementation of the DH programme, partnerships with local third sector organisations are often required for the actual delivery. Such organisations can often play an interlinking role in terms of the practical roll-out of domestic energy efficiency financial incentive schemes.

1.2.2 CASE STUDY FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR: CONGESTION CHARGES

Introduction

The Congestion Charge (CC) in London was first introduced in February 2003. The charge is in operation Monday to Friday (07:00-18:00) but does not apply at weekends, Bank Holidays or the days between Christmas Day and New Year's Day (DfT, 2010). The standard charge is £11.50 for each day, for each non-exempt vehicle that travels within the zone. The Penalty Charge Notice for non-payment is currently at £130; which is discounted to £65, or increased to £195 depending on promptness of payment (TfL, 2014c).

The CC applies to all vehicles entering the Congestion Zone, but the following vehicles are exempt from the Charge (TfL, 2014c):

- Motorbikes, mopeds and bicycles
- London licensed minicabs and taxis
- Emergency services' vehicles (including those used for lifeboat haulage, HM Coastguard purposes and certain Port of London Authority vehicles, NHS, ambulance, fire and police)
- Ministry of Defence (MoD) vehicles
- NHS vehicles that are exempt from Vehicle Excise Duty (VED)
- Some operational vehicles used by the Local Authorities within or partly within the charging zone and the Royal Parks Agency
- Vehicles used by disabled persons that are exempt from VED
- Disabled passenger-carrying vehicles exempt from VED
- Vehicles with nine or more seats licensed as a bus
- Breakdown vehicles used to provide roadside assistance or recovery services operated by accredited organisations

In addition, residents living in or just outside the charging zone receive a 90% discount. In April 2014, the Mayor of London confirmed that there would be an Ultra Low Emission Discount (ULED) for all electric vehicles and those that emit 75g/km or less of CO₂ and meet the Euro 5 emission standard for air quality (TfL, 2014c).

The CC aims to reduce congestion within Central London and was designed to encourage motorists to adopt other modes of transport as well as raise investment funds for London's transport system. Its objectives are to contribute directly to the achievement of four transport priorities, as per London's wider Major's Transport Strategy (pre-2010) of (TfL, 2008):

- Reducing congestion (and improving air quality);
- Making significant improvements to bus services;
- Improving journey time reliability for car users;
- Making the distribution of goods and services more efficient.

Relation to Energy Efficiency

Although energy efficiency is not a direct aim of the CC, it has indirect beneficial impacts in terms of promoting the use of more efficient vehicles, and modes of transport such as buses, bicycles and walking. Although research into the impacts of the CC are limited, traffic entering the charging zone fell by, and remains at around 15% lower than pre-charging levels. Monitoring of traffic levels has also shown that the CC scheme reduced traffic congestion in the zone by around 30% (TfL, 2014b). Furthermore, there appears to have been some reductions in road collisions and vehicular emissions of CO₂ and other atmospheric pollutants since the introduction of the CC scheme; although other factors mean that there has been no specific measurable impact on local air quality (London, 2010). As required by law, approximately £1.2 billion in net revenue (46% of gross revenue) has been invested in London's transport network (TfL, 2014a); including £960 million on bus network improvements, £102 million on roads and bridges, £70 million on road safety, £51 million on local transport/borough plans and £36 million on sustainable transport and the environment (TfL, 2014b).

In terms of further consideration of energy efficiency within the scheme, whilst it was first introduced as an economic instrument aimed at decreasing congestion, in 2009, the then Mayor of London stated an aim to transform the charge into a mixed economic and environmental tool; through a £25 charge for cars emitting a high level of CO₂ being introduced (Tochtermann, 2008). The current Mayor of London (2015) scrapped this charge as it was felt discriminatory and without a significant positive economic impact. However, since then, as noted above, the ULED has been introduced and is likely to help encourage the use of ULEVs in some way. In addition, further expansion of the CC zone could help increase the energy efficiency benefits, although a Western Expansion Zone was removed, mainly due to economic reasons.

Interaction between objectives

London's CC has similar objectives (in terms of encouraging alternative modes of transport, particularly public transport) as other energy efficiency economic policy instruments (both national and local) which include measures such as the cycle to work scheme and the Low Emission Bus Scheme. In addition, local energy efficiency initiatives within the city of London itself have been implemented in parallel to the CC in order to achieve the greater overall aims of London's Mayor's Transport Strategy (MTS). Such initiatives include the London Cycling Campaign and the Low Emission Zone (LEZ).

Interaction between target groups

Overall, the London CC scheme targets all private vehicle (passenger and freight) users (except those with exemptions as stated above), and as such, has the same target groups as many other transport-related energy efficiency policy instruments and measures. Such instruments include dissemination and awareness (EcoDriving Training), voluntary approaches (Freight Transport Association Logistics Carbon Reduction Scheme), economic (Local Sustainable Transport Fund), and regulatory (VED and road transport codes).

Interaction between Rules-Influencing Mechanisms

The CC combines both penalties for non-compliance and exemptions for certain vehicles. In terms of energy efficiency, the exemption for ULEVs provides an interlink with national economic energy efficiency instruments that incentivise the use of ULEVs. However, it is unlikely that the CC will have a significant effect on the ULEV market.

Interaction between the Implementation Network / governance structures

Transport for London (TfL) is responsible for the CC scheme in terms of implementation, including enforcement. The CC scheme is part of the wider Mayor's Transport Strategy for London, which is set by the Greater London Authority (GLA), in partnership with the TfL, the DfT, Network Rail and the 33 London Boroughs. Any changes in design and structure are undertaken by the GLA and the Mayor of London, with input from the relevant partners. On a day-to-day basis, the private company, IBM is the main service provider for the CC scheme, as well as the Low Emission Zone (LEZ). The service provider contract is subject to a competitive tendering process, to ensure cost effectiveness and quality is ensured. By having the same service provider for both the CC scheme and the LEZ, administrative and operational costs are also minimised. Vehicles entering the zones have their Vehicle Registration Number (VRN) read by cameras, which is then checked against a database of those who have paid in advance or who are exempt. Payment can be made before, on or 24 hours after travel in the zone, and through a number of ways; by an automated payment system (monthly direct debit), telephone, text message, online or by post (DfT, 2010). Due to the majority of the administration and operation of the CC scheme being online, the administrative burden of the scheme is minimal.

Costs of around £162million (equivalent to £25million annually over 10 years) were incurred during the implementation of the CC scheme; mainly on traffic management measures, communications and public information, systems set-up and management (Evans, 2007). In 2006-07, the administration and operational costs were £90million (TfL, 2008). The CC scheme is economically feasible, and decisions on amendments to the scheme are primarily based on economic benefits.

REFERENCES

- IEA (2014): Capturing the multiple benefits of energy efficiency. URL: <https://www.iea.org/Textbase/npsum/MultipleBenefits2014SUM.pdf> (2015-05-28)
- ASA. (2014). *ASA Ruling on The Green Deal Finance Company Ltd* [Online]. Available: https://www.asa.org.uk/Rulings/Adjudications/2014/5/The-Green-Deal-Finance-Company-Ltd/SHP_ADJ_247637.aspx#.VcSZ6fIVhuB.
- CCC (2014). Meeting Carbon Budgets – 2014 Progress Report to Parliament. *In*: Change, C. o. C. (ed.). Available: https://www.theccc.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2014/07/CCC-Progress-Report-2014_web_2.pdf
- Darby, S. (2005). The decent homes programme: Background material H for the 40% House report. *In*: Environmental Change Institute, U. o. O. (ed.). Available: http://www.eci.ox.ac.uk/research/energy/downloads/40house/background_doc_h.pdf
- DCLG (2006). A Decent Home: Definition and guidance for implementation. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/7812/138355.pdf
- DCLG (2015a). English Housing Survey: Households. Annual report on England's households, 2013-14. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/446145/EHS_Households_2013-14.pdf
- DCLG & HCA (2015). 2010 to 2015 government policy: rented housing sector. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/2010-to-2015-government-policy-rented-housing-sector/2010-to-2015-government-policy-rented-housing-sector#appendix-5-decent-homes-refurbishing-social-housing>
- DCLG, D., DECC,. (2015b). 2010 to 2015 government policy: household energy.
- DECC (2011). UK Renewable Energy Roadmap. London: Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/48128/2167-uk-renewable-energy-roadmap.pdf
- DECC (2012). The Energy Efficiency Strategy: The Energy Efficiency Opportunity in the UK. London: Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/65603/6928-the-energy-efficiency-strategy-statistical-strat.pdf
- DECC (2014). UK National Energy Efficiency Action Plan. London: Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/307993/uk-national-energy-efficiency-action-plan.pdf

- DECC (2015a). Domestic Green Deal, Energy Company Obligation and Insulation Levels in Great Britain, Quarterly report. Statistical Release. *In: Change, D. o. E. a. C. (ed.)*. London
- DECC (2015b). Domestic Renewable Heat Incentive: Changes to Eligibility. London: DECC. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/403636/2015_Dom-RHI_Regs_Changes_Info_Sheet-5_February_2015.pdf
- DECC (2015c). Explanatory memorandum to the energy efficiency (private rented property) (England and Wales) Regulations 2015 2015 No. 0000 and The energy efficiency (domestic private rented property) order 2015 2015 No. 0000 *In: Government, U. (ed.)*. Available: http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukdsi/2015/9780111128343/pdfs/ukdsiem_9780111128343_en.pdf
- DfT (2010). Congestion charge factsheet. Available: <https://tfl.gov.uk/cdn/static/cms/documents/congestion-charge-factsheet.pdf>
- DfT (2012). Guidance: Renewable transport fuels obligation. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/renewable-transport-fuels-obligation>
- DfT (2013). Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation Draft Post-Implementation Review *In: Transport, D. f. (ed.)*. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/266390/rtfo-consultation-document.pdf
- DfT (2014). Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation: Post Implementation Review. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/307437/impact-assessment-pir.pdf
- DfT (2015). Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation. Annual Report 2013-14 *In: Transport, D. f. (ed.)*. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/415132/cm-9026_accessible.pdf
- DfT, DVSA, OLEV & VCA (2015). 2010 to 2015 government policy: transport emissions. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/2010-to-2015-government-policy-transport-emissions/2010-to-2015-government-policy-transport-emissions>
- Energy and Climate Change Committee (ECCC) (2014). The Green Deal: watching brief (part 2). Third Report of Session 2014-15. *In: Commons, H. o. (ed.)*. Available: <http://www.publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm201415/cmselect/cmenergy/348/348.pdf>
- Environment, Food and Rural Affairs Committee (EFRAC) (2008). Energy efficiency and fuel poverty. Third report of session 2008-09. *In: Commons, H.o. (ed.)*. Available: <http://www.publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm200809/cmselect/cmenvfru/37/37.pdf>
- Evans, R. (2007). Central London Congestion Charging Scheme: ex-post evaluation of the quantified impacts of the original scheme. *In: London, T. f. (ed.) Congestion charging*. London: Congestion Charging Modelling and Evaluation Team. Available: <https://tfl.gov.uk/cdn/static/cms/documents/ex-post-evaluation-of-quantified-impacts-of-original-scheme.pdf>

- GDFC. (2015). *Green Deal: energy saving for your home* [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/green-deal-energy-saving-measures/overview>.
- HM Government (2011). *Creating growth, cutting carbon: making sustainable local transport happen*. London: HM Government. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/3890/making-sustainable-local-transport-happen-whitepaper.pdf
- HM Government (2015). *Cutting the cost of keeping warm – a fuel poverty strategy for England*. London: HM Government. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/408644/cutting_the_cost_of_keeping_warm.pdf
- London, M. o. (2010). *Mayor's Transport Strategy* [Online]. London. Available: <http://www.london.gov.uk/priorities/transport/publications/mayors-transport-strategy>.
- National Audit Office (2010). *The decent homes programme*. Available: <http://www.nao.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2010/01/0910212es.pdf>
- ODPM (2004). *Housing Health and Safety Rating System. Enforcement Guidance*. In: Minister, O. o. t. D. P. (ed.). Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/7853/safetyratingsystem.pdf
- Pitt, V. (2014). *Barker admits Green Deal forecast was 'spectacularly wrong'*. *Building.co.uk* [Online]. Available: <http://www.building.co.uk/news/barker-admits-green-deal-forecast-was-%E2%80%98spectacularly-wrong%E2%80%99/5065961.article>.
- TfL (2008). *Central London Congestion Charging. Impacts monitoring. Sixth Annual Report*. In: London, M. o. (ed.). London. Available: <https://tfl.gov.uk/cdn/static/cms/documents/central-london-congestion-charging-impacts-monitoring-sixth-annual-report.pdf>
- TfL (2014a). *TfL's report to the mayor on the congestion charging scheme variation order consultation*. In: stakeholders, C. L. c. c. s. c. w. t. p. a. (ed.). Available: <https://tfl.gov.uk/cdn/static/cms/documents/cc-changes-consultation-2014-mayors-report.pdf>
- TfL. (2014b). *Transport for London announces new Congestion Charge and Low Emission Zone service provider* [Online]. Available: <https://tfl.gov.uk/info-for/media/press-releases/2014/january/transport-for-london-announces-new-congestion-charge-and-low-emission-zone-service-provider>.
- TfL (2014c). *What do you need to know about Congestion Charging?* In: London, M. o. (ed.). London. Available: <https://tfl.gov.uk/cdn/static/cms/documents/tfl-cc-generic-leaflet.pdf>
- Tochtermann, L. (2008). *Congestion Charging: A tool to tackle congestion in UK cities?* In: Cities, C. f. (ed.). Available: <http://www.centreforcities.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/08-10-02-Congestion-Charging.pdf>
- UK Parliament. (2010). *Beyond Decent Homes - Communities and Local Government Committee* [Online]. Available: <http://www.publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm200910/cmselect/cmcomloc/60/6005.htm>.

UKGBC. (2014). *Written Evidence submitted by The UK Green Building Council (GRE0003)* [Online].

Available:

<http://data.parliament.uk/writtenevidence/committeeevidence.svc/evidencedocument/energy-and-climate-change-committee/green-deal-watching-brief-part-2/written/5942.html>.